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**Deciphering Southern Thailand's violence:
organisation and insurgent practices of BRN-
Coordinate**

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*For all those, who lost their lives
in Southern Thailand's insurgency.*

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List of abbreviations

Ajak	Ahli Jawatan Kampung (Village Working Committee)
BRN	Barisan Revolusi Nasional (National Revolutionary Front)
BRN-C	Barisan Revolusi Nasional Coordinate
COIN	Counterinsurgency
DPP	Dewan Pimpinan Parti (Party Leadership Council)
DSI	Department of Special Investigation
EGAT	Electricity Generating Authority of Thailand
ETA	Basque Fatherland and Liberty
FLN	Algerian National Liberation Front
GAM	Free Aceh Movement
GMIP	Gerakan Mujahideen Islam Patani
IRA	Irish Republican Army
JI	Jemaah Islamiyah
LRA	Lord's Resistance Army
LTTE	Liberation Tigers of Tamil Ealam
MILF	Moro Islamic Liberation Front
MNLF	Moro National Liberation Front
OIC	Organisation of Islamic Countries
PIRA	Provisional Irish Republican Army
PULO	Patani United Liberation Organisation
RKK	Runda Kumpulan Kecil (Small Group Patrol/ Commando)
SBPAC	Southern Border Provinces Coordination Centre
TKB	Terrorism Knowledge Base

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This book attempts to reveal the structure of a secret organisation and is therefore, in some parts, reliant on intelligence information which maybe less reliable than other sources. I therefore accept full responsibility for the written content. However, it was the lack of in depth research on BRN-Coordinate that convinced me to tackle such an under-researched topic in the first place.

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1. Introduction

Since the outbreak of violence in Thailand's Malay Muslim dominated three provinces (Narathiwat, Yala and Pattani) in 2004, although much has been written about the region and the causes of the conflict, when it comes to the perpetrators of violent acts few substantial data has been gained. Description as well as interpretation of data is impeded by a cloud of "nameless" violence that renders the definition of actors and the interests involved difficult. Whereas the acts of state violence against the Malay minority can be identified more or less easily, the motives and organisation of those on the "other side" are even more heavily cloaked in secrecy, deception and speculation.

Whereas scientific observers, state agencies and the local population must make sense of violent acts, they all face the problem of uncertainty: Who are the perpetrators of violence on the "Malay side"? What are their motives? Are they simply the victims of harassment or the failed policies of the Thai Nation state that pursue a bloodstained campaign of revenge? Are we facing a new kind of agency – a leaderless jihad engaging in nothing but nihilist violence? Or do they deliberately aim to exhaust Thailand in a "bleeding war" of the kind that defeated the French in Algeria or the Soviet Union in Afghanistan? The apparent lack of tangible political objectives on the rebels' side raises the question as to how far they can be considered rational at all. For example, why is civilian lethality so high in contrast to the former insurgencies in the region, and why are more Malays killed than Buddhists?

Experts also disagree on the question as to whether insurgents are driven by transnational Jihadism or local nationalism (Harish 2006, International Crisis Group 2005). Equally unknown is the question of organisation: Are perpetrators organised in more or less uncoordinated cells and hierarchical organisations, or is violence a reaction to changing political constellations (McCargo 2006)? Moreover, how strong is the (local and international) support insurgents receive (Abuza 2009; Davis 2010)? More than elsewhere in Southeast Asia, the conflict in the three provinces of Narathiwat, Yala and Pattani resembles a landscape of rumours, which seems to defy empirically founded scientific explanations of cause and effect. In other words, we are still dealing with a black box, or as Appadurai (2006) puts it, violence with neither a definable sender, nor a graspable message, that which resembles a "Dadaist nightmare".

The purpose of this study is to analyse the communicative dimension of Southern Thailand's insurgency, taking Barisan Revolusi Nasional Coordinate (BRN-Coordinate), the most important of the separatist groups, as a focal point. This look into the "black box" of BRN-Coordinate argues that although the group is deeply entrenched in local villages and schools, the fear of government infiltration forces the group to conceal its activities behind a "veil of secrecy". Collective violence is staged as sudden violence, while its architects hide behind the image of violence as a popular, justified reaction to state neglect and suppression. Apparently, the rationale of this strategy is to

stir up mass support for separatism, inter-communal tension and to induce ruthless suppression by the Thais. This would make international recognition of the group's leadership virtually unavoidable.

Moreover, the Thai government is pressured to give in to certain demands of the insurgents. This strategy, albeit based on clandestinity, depends on communication: it must create fear and cooperation, it must mobilise support and drive the Thai state into an escalation of violence. A crucial part in all of this is to recruit and socialize members, to convey a sense of legitimacy of violence that informs, guides and motivates people in the name of independence. This communication takes the form of discourses, rumours and violent acts – all of which can become symbols in themselves. It is my aim to bring clarity to this melange of insurgent violence, by pushing aside the façade of disorderly, confusing bloodshed and clearly identifying the networks and organisational structures through which the group communicates - both internally and with local Malay audiences.

1.1. Theoretical framework

'Guerrilla', or 'small war', is a type of irregular warfare that emerges when rebels are unable to confront states, which can draw on formalized armies and heavy weaponry such as artillery, on equal terms. Instead of direct confrontation with government forces, rebels turn into small, lightly armed squads that emerge at the time of attack, then disappear immediately, almost ghost-like, into their civilian hideouts. Moreover, such warfare often involves attacks against civilians, blurring the division between combatants and non-combatants. Such asymmetric tactics are as old as human history (Kalyvas 2010). Whereas the term "guerrilla" was originally used to describe the early 19th century Spanish resistance against Napoleon's occupation, the models of the "people's war" were developed in the seminal writings (and partly practice) of Mao Zedong, Che Guevara, Régis Debray and General Giap, among others. From there onwards more attention was paid to the political, or better revolutionary, dimension of irregular warfare (alongside its military side). It was during this time that term "insurgency" emerged (Kalyvas 2010).

The successful insurgencies in China, Cuba and Vietnam seemed to prove a "revolutionary belief" that even militarily inferior people can draw or defeat a stronger foe, if they only are willing to accept setbacks and high casualties over a longer period of time (Aron & Löwenthal 1986; Smith 2008). In other words, insurgency was a politico-military strategy that offered a panacea for ills like colonialism, underdevelopment and poverty. In the Che Guerava cult among the left-wing intellectuals guerrilla war and revolution were equated (Münkler 1992). Whereas since the establishment of the Westphalian system industrial warfare was a monopoly of nation states, guerrilla warfare was the antithesis to interstate war, which offered the

possibility of suspending power-differentials, providing sub-state collectives with human agency at the fringes of domination.

Unfortunately, with some exceptions, the social sciences have largely neglected issues of warfare in general and insurgent groups in particular (Kalyvas 2005). One reason for the general absence might lie in the problematic nature of social science research on violence in general. Research on civil wars, revolutions and other types of collective violence has been narrowly focused on its root causes rather than on its forms. Since the seminal work of Gurr (1970), quantitative studies, which attempted to explain collective violence with the help of complex factor models, have been developed. The underlying ontological assumption of these models was typically that violence is a deviation from modernity, which seemed to have ended with the process of civilisation (Elias 1997), or the establishment of equilibrium models of society (Parsons 1952). Violence is assumed to be rooted in conditions of either social anomy or deprivation. A popular starting point is, for instance, the assumption that different “social pathologies” (such as uncontrolled social change, drug consumption, unemployment, lack of democracy, unequal distribution of resources between different ethnic groups) add up, and, at some point, lead to a volcanic outburst of violence (Trotha 1997). For a long time, class conflicts were said to be the basis for revolutions or rebellions. Marx, for example, argued that the industrial proletariat’s shared experience of exploitation would form the ground for collective revolutionary, i.e. violent, action. However, the history of European revolutions as well as anti-colonial movements would later show that students and rural working people actually featured more regularly in radical social movements (Lipset 1993).

However, the overall weaknesses of this approach are twofold: On the one hand, it takes attention away from the form and problematic nature of violent collective action and the communicative processes connected to it, which were seen as emerging quasi-automatically as a consequence of structural inequality in order to elevate the suppressed masses from poverty and exploitation. On the other, even sophisticated factor models and econometric explanations of violence, suffer from fundamental methodological flaws (Kalyvas 2008). Leaving out the role of collective action, these models cannot explain how the same violence-inducing circumstances may lead to the outbreak of violence in one context, but not in others.

In Southern Thailand, for example, class-based approaches – either defined in the narrow sense as access to land or in the wider sense of income - cannot adequately explain the Malay Muslim insurgency. Though the region belongs to the poorest in Thailand, empirical evidence on insurgents shows that participants in the insurgency come from a variety of socio-economic backgrounds (see Chapter 3). Whereas the rural population features prominently, insurgents are also found among school owners, Islamic scholars and university students. Though professionals are fewer in number,

they occupy important positions within BRN-Coordinate, especially in recruitment. Moreover, qualifying such structuralist explanations is the fact that an overwhelming majority of Malay Muslims do not join or actively support the insurgency, though many may hide sympathetic sentiments towards the insurgency for several reasons.

Since the 1980s, research on violence and the understanding of armed groups has undergone a shift, influenced by the so-called “cultural turn”. The charisma of the “people’s war” went into decline as most of the people’s wars, especially those in Latin America, failed to fulfil the prophecy of revolution. Moreover, in 1979 Afghan villagers openly began to lead another kind of insurgency, namely the one that was now directed against economic and social modernisation programs that were initiated in Kabul. Fighting not for a revolutionary agenda, but for the preservation of the old order, the figure of the insurgent turned from a “catechist of modernisation” to a “partisan of tradition” (Münkler 1992). This also raised the question of the communicative dimension of armed groups. Whereas formerly insurgents such as the Vietcong had clear political programs that combined nationalist as well as socialist elements, the mujaheddin in Afghanistan lacked such communicable programs (Pike 1968). As the idea of socialist revolution increasingly lost its charismatic appeal, the transnational framing of insurgencies was now more and more provided in the context of rising culturalism. However, for many, the partisan of tradition remained an ambivalent figure. In the past the ethos of socialism had “intellectually upgraded”, the ideological poverty and contradictions of nationalism. In other words, socialism provided a basis for a common understanding, even solidarity (and sometimes scientific interest), between many Western intellectuals and insurgents. Now even the political conservatives in the United States could hardly understand the anti-modernist and anti-centralist stance of Afghan insurgents, though the US government still supported them in their fight against Soviet imperialism (Münkler 1992).

Moreover, the increased targeting of civilians (e.g. kidnapping of civilians, and hijacking of airliners etc.) in the 1970s had important consequences for the knowledge production on insurgents: As the “partisan of tradition” lost its semantic struggle in the West (the freedom fighter, on many occasions, became a terrorist), mainstream social science lost its last grain of interest in irregular warfare. Rather than focusing on the issue of warfare from a social science perspective, the studies focused, if at all, primarily on the onset of civil war on the one hand, and, on the other hand, on its effects. Consequently, insurgencies were left to the military and its “organic intellectuals”, who reduced the issue of insurgency to one of military details such as tactics, and firepower (Kalyvas 2005).

Yet although social science and military studies had separated in contempt at least since the Vietnam war (in contrast to WWII, when, for example, German intellectuals supported the Allied Forces) both public and expert discourses on insurgents shared

similar assumptions: whereas the conventional insurgent was considered political, moral and, importantly, rational, the insurgent of tradition was considered not to be a subject of rational analyses and rather deprived of morality. This re-conceptualization was expressed in the shift of discourses from “insurgency” to “terrorism” (Stampnitzky 2009). Not only was the terrorist not considered rational, but there also was a belief that he “is – must be – psychologically warped, if not actually mentally deranged” (Arblaster 177: 420). In other words, insurgency was subjected to a de-legitimizing claim of being apolitical, which furthered the tendency towards a purely technical analysis of irregular warfare.

It was only when 9/11 brought insurgency back into America’s territorial and symbolic centre that interest in the issue was renewed. But underlying this interest was the premise that a new terrorism had emerged, which was characterized not only by the shift from nationalism and socialism to religious motivations, an increase in indiscriminate lethality, but also by a change from hierarchical forms of organisation towards network-based organisation. This rendered the phenomenon even more inaccessible (Clausen et al. 1993; Lesser et al. 1999; Waldmann 1999). It seemed that the era of conventional insurgency, as developed earlier in the 20th century, had finally ended and was being replaced by what some authors labelled “new terrorism”. For instance, Hoffman (1998) argued that the abovementioned characteristics rendered the knowledge on insurgency and old terrorism obsolete:

“The growth of religious terrorism and its emergence in recent years as a driving force behind the increasing lethality of internationalism terrorism shatters some of our basic assumptions about terrorists and the violence they commit.”

Hofman 1999: 204-205

Yet, as Crenshaw (2009) convincingly argues, the declaration of the “new terrorism” paradigm is premature:¹ First, the so-called “new terrorism” is not fundamentally different from old terrorism. Empirical differences in terms of goals, methods of warfare and organisational structure are not sufficiently distinct as to allow for such a paradigmatic shift. The National Memorial Institute for the Prevention of Terrorism’s, Terrorism Knowledge Base (TKB) classified only 54 out of 124 terrorist groups as “religious”, whereas the majority are listed as nationalist groups, although it must be added that the classification between “nationalist” and “religious” is theoretically weak and hard to verify using empirical evidence (Crenshaw 2009). For example, is Hamas a nationalist or Islamist group, when it calls for an Islamic-Nation state in Palestine? In Southern Thailand such classifications are equally difficult to establish. On the level of

¹ Similarly, the distinction between old and new wars was convincingly criticized not only on empirical grounds, but also because a typology according to other criteria that appears more productive. Analytically, type of war and type of warfare shall be distinguished, with the former being classified, for example, by primary cause (e.g. international or internal), goals, worldviews or motives (‘greed vs grievance’) etc. According to Kalyvas (2005) the classification of the latter should start with an ideal-typical distinction between conventional and non-conventional warfare.

individual members, as will be shown below, both nationalist as well jihadist motivations for joining the group can be found, but as long as BRN-Coordinate remains a clandestine underground organisation it can draw on the appeal of both (Islamism-Nationalism) and avoid ideological struggles.

Second, Crenshaw points out that “new terrorists” are supposed to pursue mass casualties just ‘for the sake of their own’ and not as a means to an end, as old insurgents and terrorists groups presumably did. But as the case of the Red Army Fraction (RAF) in Germany illustrates, armed groups from earlier periods also ceased to be concerned with public support, committing violence for the sake of the group only. In other words, all armed groups and social movements, not only the religiously driven ones, which are said to replace the “mass audience” with God, are subject to the risk of inversion (Münkler 1992; Wieviorka 2004).² Turning to Southern Thailand, I will argue that BRN-Coordinate protects itself against self-referentiality by constantly monitoring the public reception of violence among Malay Muslims in the region. Third, turning to the structure of organisation, the often-claimed clear shift from vertebrate to cellular organisation (Appadurai 2006) cannot be upheld. Indeed, according to Mayntz (2004) all clandestine terrorist organisations feature a combination of hierarchical and network elements (an argument which I will come back to later).

A rather utilitarian approach towards civil wars can be found in the paradigm of the “new wars” and markets of violence, which emerged in the 1990s, diverging from the culturalist discussion on violence (Creveld 1991; Kaldor 1999). It was argued that the state’s monopoly on warfare, which marked war from the 17th until the early 20th century, was becoming increasingly undermined. Instead, warfare is now marked by greater lethality, an excessive use of violence against civilians, lower levels of weapon technology and formal organisation of violence as well as a tendency towards the commercialization of violence by a multitude of violent actors (especially non-state actors on one or more sides) within states. It is often assumed that these rational armed groups lack political goals. Instead they create spaces of everyday violence on the ground and are, on a global scale, embedded in an economy in which formal and informal aspects become increasingly intertwined (e.g. the trade of “blood diamonds”) (Elwert 1997).³

Due to a lack of conceptual clearness, a lack of data, and because the term “terrorism” is typically used in these discussions on warfare in order to delegitimise political enemies and strip them of international support (or win it), observers typically fail to distinguish terrorism from guerrilla warfare; thus one man’s freedom fighter is another man’s

² In addition, with more than 37,000 people killed, conventional armed groups such as the Sendero Luminoso in Peru have caused much higher causality rates than any terrorist group (Crenshaw 2009). In Uganda the Lord’s Resistance Army (LRA) systematically used mutilations, abductions, and unpredictable attacks as a force multiplying strategic means (Vinci 2005).

³ Clausewitz (1885) already pointed out in the 19th century that there are always actors, who profit from war.

terrorist. Although on an empirical level both phenomena are often hard to tell apart, there is no reason why we should not distinguish these fundamental types of collective violence on an analytical level. Both are, in a sense, weapons of the weak, which are employed by groups that are militarily inferior to a stronger group and, at least initially, lack mass support and hence attempt to make up for this military power differential through irregular methods of fighting. But the two can be distinguished along three dimensions (see, e.g., Waldmann 1993):

1. The Function of Violence: whereas guerrilla warfare attempts to rescind this inferiority within the logic of military destruction, terrorism chooses a different logic of violence. Guerrilla warfare employs the irregular fighting methods mentioned above in order to gain time and other resources to mobilise forces for conventional warfare, whereas terrorism refrains from engaging with the state via conventional means from the beginning, aiming rather for the psychological effects of violent action, making no distinction between combatants and non-combatants. No matter how severe the physical consequences may be, physical destruction is not the main function of terrorism. Instead, its purpose is symbolic. Acts of terrorism are an attempt to instil the idea that 'nobody is safe' from violence while highlighting the failure of the state to fulfil its most basic function, namely the physical protection of its citizens. Another second symbolic function of terrorism comprises the acting out of revenge, gloating and the raising of sympathy and as support among the population for the terrorists.

2. Social Support: terrorism is typically limited to a radical milieu of small groups (e.g. students, middle class) and hence it is often questionable as to how it is an isolated phenomenon. Guerrillas, on the contrary, mobilise the masses and base their violent campaign on broad social support (ethnic group, social class etc.).⁴

3. Territorial Dimension: with regard to the spatial dimension of violence, terrorism refrains from infiltrating larger areas. Solely relying on the shock-effect of demonstrative violence, terrorists attempt to create an image that they can attack anyone, anytime and anywhere. Since guerrillas depend on the local population, their logic is to expand the territories in which they can "move like a fish in the water", as the famous Mao dictum puts it.

Both types of violence can be used simultaneously by the same group. However, when taken together with the second and third dimensions, we can classify more easily violent groups, and therefore avoid conceptual confusion or political labels. Especially if armed groups fail to position themselves in the international public, they tend to lose their

⁴ Guerrillas can substitute the transport capacities of a conventional army through the broad support of the local population, which provide hideouts, food supplies, medical support and intelligence. Mao Zedong expressed this in the dictum of the "fish in the water". Technological advantages have made modern troops highly dependent of transport capacities and thus more vulnerable to attacks by guerrillas, who themselves would lose their advantage of mobility if they too had to draw on conventional logistics. In Zimbabwe, for example, this support has enabled the guerrillas to organise themselves effectively in semi-autonomous units (Schmidt 1999).

struggle for meaning, which can have significant consequences in terms of political support. For example, “old-style” guerrilla organisation such as the LTTE in Sri Lanka, that make regular use of terrorist violence, but which are basically guerrillas with mass mobilisation and shadowy state-structures, were successfully branded as “terrorists” by the Sri Lankan government, international media and the European Union. With regard to Southern Thailand, a similar conceptual confusion becomes apparent. Whereas Gunaratna and Archaya (2005), obviously judging from the type of violence they discern, employ the term terrorism to characterize the violence in Southern Thailand, other authors (Janes’s *World Insurgency and Terrorism* 2007) consider BRN-Coordinate’s attempts to build up mass support along wide areas and thus, rightly I would say, refer to it as an example of guerrilla-like “protracted warfare”.

Yet despite all their shortcomings the “new ...” paradigms have produced significant consequences for discussions on armed groups: First, warfare and armed groups were overlooked as phenomena in themselves: whereas until the end of the 1970s they were seen as dependent variables of structural phenomena such as class exploitation and colonialism, they are now seen, similarly, as the (irrational) outcomes of ethnic or religious sentiments. Similarly, McCargo (2008) argues that a “crisis of legitimacy” of the Thai state among Malay Muslims has a direct causal relation to the outbreak of insurgencies in the South. But such popular sentiments are unlikely to translate into protest in a quasi-automatic fashion, regime changes or revolutionary action (Prezowski 1991). Comparable structural factors may cause violence in some cases, whereas in other cases they may not.

Second, what these approaches typically overlook is the fact that without an organised alternative for collective action, contentious populations retreat into their private lives, for example, into religiosity, or they turn to weapons of the weak, which can also be violent, but then they are rather weakly coordinated (Scott 1990; Tilly 2003). Hence even illegitimate regimes (like in Burma) can be stabilized. In other words, the narrow focus on “root causes” of violence led to a neglect of the study on collective violence organisation itself, and, especially, of the role of violence specialists, who often hide their own interests behind popular views. Whereas, for example, social movement research - which has much to offer in this context - has made a shift from structural explanations to viewing collective action as a process (cf. Tarrow 2006), research on violence still has to fully conceptualize insurgent organisations as a link between the contentious individual, motives, ideas about the proper use of violence, and structural circumstances (Tilly 2003). Here the enormous diversity of warfare is largely unobserved - not to mention the fact that there are very few attempts to compare the forms of warfare and put the existing (typically descriptive) case studies of local

warfare into systematic social-scientific typologies (Kalyvas 2005; Schlichte 2009).⁵

In an attempt to bring back the research of warfare into social-scientific research, authors like Kalyvas (2005) or Weinstein (2007) argue for approaching warfare in civil wars as a phenomenon *sui generis*. Similarly, Schlichte (2009), on whom I also draw heavily in this study, points out that it is necessary to bring political sociology into the study of the formation and trajectories of armed groups in order to account for the fact that some groups succeed in the quest for political domination, whereas most fail - without being trapped within econometric reductionism or culturalist essentialism. Whereas factors like organisation or mobilisation of armed groups are surely linked to pre-war conditions, the social, political and economic environment of warfare is fundamentally different from collective action during peacetime:

First, warfare environments entail more “constraints and far less consent” (Kalyvas 2005: 89). Second, for the actors involved the stakes are significantly higher than in peaceful forms of collective action. To put it in the words of Mao Zedong, “war has its own particular characteristics and in this sense it cannot be equated with politics in general” (quoted in Kalyvas 2005: 89). Warfare alters not only society, politics and the economy, but it also creates its own organisations, interests, motives and communicative practices. It is one thing to feel sympathy for rebels, even justifying their action in a “coffee shop-talk”. Indeed, as elsewhere, there is a plethora of such talk in Thailand’s Deep South. But it is a totally different thing to actually recruit hundreds or not to speak of thousands of recruits, socialize them into a system of violence, provide them with arms and order them to shoot at a heavily equipped Thai military convoy in Narathiwat province.

Specifically, Kalyvas (2006) calls for a switch towards micro-level research in order to reveal the chief mechanisms constituting warfare as collective action. Since any form of enduring collective violence (even uncoordinated scattered attacks) presupposes a violence-fostering milieu, roles, communication and a set of rules. Violence cannot be based upon emotions alone. As Elwert (2003) points out, the emergence of warfare implies the formation of specific new concepts, consciousness, experiences, and social positions. It also indicates the creation of new social systems that link positions with actions thus fostering the emergence of new social groups that constitute a distinct life world. At the core of these systems we find armed groups that, following Schlichte, can be conceptualized as:

“[...] figurations, that is smaller settings, groups or less structured collectives, and as ensembles of interdependent individuals. These

⁵ Another reason for this deadlock is the danger of doing research in conflict areas and the difficulty of collecting reliable data, although recently more and more social scientists are willing to take the risks of “fieldwork under fire” (Nordstrom & Robben 1995). At the same time the involvement of social scientists in the “war on terror”, as so-called embedded anthropologists in Iraq or Afghanistan, for example, has obstructed objectivity in approaching terrorism and guerrilla warfare (Perugini 2008).

individuals are linked by asymmetric power balances, as they exchange for favors or commodities, as they maintain emotional ties, and even as they fight.”

Schlichte 2009: 17

Based on the sociology of Elias, Schlichte argues that the figuration approach avoids a narrow understanding of armed groups, which either reduces them to the actions of individuals (as, for example, in behavioral sciences, rational choice theory or parts of psychology) or to a consequence of structural conditions. Instead, the relations between interdependent individuals are seen as the formative element of armed groups. Power relations within figurations are not equilibria, but rather precarious balances. This does not mean that individuals are equal, but that one side never exclusively dominates, although, as will be shown later, secret armed groups like BRN-Coordinate attempt to exert total control over their members. More or less constant shifts of power, and conflicts as well as balancing acts of consent are at the core of these organisational processes. If armed groups are not able to handle these conflicts, they risk disintegration from within, or infiltration by external actors.

Beyond these common dynamics of armed figuration, we find significant differences. Weinstein (2007), for example, takes up the question as to why some armed groups act in a predatory fashion, suppressing, illtreating and exploiting the local population, while other groups show a significant deal of restraint and ideological orientation. Instead of plumbings for an either “greed” or “grievance” distinction, he deduces two types of insurgencies: (1) opportunistic rebellions in which participation involves short-term goals (e.g. economic resources) and undisciplined predatory behaviour by insurgents, and (2) activist rebellions that are about dedication to a higher cause, no matter how well formulated, involving the investment of time, risk and sometimes money for the rebel’s cause. Weinstein correlates both types with a distinction between recruitment strategies and motivation for joining:

“[...] recruitment strategies depend a great deal on the incentives that are likely to motivate individual participation. [...] High commitment individuals are investors. [...] Low investment individuals are consumers.”

Weinstein 2007: 8-9

He explains these distinctions through different initial endowment patterns. Whereas low commitment rebellions can draw on given resources (local exploitable resources, international support) and are thus independent of popular support, the high commitment rebels are without such endowments and hence seek cooperative relations with their “host community” in which they mobilise recruits and other local resources necessary for their cause. Hence in the latter case insurgents behave in a constrained and disciplined way, exerting only selective violence against the host population. In the

former they see the local population as an object for exploitation and, we might add, for nihilist violence.

Yet Weinstein's restriction to a path-dependency model of armed groups based on their initial endowment not only overlooks that the auto-dynamics of violence can lead to a change in motives - many state-builders emerged as social bandits (Tilly 1984), whereas other political insurgents may end up as entrepreneurs of violence (Waldmann 1999)- but he also leaves out the role of the communicative context of insurgencies. The latter question takes us to Schlichte (2009) again, who reminds us of the complex relationship between violence and legitimacy, which, beside the question of everyday tactical operations, is a key dynamic at the centre of communicative relations within armed groups. Activist rebels, to put it in Weinstein's terms, must generate a certain degree of legitimacy among different possible audiences (internal, local and international public), as they depend on support from the local population (either overt or covert in nature like in Southern Thailand) and/or international support. Probably even more important is the legitimacy among group members themselves, as they have to recruit fighters, uphold their motivation, avoid internal conflicts and protect themselves against the delegitimizing emotional effects of violence (such as fear or guilt over indiscriminate killings) that contradict the group's moral ambitions.

For this purpose, armed groups can draw on and communicate different types of legitimacies. For example, groups that are able to achieve territorial control gain basic legitimacy from the local population simply by ending the state of war and restoring a kind of preliminary order, even though they might not have the normative or political consensus of the local population (Schlichte 2009). As BRN-Coordinate still remains a highly secretive organisation and has hence not achieved such territorial control against the Thai state, a second type of legitimacy becomes more important for them: charismatic ideas or political programs promoted by armed groups that exert a high degree of appeal. Regularly, but not always, such charismatic mobilization is explicitly located in the transcendental sphere, but it also plays a role in achieving more secular goals such as national liberation or socialism. For a certain period of time these ideas and the leaders and organisations associated with them exert a sort of emotional function that takes people out of their mundane existence and into the "extraordinary" ("Außeralltäglichkeit"). Weber's definition of charisma refers to:

"[...] a certain quality of an individual personality by virtue of which he is considered extraordinary and treated as endowed with supernatural, superhuman, or at least specifically exceptional powers or qualities. These are such as are not accessible to the ordinary person, but are regarded as of divine origin or as exemplary, and on the basis of them the individual concerned is treated as a "leader". In primitive circumstances this peculiar kind of quality is thought of as resting on magical powers, whether of prophets, persons with a reputation for

therapeutical or legal wisdom, leaders in the hunt, or heroes in war.”

Weber 1978: 241

Whole organisations can bask in the direct charisma of the divine, when they, like BRN-Coordinate, claim a special link to God and argue that their armed struggle to free Patani from the rule of the Thai unbelievers is the fulfilling of God’s will on earth. In the context of a charismatic idea like the jihad, the group’s secretive aura as well as the dimension of the unknown fosters imagination and hence only boosts the appeal for members, as well as for some external observers. In other words, we are dealing with a charismatic organisation, whose cohesion depend on a form of institutionalized power as well as on an emotional hope for a new order coming from the hand of the chosen ones associated with the organisation.⁶

Weber’s concept of charisma is also a useful conceptual tool with regard to the question of BRN-Coordinate’s organisational structure, which was raised at the beginning. The few existing scholarly accounts on the group disagree on its precise organisational nature. It is either framed as a classical vertical organisation - a formal set of social relations that pursues a collective goal, with specific determined roles, central steering, and a clear boundary that separates it from its environment – or as loosely connected network. I argue that it is more useful to approach BRN-Coordinate as a hybrid that simultaneously combines a hierarchical organisation at its core with loosely connected elements on the ground. This reduces the need for communication among units and therefore enables insurgents to act autonomously in matters like planning attacks, recruiting new members, and gathering intelligence. Whereas the former delivers the advantages of centrally steered activities, which crucially affects the group’s capacity to act violently, the latter enables the group to cloak its campaign of protracted warfare behind a veil of secrecy and hence protects it from government infiltration.

The result is a dialectical system of loose coupling that is at the same time deliberate and spontaneous, centrally determined and indeterminate. Yet not all actions are indeterminate, as a certain code of conduct exists even in the indeterminate sphere and not all elements of the group and not all practices enjoy the same autonomy. For example, assassinations of fellow Malays Muslims and the issuing of threatening letters have to be sanctioned by superiors. But if not all action is steered and monitored by the centre, how can the organisation guarantee the same practices and protect itself from falling apart by internal power struggles? Indeed BRN-Coordinate members seem to act according to an unknown script, speak a similar language and put their lives in the

⁶ Social movements typically start off with this charisma and then transform it into a more rigid, hierarchical and dogmatic organisation, a process called “Veralltäglichung” (routinization) by Weber (1978). During this transformation to a more formalized form they tend to loose the appeal of the extraordinary. However, as Eisenstadt (1995) pointed out, institutionalization and charisma are not necessarily contradictory. Successful organisations can “re-new” themselves and gain the mobilizing momentum they lost by drawing on newly emerging charismatic narratives that are often located in transnational public spheres.

hands of others by cooperating with unknown fellow insurgents. The answer lies in a combination of factors. The group makes use of a standardizing training programme that socializes its members into the methods, mode of thought and general objectives of the group, which are then applied by members individually. At least at the rank-and-file level this coordination is driven not by self-interest, but by the members' identification with or high commitment to the group, both which are especially strong when coupled with the mobilising power of charisma (Elwert 1999). At the same time BRN-Coordinate makes use of (peer) surveillance and sanctions for defection. Such a combination of seemingly contradictory mechanisms of internal and external control is crucial in explaining the cohesion of social figurations (Elias 1997).

The group refrains from directly taking credit for its actions in public. This brings into consideration the "communication side" of violence. Here we will switch from the performer's perspective to the witness's perspective (Riches 1986; Reemtsma 2008). It is through the communication of violent conflicts, that violence is institutionalised in society. Violence can become a symbol of communication in itself. While a violent act destroys the relation between the performer and his victim, it also creates a credible and powerful threat - that of further violence. Hence, a power relation between the performer and the audience(s) emerges. Importantly, this meaning of violence implies the "option" for action. For example, if a Malay villager, (who initially does not support the insurgency and considers their use of violence unjustified), witnesses the ruthless murder of a fellow innocent Malay civilians by a small group of people wearing Thai military uniforms, he is likely to change his opinion. The power of the violent act against his fellow Malay has the effect of turning our civilian into an activist who is now in favour of those, whose violence is now perceived to be an act of rightful revenge. The vision and symbolism of the Thai military against the Malay civilian has a persuasive and positive effect for the insurgency. On the other hand, it is certain that had the Malay villager in this case known that the assassins were actually insurgents and the victim was a civilian, who had collaborated with the government, he would not have so easily been swayed.

Tilly (2003) argues that in analysing violence, one should not fall into the trap of defending, romanticising or condemning a violent actor after describing him. Rather, it is more useful to adopt an approach that identifies the causality within the "negotiated interactions" between violent actors. However, coming from a local perspective and primary experience, such neutrality is hard to maintain because in a climate of fear and distrust people develop necessary coping strategies. One of these strategies is the shifting of blame in an attempt to "make sense" of the violence. In Southern Thailand, there is no "neutral" public sphere or body that is able to give an in-depth analysis or a "neutral view". Any possibility of neutrality has to counter the strong and popular local rumour networks which are often even divided among ethnic lines (Apitzsch 2010).

These networks, whose views are based on hearsay and ideologies of revenge, were the only available “vehicles” for interpreting the violence and delivering the accounts of it and thus neutrality was virtually nonexistent.

When the state in Southern Thailand, known for its power abuses in the past, loses its link with and trust from local society, and when insurgents hide in the underground, without any sign of existence, the state usually ends up on the losing side in this process of blame. Officials may exert a certain degree of restraint against the use of violence. But regardless, a uniform will always be visible. The partisan, on the other hand, draws on his invisibility and local propaganda machinery that, linked to communities, is better equipped to manipulate the reception of violence. The partisan usually enjoys the benefit of people’s lack of trust in the state.

Global flows of ideas such as the “war on terror” and transnational identities have made the deciphering of violent conflicts even harder (Das & Kleinman 2000). As Edmund Leach pointed out, violence can be the highest form of social exclusion. If one group engages in violence against another, the lines between both groups are demarcated through the acts of violence. In other words, through its various discourses violence becomes social. While violence is universal, the perceptions of it are specific to historical circumstances. Here, collective identities, memories, ideas of revenge and honour as well as holy texts are crucial to the formation of perceptions of violence (Orywal 1996; Schmidt & Schröder 2001). However, the perceptions of violence vary and its legitimacy is always contested by some actors (Riches 1986). As will be shown more than once in this work, there are many Malays, even whole Malay communities, who resist the insurgents, question their legitimacy or simply take a neutral stand. Whether we can speak of “multiple realisms” (Das & Kleinman 2000) or should question the term “reality” at all, such as in the Actor-Network-Theory (Latour 1993) is another question. What is clear though is that the perceptions of violence must be disaggregated, just as violence itself should be. It should be the task of social science to identify networks and organisations that interpret violence, question how these networks define the meanings of violence, and then integrate them within existing discourses and rationalities.

Therefore, the second chapter will begin with a description of the organisational architecture and aims of BRN-Coordinate, explaining how, despite reduced communication due to “secrecy”, a sophisticated division of labour within the insurgent practices is sustained. In brief, I will argue that BRN-Coordinate is neither a loose network nor a pure hierarchical organisation, but rather, similar to the Provisional Irish Republican Army (IRA), a hybrid form: “a cellular-based, hierarchically-organised authoritarian structure” (Horgan & Taylor 1997: 3). Although its village-based cells retain some degree of autonomy (a result of the group’s obsession with clandestinity that protects it from government infiltration) they are basically part of a sophisticated

hierarchical organisation, which comprises a political and military wing. Their structure is centralised and subject to a tightly organised chain of command, which, by working together, facilitates insurgent practices.

The third chapter focuses on the ability of BRN-Coordinate to consistently generate and sustain collective violent action. The careful recruitment of members and the subsequent process of socialization will be examined, emphasising inter-subjective symbolism. This symbolic ground is crucial for the institutionalisation of armed groups for three reasons: first, it forms a basis of legitimacy for the internal power structures of the group; second, it legitimises the use of violence; and third, it facilitates communication and strengthens ties between members. Socialisation, through its various mechanisms, also binds members to the organisation. This in turn protects the group against possible defections. These mechanisms of socialisation include both intrinsic motivations, the reduction of communication with the “outside world”, as well as disciplinary measures.

Moving down to the micro-level, the fourth chapter approaches the insurgency as a subjective experience. After pointing out the socio-economic heterogeneity of insurgents using statistical data, the chapter describes the pathways into the insurgency of three selected group members as well as the manifold goals and meanings – symbolic as well as practical – which they associate with the rebellion. It will be emphasised that the meanings of violence and the motives for joining vary among insurgents, ranging from jihadist ideas to that of secular nationalism. This defies the idea of a uniform “insurgent profile”.

The last chapter explores communicative relations between BRN-Coordinate and the local Malay population who are its potential support base. Although the group refrains from publicly taking responsibility for its violent attacks, violent attacks have become important symbols within local communication. The chapter will trace the popular support for the insurgency and explain how this support is connected to the local social structure. In its attempt to convince the local Malay population of the acceptability of violence, BRN-Coordinate constantly controls popular perceptions of violence and manipulates these perceptions through propaganda and the selective use of violence itself. Finally, the chapter will throw light on the diverging interpretations of violence among leading officers of the 4th Army Area Command and how these influence state counterinsurgency approaches.

1.2. Methodology and sources

As this thesis tries to account for manifold meanings and behaviours with regard to violence, and shed on the light on the systemic organisational structure behind the violence, I opted for an interdisciplinary approach. Fieldwork and participant observation, the strengths of anthropology, offered the best means to gather data on and

describe emic perspectives of insurgents and witnesses of violence. A basic problem for anthropological violence research is the question of empathy and cultural relativism (Zitelmann 2010). If we as scientists report on the local perspectives of the performers of violence, is there a possibility that we (unintentionally) glorify or even reproduce the legitimacy of violence? Or, on the contrary, by explaining the cold and ruthless logic of an insurgency, are we, in fact, inflicting moral standards? The English term “violence” itself, defined here rather narrowly as “the intentional rendering of physical hurt on to another human being” (Riches 1986: 6), implies monopolization of violence by the state as well as a resulting moral connotation distinguishing between the moral and immoral use of violence, which might not be applicable in a cross-cultural context (Riches 1986). According to Weber (1978) any question of research implies taking sides, while the research that attempts to answer the question itself will be filtered and corrected by scientific logic and plausibility.

The field research in Southern Thailand was split in two periods, one between August 2007 to July 2008 and one between July 2009 and March 2010. The first period consisted mainly of the conducting of basic open interviews and engaging in participant observation among Malay communities in Narathiwat province, whereas the second period focused specifically on semi-structured interviews and fieldwork with the insurgents themselves, and counterinsurgency specialists from the Thai government (COIN), the Royal Thai Army and the Royal Thai police. Working with unnamed commanders of the 4th Army Area allowed me to compare COIN units and the insurgent practices they dealt with on the village level.

However, as mentioned above, I consider the meanings, global concepts of the “enemy” and perceptions of violence in a deeper and broader sense than in terms of simply that which is given by the cultural context of a conflict. During civil wars these features are shaped and instrumentalised by armed actors in order to give violence a more permanent basis (Elwert 2003). Hence the use of political sociology terminology, in particular, the interpretation of Elias and Weber by Schlichte (2009), was used for a more theoretically guided analysis of the structure and dynamics of armed groups. Although one statistical analysis of captured insurgents was made, this is mostly a quantitative study. Because statistical data on wars and civil wars are themselves influenced by politics, unreliable and difficult to gather, I was careful in my estimations on the number of insurgents and their supporters. Moreover because the hyper-secrecy of BRN-Coordinate limited the range of sources, this thesis relied extensively on documentation and secondary data analyses from secret state intelligence resources. However, direct reference to the insurgents, COIN specialists and specific intelligence documents had to be avoided, because if their identities were revealed, officials who enabled me to access the information would be subjected to disciplinary sanctions. As stressed in an article on the permissibility and “danger management” of research in

conflict zones, interviews with insurgents entail an element of danger for both the researcher and the interviewee (Helbardt et al. 2010). Active but also captured insurgents are subject to retaliation measures by insurgent groups, who naturally fear the disclosure of secrets.

With regard to getting reliable data, another problem is that as part of the market of violence in Southern Thailand, a market for information brokers and negotiating consultants has emerged. Wars and insurgencies have become profitable business for local and international scholars. When relevant agencies come to the region, these brokers indicate that they are the ones with a “real” understanding of the violence, its roots and its responsible actors. Often, this information seems to be mere simulacra in order to satisfy the demands of the media, researchers and consultation agencies, all which are attempting to negotiate peace in the region. It took a lot of time, trust and crosschecking of data to finally get behind this veil – to the extent that this is possible at all.

Figure 1.1. Map of Southern Thailand

2. Organisational aspects of BRN-Coordinate

Our current popular understanding of violence has been influenced by the global political experience of an apparent rise in international terrorism, epitomized by the 9/11 attacks, and the “cultural turn” in the social sciences that assumes religion and ethnicity to be self-explanatory categories for the motivation of violent acts, replacing the former ‘trendy’ ideologies such as socialism or nationalism. The result is that present-day terror is commonly believed to be undertaken in the name of God. These changes, coupled with the rise of the sociological concept of the network society (cf. Castells 2010), have given rise to paradigms such as the “new wars” or the “new terrorism”.

These paradigms have not only altered our understanding of the goals and means of collective violence, but also of the organisation of violence. In particular, the American way of framing terrorist threats as a “religionisation of violence” goes hand in hand with a shift from a classical hierarchical organisation of violence towards more ambiguous forms, such as loose networks, the ‘leaderless jihad’, or cellular organisations, whose rationality and sense of humanity are often questioned (see, e.g. Lesser 1999; Appadurai 2006; Sageman 2008).

The “new terrorism” paradigm exerts a certain appeal when analysing violence in Southern Thailand, where terrorist attacks on civilians and state personal are on the rise and the role of religious motivation is a hotly debated issue (see, e.g. ICG). Since 2004 terrorist groups often have not been taking responsibility for violent attacks. Influenced by discussions about “new terrorism”, authors like Pathan and Liow (2010) assume that separatist violence in Southern Thailand has adopted fundamentally new characteristics. Although both warn against exaggerating the concept of religious motivation (and international connections), stressing instead the role of local history as a motivating force for insurgents in Southern Thailand, both still assume that there is a rupture in the structural organisation of the insurgency. Analysing the main insurgent organisation in Southern Thailand, BRN-Coordinate, both argue that the key feature of this “new insurgency” is the low degree of organisation.

In contrast, I argue that although BRN-Coordinate has changed from its predecessor organisation, BRN, as a reaction to the successful counterinsurgency campaign of the Thai government, the group still remains, at its core, a hierarchically organised group. In other words, the departure from the past is not as pronounced as some scholars argue. After outlining the group’s goals and strategies, this chapter will describe the group’s main organisational structures and processes, emphasising secrecy as a main organisational principle. The chapter will then show how BRN-coordinate is a hybrid form that simultaneously comprises elements of a command-and-control apparatus as well as a flat network, explaining how these elements fit together.

2.1. How important is BRN-Coordinate?

Various state and non-state accounts about violence in Southern Thailand assume that BRN-Coordinate is the leading insurgent group in the region (National Reconciliation Commission 2006; Liow & Pathan 2010, Janes's World Insurgency and Terrorism 2007). However, presently this hypothesis is not supported by empirical evidence, as field research on insurgents also poses an incalculable security threat and presents a moral dilemma to the researcher. Thus scientists, when talking about insurgents, are mostly left to describe the local or national narratives about insurgency rather than analyse the insurgents themselves. Other organisations may still receive support and play an important media role, such as the PULO whose members run websites and are willing to give interviews to the press. This evidence combined with failed peace talks (e.g. the Langkawi talks in 2005)⁷, interrogation of insurgents, and intelligence reports, suggests that the key insurgent actor on the ground is indeed BRN-Coordinate, while Gerakan Mujahideen Islam Patani (GMIP), PULO, and New PULO play a secondary role (Lt. General interview, September 14, 2009).

With regards to PULO, most of its leaders were arrested in 1997-98 and its rank and file joined government amnesty programs (Abuza 2009), leaving only a fraction of outspoken leaders based in Europe and a fighting force of 30-60 insurgents in Southern Thailand. The strength of GMIP is still a matter of discussion, with Thai intelligence sources estimating that the group has a force of approximately 40 fighters on the ground (Abuza 2009). Although GMIP seems to enjoy a relationship with the Free Aceh Movement (GAM) and has a number of 'Afghanistan-hardened' fighters, its heavy involvement in "contract killings" and the narcotics trade casts serious doubt on the political motivation of the group. Instead, GMIP seems to be fully established in the local market of violence (Elwert 1996).

In addition, statistical evidence indicates that BRN-Coordinate holds a dominant role as the leading insurgent group in the South. Throughout the course of this research, 150 official interrogation records were analysed for content as well as quantitative features. Of course, the fact that these records were produced by the state, in the interest of those who run and control it, is problematic. However, the hyper-secrecy of the insurgents in southern Thailand hardly allows for other forms of direct data gathering. Interestingly, the data showed that 58% of the suspects admitted to having passed the RKK (Runda Kumpulan Kecil) training curriculum. RKK is not a separate insurgent group, but rather an irregular military tactic based on the use of small group assault units, which that was probably adopted by BRN-Coordinate from Indonesia (Lt. General interview, September 14, 2009). The term itself might be translated as 'small group patrol', or commando. An RKK-squad usually consists of six fighters using irregular tactics, but

⁷ Under the mediation by former Malaysian Prime Minister Mahathir Mohamad senior Thai officials met with representatives of insurgent groups in Langkawi, Malaysia in an attempt to develop a peace plan (Bukhari 2006).

according to the requirements of operations, two or more teams can cooperate and, theoretically, all units can coalesce into a conventional force. However, the key tactical advantages of these commandos are speed and low visibility, which they lose, once more RKK units are assembled.

Recently, the degree of centralized control of rebel violence was apparently illustrated by insurgents, who suspended bomb and small-arms fire attacks by groups of insurgents in three districts of Narathiwat province between in June and July 2010 as part of secret peace talks. According to Davis (2011) Thai government representatives and insurgent representatives (from BRN-Coordinate and PULO) had selected the stop of these activities in Cho Airong, Rangae and Yi-Ngor districts as a confidence building-measure and as proof for insurgent command over troops on the ground.

Although the specific size, the degree of control in other districts than those mentioned above and the dissemination of BRN-Coordinate might still be contestable, these factors at least highlight the importance of taking into account the group and its pattern of organisation. Building on captured documents of the group, interviews with BRN-Coordinate members, intelligence staff, as well as interrogation records, the following picture of the group emerges:

2.2. Collective goals

BRN-Coordinate is an insurgent organisation whose goal is an independent Islamic state (Negara Melayu Islam Patani⁸) using Islamo-Nationalism as their legitimizing ideology. The ‘Islamic homeland’ envisioned by BRN-Coordinate comprises of the Thai provinces of Narathiwat, Yala, Pattani, and the four Malay-Muslim dominated districts of Songkhla province (Thepa, Channa, Sabai Yoi and Nathawi). This region is considered to be the core area of the former independent Islamic Sultanate of Patani, which was annexed and divided between the Kingdom of Siam and British Malaya in the late 19th and early 20th centuries (insurgent interview, July 15, 2009; Colonel interview, July 17, 2009).⁹ The “Patani Malays” (Bangsa Melayu Patani)¹⁰ consider themselves to be a nation on their own, united by religion, language and history, distinct both from the Thai nation and the Malaysian nation as the Constitution of the original BRN claims.

The organisation seeks to effect meaningful political change within the borders of an imagined nation-state, with strong reference to both the history of Patani as a former

⁸ *Pattani*, written with two “t”, refers to the province within the Thai nation state, while *Patani*, written with one “t” is used here to refer to the area of the former independent sultanate.

⁹ At least two of BRN-Coordinate’s leading figures at the provincial level have admitted that they also consider the bordering parts of Terengganu and Kelantan as part of the imagined homeland, but, as Malaysia serves as a safe haven for BRN-Coordinate (and other Patani insurgent groups), questioning rights to the Malaysian territory is currently considered politically dangerous and thus avoided.

¹⁰ I will use central Malay spelling here.

independent Sultanate, as well as the use of Islamic-based vocabulary, symbolism and social understanding. In the long term BRN-Coordinate seeks to implement sharia (i.e. Islamic law based on the principles of the Koran and Hadith¹¹) in an independent Patani state. However, the group's main short-term policy is simply "Siamese out", meaning the withdrawal of the Thai state presence in Patani. BRN-Coordinate's ideology defines the Patani territory as an "Islamic land" (Darul Islam in Arabic) that was invaded by the infidel Siamese. Hence, the fight for freedom (kebebasan) is framed as a holy war, or jihad, in which all local Patani Muslims have the religious duty to participate. In contrast to de-territorialized Islamist groups like al Qaida, which reject the idea of nationalism and instead embrace the idea of a worldwide community of Muslims (ummah), BRN-Coordinate pictures the Patani nation as a sacred religious community, or Patani Darulsalam. However, such a combination of apparently contradictory ideas of nationalism and jihad is not unusual in the Islamic world and BRN-Coordinate can draw on the appeal of both, while avoiding ideological conflict as long as it does not take a public position (see chapter on recruitment).

Because BRN-Coordinate emerged as a splintered group after its predecessor organisation BRN, which was founded by three principal actors (Haji Abdul Karim bin Hasan, Haji Harun Sulong, and Ahmad "Mat" Bong)¹² in 1960, and then disbanded in 1981, it could draw on the experience of past failed insurgencies. Striving to be a potent military organisation, it makes use of a combination of both conventional territorial-based insurgency strategies and terrorism. The latter can be understood as a partial substitute for the lack of the former (Crenshaw 2001). In a rational sense, terrorism is a form of violent coercion, based on the "power to hurt" that aims to produce a change in the incumbent's political position. In the pursuit of this goal, BRN-Coordinate aims to maintain the allegiance of the Malay Muslim population in Southern Thailand (except Satun province), as its primary support community.

2.3. BRN-Coordinate Strategies

Insurgent strategies can have very different forms. Che Guevara's military-focused strategies stressed that, in an environment of economic grievances, an insurrection in rural areas could create the conditions that would lead to the overthrow of the government without the need for sophisticated insurgent political structures. The most successful insurgent strategy relates to the "theory of protracted warfare" as laid out by Mao Zedong and applied in China as well as in Vietnam and Algeria, although each country employs different adaptations (see, e.g. Mao Zedong 2000; Pike 1968: 26). Since the 1960s, Southern Thailand's insurgents systematically spread this stock of knowledge among their ranks, when political teachers discussed guerrilla tactics from

¹¹ The Arab term Hadith refers to statements and acts ascribed to the prophet Muhammad.

¹² Haji Abdul Karim bin Hasan was the head of a traditional pondoh school in Narathiwat and Haji Harun Sulong the owner of Thamma Wittaya school in Yala city (Davis 2010).

China, Vietnam and the Algeria Wars in jungle camps. Patani Malay insurgents met with Thai and Malayan communist insurgents to exchange ideas on the art of guerrilla warfare. The writings of Che Guevara and Mao Zedong were translated either into Malay or Thai (Suhrike 1977). Recently the Thai military found in the home of a leading BRN-Coordinate figure the Thai version of a book by General Giap, Vietnam's leading military strategist in the war against the Americans. Throughout the retrieved book there were marks and comments by the reader, written in Malay (Colonel interview, August 2, 2009). Thai intelligence sources also often find documents (mostly downloaded from the Internet) about "holy wars", such as al Qaida's fight against "the West" or the Palestinian struggle against Israel.

What appears to have remained central until today is the idea of protracted warfare. Mao argued that subversion, i.e. the mass mobilisation of the population, must precede any military action, whereas military resistance is organised in different phases. It is this theory, in an adapted form, which has significant influence on BRN-Coordinate's strategic thinking. The most famous document that provides insight into BRN-Coordinate's strategy is a handwritten paper, which was found in the home of an Islamic scholar called Masae Useng on May 1, 2003. On 30 November 2004 the same document was found at a religious school called Pondoh Jihad in Pattani's Yaring District. The owner of the document is believed to be the head of the BRN-Coordinate's political wing in Pattani (Colonel interview, September 3, 2009). Inspired by Mao Zedong's idea of a "protracted warfare" it outlines, in Jawi, a seven-step politico-military strategy that leads to the final goal: independence. The first five steps outline the subversion needed to reach this goal, which includes:

Phase One: the aim is to mobilise the (Malay) masses by constructing (political) consciousness. Short remarks on the primary document also provide insight into the different narratives BRN Coordinate uses in order to foster awareness about the following concepts: "religion", "Malayness", "Patani" history, the idea that "Siam invaded Patani" and, finally, the necessity to "resist". These terms broadly correspond to the indoctrination narrative mentioned above.

Phase Two centres on the integration of specific institutions into mass subversion, namely: places of "religious teachings", tadika (elementary Koran schools for young children), pondok (Islamic religious boarding schools teaching Koran studies and Arabic language), and "councils". It is not clear to which councils the document refers, as it may be Islamic councils, village councils or the local mosque councils. All three would make sense in this context, however claims of insurgent activities in these institutions are hard to substantiate.

It is only during Phase Three that BRN-Coordinate plans to systematically integrate its members into a mass-based political resistance organisation. This allows them, for example, to gather intelligence and to erect a stable system of income by taxing their

members. While short-term needs (e.g. acquisition of weapons) can be satisfied by plunder or assault, every organisation has a natural need for a steady source of income. Thus, BRN-Coordinate has established a principle of taxing its members 30 Baht per month, plus an additional 365 Baht at the end of the year.

Based on the political organisation, the military organisation is developed in Phase Four, which includes the recruitment and training of resistance fighters. The content of Phase Five is not totally clear. It is only described with the headline “nationalism” and seems to be the final mobilisation of a Patani “national consciousness” for the preparation of Phase Six and Phase Seven. Phase Six represents final military preparation and phase seven being the revolution itself. Phases Six and Seven are not described in detail in the document, so we must draw on other evidence to shed light on these crucial last stages.

The document helps us to answer to the following question: when and how was the plan actually implemented? Initially, Thai intelligence assumed that BRN-Coordinate began to implement its plan in 1992, because this is the year referred to in the document. However, recent interrogations of high-ranking insurgents in Autumn 2009 suggest that it was launched already in 1984 (insurgent interview, August 17, 2009; Colonel interview, July 7, 2009). However, within the first ten years, from 1984 to 1994, the group seemingly restricted its subversions to the indoctrination of the population and the recruitment of members (Phase One). Other authors’ data also hint at the time of being recruited around the mid 1990s (Askew 2009a; Liow & Pathan 2010). However, the magnitude and success of recruitment efforts during the first decade are still unclear. It is possible that the group required more time to reorganise and develop its strategy in detail, at both the operational and the tactical levels. Intelligence officers suggest that the political and military arms were established in the second decade (1994-2004), while the mass mobilisation of Phase One continued.

Moreover, the document states two different figures regarding the number of fighters: 3,000 and 30,000. The latter possibly refers to the amount of guerrillas considered to be necessary for the revolution. It is very likely that the figure of 3,000 fighters refers to the main military force, RKK, or commandos, while the figure of 30,000 might be the amount of ordinary village youth members with basic military training. Two high-ranking BRN-Coordinate members, at the political company level in Narathiwat and Ismail, claim to have successfully trained around 3,000 RKK soldiers (that is 1,000 for every province) as was planned to be completed by 2004 (insurgent interviews, December 2, 2009). Regarding trained members of the military wing, based on the number of captured insurgents, interrogation and statistical evidence on violence patterns, military and police intelligence officers consider figures, ranging from hundreds to several thousand to be realistic estimates (Colonel interview, September 2, 2009).

Whether the group has 30,000 members at all cannot be verified. Nevertheless, conservative estimates within the Thai intelligence community consider this figure or an even higher one to be quite realistic. Yet, even if BRN-Coordinate has this amount of militarily trained members at its disposal, it is highly unlikely that the 30,000 juwae, or fighters, would all sufficiently supplied with weapons, even those weapons of a small calibre. Finally, the document also provides information about the number of “experts” or officers, who most likely function as instructors and commanders of the military wing, listing them at about 300 members. Again, based on the limited information available from captured BRN-Coordinate members and calculations by informed Thai intelligence officers, such numbers are considered highly realistic (Colonel interview, August 2, 2009).

It appears obvious that the leaders of BRN-Coordinate had long planned to start the insurgency in around 2004. However, why they consider 3,000 commando fighters (plus a 30,000 members with basic military training), numbers that are very unlikely to be sufficient for a successful revolution is matter of speculation, because the Thai military has approximately 305,000 troops (Lt. General interview, July 18, 2009). Thus, it becomes difficult to understand the group’s strategy, as questions about how they intend to revolt are not easily answered, especially when considered in light of the information that the document provides.

Here, the question of rationality arises. Waldmann (1993) and other authors claim that terrorist violence is irrational in the sense that terrorist act alone have no chance of taking over military power or otherwise changing a regime. A conventional way of interpreting terrorist violence, one that is often offered, for example by parts of the Thai military and intelligence community, is to understand it rationally, as simply a way of generating power in what is basically a political bargaining process. Here, observers approach the goals and strategies of an armed group in light of its capabilities and past action, with the assumption that insurgents are instrumental and calculating. No matter how unrealistic the group’s aims are, they must be taken seriously in order to be able to interpret their means (Crenshaw 2001). In other words, it is correct to assume that armed groups like BRN-Coordinate act rationally, even though, to put it in Weber’s terms, the assumptions on which their actions are based may be irrational (Weber 1978).

However, Laqueur (1987) and Smith (2008) propose that the rationality of terrorism is not to be found on the battlefield, because a strategic victory would never be achieved there. The logic of terrorist violence is rather to establish the condition, in which, for example, the Thai government would be willing to negotiate BRN-Coordinate’s demands. BRN-Coordinate does not pursue its violent campaign with the aim of achieving a strategic military objective like taking or holding territory, which it (at the moment at least) is simply unable to do - neither in terms of manpower or terms of

arms. Weaponry that is used by BRN-Coordinate remains simple.¹³ In this sense, insurgents employ violence in the villages and partly in the cities, simply because they can. Targeting the civilian Buddhist population, in combination with assaults on officials, exposes a weakness in Thai state surveillance in the South and hence, influences the will of the incumbents in Bangkok.

In order to create the political conditions for independence, violence seems to have two overall tactical functions. First, it specifically targets civilians, which are hard to protect. The terrorist campaign against Buddhist civilians attempts to remove Thai Buddhists from the area by establishing a regime of fear, using indiscriminate violence. This undermines the Thai government's will to hold the area or, as a former member of the Thai National Security Council stated, "[o]nce we lose the people in the area and simply own the soil, there is no need to defend it. In the worst case scenario the Buddhist will be gone, the economy is destroyed and most Malays will be on the side of the insurgents." Second, BRN-Coordinate's military campaign attempts to render the area, especially the Malay villages, ungovernable and thus turn people's loyalty towards the insurgents. Hence, the group specifically targets Malay village heads and subdistrict chiefs, leaving many of them dead, while others flee to the cities to seek protection (McCargo 2008). Here, again, the mass indoctrination and infiltration of villages distinguishes BRN-Coordinate from small cellular terrorist groups. Both enable the group to attack village heads and Buddhist civilians with high precision and on a large scale, something that small terrorist groups can hardly attain.

Importantly, such a protected insurgent campaign also has a time dimension. A long-term military campaign, such as in Southern Thailand, aims to demoralize its enemy's government, its population and its army over time. Modern counterinsurgencies have often failed, not due to a lack of material or personal resources, but, rather, as it was the case with the Americans in Vietnam, the reigning regime lost its political will to defend a certain area (Creveld 2008). Aron and Löwenthal (1986) argue that the logic of anti-colonial protracted warfare can be reflected in a simple formula; what the guerrilla needs is not a military victory, as in Mao Zedong's type of protracted warfare, but he simply needs to stay alive militarily in order to win politically. The longer the insurgents are not militarily defeated, the higher their chances of winning politically. Like insurgents elsewhere, they hope that the incumbent government will not withstand the moral dilemma of a strong state "fighting" a weak enemy, typically involving high numbers of civilian deaths (Crefeld 2008). In other words, the insurgents consider the Thai state in Patani a colonial power and hence Bangkok's will to defend the three

¹³ For assassinations pistols are typically the main choice, while assault rifles and shotguns that are seized from village defence volunteers are used for assaults and ambushes. Intelligence suggests that the group is possibly in the possession of seven rocket-propelled grenades and a small number of M-79 40mm grenade launchers. The total quantity of firearms remains a matter of speculation; some accounts estimate a number of 2000. IED's usually do not extend the 3-15kg range (Janes's World Insurgency and Terrorism 2007).

provinces is, in their view, subject to “moral attrition”.¹⁴

Insurgencies are usually mosaic in nature, meaning that tactics constantly adapt and different tactics are employed if one tactic fails. Thai military strategists assume that one possible aim of BRN-Coordinate is to involve the Thai government in protracted “anti-colonial independence warfare”, in which the involvement of a third foreign actor will replace the lack of military power on the insurgent’s side. BRN-Coordinate’s main strategy seems to consist of the following rather simple elements: staying alive; fostering support among Malays to create a climate of intercommunal tensions and to induce mindless repression by the Thais until the conflict reaches the international level, with the hope that the international community will side with the Malays as a suppressed minority that is unjustly ruled by Bangkok.

Such strategies of escalation based on terrorist campaigns are known from different conflict sites. In Argentina leftist groups aimed to create chaos and indiscriminate repression through terrorist campaigns. However, although the Argentinian military was successfully lured into reprisals, their violent campaign eliminated the insurgents themselves (Kalyvas 2006). Similarly, in the mid 1950s during the Algerian war of independence, the National Liberation Front (FLN) decided to stir inter-communal tensions by massacring both French and Muslim civilians in order to increase mass support for the group (Feraoun & Le Sueur 2000).

In Algeria this strategy worked, because the French governor general Soustelle reacted with overzealous repressions. This reaction forced the remaining neutral Algerian Muslims, who had earlier cooperated with the French, into the hand of the militants, destroying any chance of reconciliation. With the consequential manifestation of a collective will for independence, the UN adopted a resolution to hear the Algerian question, and in the fall of 1955 the issue was placed on the UN agenda (Feraoun & Sueur 2000). Importantly, in contrast to the French, who adopted a hard line policy of bombing innocent Muslims and all-out assault on the FLN, which included, for example, the establishment of concentration camps, the Thais have seemingly learned their lesson and, despite all allegations of human rights abuses, have opted for a strategy of constraint (interview Lt. General, November 10, 2009). In the end, the French, despite their military preponderance, could not sustain the economic and political costs of war.

Unlike French settlers in Algeria, Thai Buddhists in the South have not played a crucial part in radicalizing the government’s counterinsurgent approach, although many Buddhists blame Bangkok for “pampering” Muslims and being too soft against insurgents. Though there has been an increase in armed defence groups and Buddhist

¹⁴ Herein lies an important difference between anti-colonial and “non-anti-colonial” guerrilla wars: While Mao’s enemy fought for their only homeland and thus equated military with political defeat, the colonial powers could distinguish between a political and a military defeat: they always had the option to withdraw from the foreign land, i.e. find a political solution without a military decision (Münkler 1992).

vigilante violence, in contrast to other conflict sites (see, e.g., Waldmann 1993), such risky tendencies towards militarization remain under control. Especially in the countryside many Buddhists opted for leaving the region.

Insurgents assume that if a similar scenario of escalation should occur in the South, the Thai Army would be likely to side with the Buddhist population or, at least, be unable to control such a confrontation, possibly open the door for an international actor, preferably the United Nations or the Organisation of Islamic Countries (OIC), to intervene. For the military leadership of the Thai army, there is a legitimate fear of such intervention (e.g. in the form of the ‘blue helmets’), because intervention is viewed as the end of Thai sovereignty in the South. This would bring the insurgents closer to their aim. In such a scenario of escalation several consequences would prove crucial for the success of BRN-Coordinate, including:

1. The turning of international opinion against Bangkok and its handling of the South. This would undermine bilateral relations between the Thai government and its international partners and donor states. Importantly, while former Western allies, who are keen on the promotion of democracy, may possibly sanction Thailand, Islamic countries most likely would call for direct intervention in the South in order to protect the civilian population.
2. For BRN-Coordinate, such elevation to the international level in any form could allow BRN-Coordinate to remove its status as a clandestine organisation and rather appear as a political actor openly. The international community is more likely to recognize and thus guarantee the safety of the group.
3. A Buddhist backlash against Patani Muslims could increase support for BRN-Coordinate among the Malays and the international (Islamic) community, building fierce opposition and even hatred towards Buddhist chauvinism. Many Patani Malays who are currently neutral with regard to the question of autonomy might become open supporters of breaking from Thailand. This could also mean a further increase in the form of resources for the group and thus strengthen its military position as well as political power.

In whatever way BRN-Coordinate leaders planned the revolution, it is clear that the “seven-step-plan” is a long and meticulously planned and executed, mass-based endeavour that covers a time span of over 20 years. However, that is not to say that it is without flaws. Therefore, it was not Prime Minister Thaksin Shinawatra who triggered the outbreak of the insurgency with his misguided and violent politics in Southern Thailand. Instead, it was the Thai state’s record of human rights violations and cultural repression in the South, combined with the events in Tak Bai and Kru Se, which led to the outbreak, as they provided the best propaganda that insurgents could possibly hope for. Both seemed to affirm the insurgent’s image of Siam as the “ruthless colonial

suppressor” of the Malays bringing it on a global stage, and they did so at exactly the right point of time. Ismail and various intelligence officers even insist that the demonstration at Tak Bai was instigated by BRN-Coordinate in order to trigger Thai state suppression of the protestors (Lt. General interview, July 23, 2009). For the same purpose, the group organised another wave of local demonstrations against arrests issued by Thai officials in 2006, but ceased this tactic of provocation when the Thai military avoided a potential “second Tak Bai”. This stopped outbreaks of violence at these demonstrations. Other evidence supports the thesis that the insurgency was planned for 2004. First, conventional guerrilla strategy dictates that shortly before the beginning of an insurgency, the insurgent movement must prepare by procuring more weapons, ammunition, etc (Thompson 1966). Indeed in 2003, one year before the outbreak of the insurgency, there was an increase in attacks on isolated police and military installations - the April 2004 raid on Chulaporn Camp in Narathiwat was only the climax (Colonel interview, July 23, 2009).

2.4. Formal structure

BRN-Coordinate has developed a refined organisational strategy that underlies almost all of the group’s activities. BRN-Coordinate appears to have a centralized, top-down authoritarian structure, which, on the local level, is based around a political and military wing, which was developed previously by BRN original.

Hierarchical differentiation begins with leadership organisation. The highest authority of the BRN-Coordinate is vested in a ca. 30-member Party Leadership Council (Dewan Pimpinan Parti, or short DPP), within which a council chairman, vice-council chairman, a general secretary, a vice-general secretary, at least three (less important) assistant secretaries, and seven different councils, form the executive. Thai intelligence suspects that Sapeing Basoh, the BRN general secretary and his deputy, Asae Chaelong, are the leaders of BRN, although formally, they are subordinate to the chairman and the vice-chairman, both whom had to flee authorities in Thailand and now reside in Malaysia. While DPP has around 30 formal positions, some single members hold double or even triple positions within the organisation. Sapeing Basoh, for example, is the general secretary, the head of the military council (legislative level) and the head of the military section (executive level – below the DPP council).

In addition to the leading figures, DPP consists of seven councils, which reflects typical functional differentiation of insurgent organisations, this includes the: military council (militeri), economic council (ekonomi), youth council (pemuda), foreign relations council, propaganda council (propaganda), religious council (ulama), and finally the political-administrative council. Each council consists of a minimum of two members but many probably consist of more.

Meetings at the DPP-level take place regularly (at least several times a year). During the

meetings, the current situation of the group is discussed and policy guidelines are passed, usually on a yearly basis (insurgent interview, July 15, 2009; Colonel interview, July 17, 2009).

Figure 2.1. Formal structure of BRN-Coordinate

Below the governing body there are seven administrative sections that mirror the functions of the seven councils (economy, propaganda etc.). These sections implement the policy guidelines as laid down by the DPP executive. However, the administrative sections do not reach down to the local level independently, because such an extensive organisational structure could be easily detected and destroyed by the Thai state. Hence, below the centralized DPP structure, the administration of the group is divided into the two mentioned wings: political and military (Colonel interview, September 3, 2009; insurgent interview, September 6, 2009).

2.4.1. The Political Wing

While the latter is basically responsible for military activities, the former subsumes all other functions of the group, i.e. recruitment, propaganda, economic administration, religion, etc. As BRN Coordinate does not account for foreign relations at the local level, foreign relations is the only function that remains at the DPP level. The two wings serve as a link between leaders and the general population at the village level. Since mass support from the population is a precondition for conventional guerrilla military

activity as well as for the overall success of any guerrilla organisation, the primary aim of the group is to ensure that the political wing gains control over the population and destroys the state’s legitimacy among Malays in the region through continued subversion.

This dual organisation can be found at different spatial echelons. The kawasan (‘KAS’, Malay for province) is at the highest level. The imagined homeland is divided into three KAS, only partly reflecting the administrative structure of the Thai state. KAS I, for example, comprises the Pattani province but it also includes Songkhla’s four districts, Thepa, Channa, Nathawi and Saba Yoi (see map). Below the KAS, the political and military wing are organised, firstly, at the area level (or wilayah in Malay), which is headed by the sukum-committee.¹⁵ According to military sources KAS I comprises, for example, five sukum (see figure 2.2.); secondly, the district level, which is headed by the komis¹⁶ and, thirdly, at the subdistrict level (ligaran).

Figure 2.2. KAS I (Pattani; including sukum)

Source: 4th Army Area

Most importantly, however, is the village level for the political wing, referred to as “Ajak” in BRN-Coordinate terminology. Ajak is an abbreviation for the Malay term

¹⁵ Sukum can be translated as “administrative area” or “administrative zone”, but BRN-Coordinate members apparently also use this local Malay term to refer to the sukum-committee (chief). In Thai intelligence sources the word sukum is sometimes spelled “sakom”.

¹⁶ Komis is an abbreviation for the English term commissary.

Ahli Jawatan Kampung, which can be translated into English as the ‘village working committee’ (field commander interview, August 13, 2009; insurgent interview, September 23, 2009). Past insurgencies in Thailand were organised mainly in the jungles, where professional guerrilla armies attempted to counter state power. However, these insurgencies (especially in the 1970s and 1980s) failed because the Thai army was simply too strong to be defeated in a regular guerrilla campaign. One of the key lessons obtained from the failed Patani insurgencies in the past was that guerrillas should not be based in detached jungles where they could easily be hunted down, and that mass indoctrination of the population should not be neglected (insurgent interview, September 20, 2009; Lt. General interview, September 15, 2009).

In their earlier guerrilla campaign of the 1970s and 1980s, PULO and BRN, as Liow and Pathan (2010) rightly note, maintained their connection to the villages. This practice was employed, for example, to guarantee the logistics of the groups. Wives and sisters of fighters transported collected money from and to Malaysia. They also supplied their relatives in the jungle with medicine or food. Coming down from the hills to interact with villagers, insurgents tried to convince others of their goals. However, mass indoctrination programs were not systematic nor widespread, not the least because the insurgents were occupying the jungles and had few opportunities to engage in such efforts (insurgent interview, August 7, 2009). In the past, insurgents mostly concentrated on the military campaign and neglected a political platform for the three provinces. As one BRN member explained, in regards to the period of transition at the end of the 1978/1979: “Most of our members simply wanted to fight and recruit supporters; this is what they did all the time. But they forgot about economics, youth and other issues. We had to find a new position, but there was no unity in the group.” However, most classic guerrilla manuals emphasize that popular support in the villages is extremely important for the success of any insurgency; it is only when military activity is coupled with mass subversion in the villages that it can generate political leverage. Therefore, present conditions ensure that Ajak-level indoctrination, recruitment and so forth, takes place, and resources such as taxes, hideouts for insurgents on the run, information, etc., are mobilised. Furthermore, irregular warfare is highly dependent on information from the local level (Weinstein 2007: 203); armed groups can only mobilise support and avoid detection when they are aware of who their friends and foes are. Ajak committee members and their networks of local ties allow for the gathering of such information.

The Ajak-committee chief represents the top level of the village committee. In at least one village in Narathiwat, the Ajak-committee chief also had a deputy (it is not clear if every Ajak-committee chief has a deputy). The Ajak-committee chief coordinates the main activities for the group at the local level, which are divided into different sections, including: economy, youth work (pemuda), religious activities (ulama), and watchman

activities. Ideally, other members in the village exert these functions. Hence, BRN-Coordinate tries to win support from local leaders such as the Imam or ustadz for the ulama section or they try to recruit such leaders to assume the role of Ajak-committee chief, while local traders are, for example, preferred to lead the economic section. Since these people are based in the local community, they possess knowledge about the local population (e.g. who is pro- or anti- government) and their acquaintances, thus facilitating mobilisation. However, for the sake of the group's secrecy, BRN-Coordinate limits the number of Ajak operatives to 12 people. Naturally, the strength of BRN-Coordinate varies across the region. In some villages BRN-Coordinate is unable to recruit any members, or their numbers are limited, such that no functional Ajak-committee can exist. However, in other villages the Ajak-committees are able to fulfil their complete set of tasks, which comprises:

1. Collecting membership fees. The economic section is responsible for raising the group's income by collecting a membership fee of 30 Baht per month. It can also generate further income by, for example, establishing a local 'mini-mart' or engaging in other economic activities. Members who refuse to pay the fees are usually not punished but are in a way coerced by ideas of shame and honour. The basic sum of 30 Baht is deliberately set to a low amount so that adult members have no excuses for not paying. For instance, if a member argues that he cannot pay his fee, because he has not earned enough money during the month, the collector will argue that 30 Baht is only a "negligible sum" in order to induce a feeling of shame. In some villages Ajak-committees collect higher amounts. One known Ajak-committee in Yala collected 100 Baht per month, calling it "jihad money", or "wang jihad" in Malay. The name itself that in making financial contributions to the group, members feel somewhat religiously gratified.

There are reports indicating forced fee collection, which is typical for groups that, unlike BRN-Coordinate, exert territorial control, but these claims are still hard to verify due to inconsistent empirical data. Under the veil of secrecy, however, forced taxation as well as forced recruitment is dysfunctional, because both increase the risk of defection to the government side. For security reasons, in villages where Thai COIN units are employed, the members of the economic section now refrain from gathering the money themselves (as they did in the past), because regular activities such as these could easily draw the attention of counterinsurgents or government collaborators. Instead, the money handover is organised with the help of undetectable means, such as 'dead-letter drops', cisterns, tress or waste bins at the market. Here members can inconspicuously leave their membership fees for the economic section to pick up. The money collected is partly transferred to BRN-Coordinate leadership or used locally to finance the acquisition of "walkie-talkies" or petrol, which are necessary for operations.

Other sources of BRN-Coordinate can be distinguished according to regularity and

degree of enforcement or willingness of the people to volunteer and cooperate (Schlichte 2009). Donations are made by BRN-Coordinate members (see below) and foreign sources, mostly from the Middle East and Europe (Janes’s World Insurgency and Terrorism 2007). Some Private Islamic Schools like Narathiwat’s Islamburapa School, an educational institution closely connected to BRN-Coordinate (see below), donated 10.5 % of their earnings to the group. In addition, individual members contribute to BRN-Coordinate on special occasions such as in the event of marriage. Some members who I interviewed referred to these donations as zakat, an Arabic term for “alms giving” - one of the five pillars of Islam. The amount in these donations and its importance in comparison to the membership fees, which is a more reliable source of funding, is unknown. During local level elections (e.g. for the Tambon Administrative Council) there are instances where BRN-Coordinate acts as a vote-broker, asking members to vote for certain candidates, who are members of the group. Then, after a successful election in Rueso district, Narathiwat province, the group received 2.5 % of Tambon Administrative Council funds (ligaran-committee member interview, September 28, 2009). Another regular source of funding and investment are the BRN-Coordinate related enterprises such as the Tom Yam Gung shops¹⁷ and restaurants in Malaysia, property acquisition, and the franchising of local minimarts in Southern Thailand. According to Thai intelligence, parts of larger Buddhist enterprises are also subject to extortion. Sources suggested, for example, that *BIG-C*, the only and hence largest retailer in the three provinces pays 2.5 % of its revenue to BRN-Coordinate and employs group members among its security staff. In return for loyalty, BRN-Coordinate provides the company with protection against bomb attacks. Regarding criminal activities, such as drug trade and prostitution, there is no information as to the extent of the group’s involvement.

Figure 2.3. BRN-Coordinate funding sources

	Irregular	Regular
Voluntary	Donations	Membership fees, self-run enterprises
Enforced		Extortion

Source: Radtke 2009 in Schlichte 2009: 121

2. Identifying enemies: Enemies can be defined as those who oppose the movement and give active support to the government. Ajak-committee members constantly try to gather information about Malays who may potentially collaborate with the Thai government. Fellow villagers who are, for example, said to be government spies are

¹⁷ There are hundreds of BRN-Coordinate owned restaurants. BRN-Coordinate helps members to invest into a Tom Yam Gung restaurant and gets the papers that are necessary to run a business in Malaysia (insurgent interview, 26 September 2009). Later, the members return parts of their revenue to the group.

monitored and, if they are considered a security threat to the Ajak committee, the military wing eliminates them. This is part of the duty of the internal security section to gather intelligence on strength and track the movements of security forces. “Grade A” villages are able to organise patrols with watchmen, mostly young men, who are ‘on guard’ in the village 24 hours per day, 7 days of the week, checking who is entering or leaving the village. The youngsters make use of everyday activities to cover up their surveillance. For example, they raise cattle or go fishing at strategic points or intersections and at the same time observe and report on who is leaving and entering the village. In other villages, where BRN-Coordinate is less strong, the group is not able to establish such guards and comprehensive intelligence.

3. Disseminating propaganda and recruiting new members: Religious activities (e.g. Friday prayer) and indoctrination are organised by the Ajak-committees’s ulama section in order to retain existing members or recruit new ones. Indoctrinators from within and outside the village will engage pupils with talks, for example, about local Patani history, jihad or make use of other elements in BRN-Coordinate’s ideological repertoire (see next chapter). Newly recruited members then pass through an ideological indoctrination and receive basic military training. While one section of the recruits remains with the political section, the others are chosen to switch to the military wing where they receive RKK training.

4. Supporting the military wing: In addition to recruitment, the military depends on the political wing in other regards. As the members of the military wing avoid operating in their home villages due to a high-level risk of being recognized by locals, they require additional assistance in their area of operation. Thus, it is the task of the local political wing to provide maps, information on targets, intelligence on local state security forces and logistical support (insurgent interview, September 12, 2009). For example, after an assault RKK-fighters typically leave their weapons at certain places during the getaway. Here members of the local political wing or other RKK-fighters will then pick up the weapons and transport them to a temporary safe place. As the political wing subverted larger areas after its establishment in the mid or late 1990s (see below), the flow of recruits and intelligence for the military steadily increased. In this way, the military wing could also cover an even wider area. Importantly, in this division of labour distinguishes BRN-Coordinate from cellular forms of terrorism, or leaderless jihad, where small groups of terrorists operate independently (see, e.g., Sageman 2009). Furthermore, it explains the “ghostly” nature of RKK-fighters. Although every single military operation demands weeks of preparation, the fighters themselves seem to appear only for executing their mission and then they disappear without a trace.

It is important to know that although one of the aims of BRN-Coordinate is to make Southern Thailand ungovernable, including, for example, specifically attacking Malay village heads who are not on the insurgent’s side, it is not (yet) the task of the Ajak-

committees to supplant the Thai administration, because any form of publicly visible rebel administration would be monitored and sanctioned by the Thai state. Analytically, the Ajak-committees distinguish BRN-Coordinate from conventional terrorist organisations, which, though they have certain milieus in which they can grow, usually refrain from both building a kind of territorial presence or mobilizing mass support (Waldmann 1993). These are features of guerrilla organisations as outlined by theorists like Mao, who argued that guerrilla forces should not be isolated from the local population. On the contrary, they argued that the key advantages of a guerrilla army over a conventional army derive from its establishment in the local population, which provides cover and supplies them with necessary resources. The non-combatant population ensures an operational base for the partisan, a dictum that was expressed in Mao's famous picture of the guerrilla moving freely among the local population like a "fish in the water" (Münkler 1992: 112). Terrorist groups usually only communicate with the population through the symbolic dimension of their violent deeds (Waldmann 1993). Moreover, the territorial dimension is a potential political power base for the group's leaders, who, once the group is able to come to the surface and engage in possible negotiations with foreign actors or the Thai state, can claim to have borne the bigger part of the violent campaign and to represent a significant part of the population. Thus possible benefits of the insurgency (e.g. independence, autonomy or other resources) cannot be claimed by free-riders such as local politicians.

2.4.1.1. The role of female insurgents

In various countries, women play an active role in militant Islamic groups, including terrorist groups (Schröter 2008). For guerrilla groups like BRN-Coordinate, whose aim is to systematically infiltrate local communities, female members appear to play a significant role. In the 1970s women were already active in BRN (Jane's World Insurgency and Terrorism 2007). Unfortunately, we still have very little data on their participation today. It is, however, known that while in some villages BRN-Coordinate could not recruit enough members to establish a single Ajak-committee, in other villages, local support was so strong that the Ajak-committee had a fully-fledged women's section. Recruitment and training of women is organized separately from the men's training. They appear to play a key role in various sections of the group. First, many young female members are trained as nurses. Interestingly, female BRN-Coordinate nursing instructors tend to use Thai books on nursing, as most young female members are more skilled in Thai than in Malay as a scholarly language. Most of the training is completed in the form of reading at home, yet at least one BRN-Coordinate "nurse" captured by Thai security forces had gained further knowledge about medication and emergency medicine by working in a pharmacy in Yala. Other female instructors probably have a formal education in nursing and have work experience as nurses in Thai or Malaysian hospitals.

Second, within the Ajak structure, they provide crucial logistical services for the military wing. Not only do female insurgents prepare food and cover for RKK-members on the run, but they also transport weapons. This service has become increasingly important, because Thai security forces have a very limited amount of female staff that can carry out body searches, most female Malays remain uncontrolled by police and at army road checkpoints. In one village in Narathiwat, a female BRN-Coordinate member, who was the wife of the Ajak-committee chief, took on a leadership role in the economic section. For instance, she collected membership fees and grew and sold vegetables in order to raise money for the movement. This crop growing not only generates income, but it is also considered as preparation for economic self-sufficiency in the case of an escalating violent situation and the early stages of independence.¹⁸

The actual number of female members is yet not clear, but a 27-year-old female BRN-Coordinate member claimed to have passed a test in basic nursing along with 100 other female members in a single month in 2005. If this number is correct, the group may have already trained a high number of female members. Commenting on the role of women within BRN-Coordinate Aishya, a 31-year-old female member of an Ajak-committee in Narathiwat's Rangae district remarked in early 2011:

“I think that women play a very important role. After entering the group we were divided according to our capabilities: some of the more beautiful women received training in intelligence. They were taught how to flirt with Thai soldiers and squeeze information out of them without arousing their suspicion. Women, like me, who were good in financial stuff, joined the economic work and raise money. Women who have an ability to speak are asked to mobilise other women who have not yet become members.”

Aishya also mentioned that there were many general tasks for women across all sections: “Many of us are trained as nurses. So when an RKK fighter gets injured, we receive a phone call and are asked to go to a certain village and bring some medicine. We even have one medical doctor for very bad cases in which we are not qualified enough to help. But we never know who he is, because we have to leave the village before he arrives to treat the patient.” Aishya remarked that she had two female instructors teaching her and that there were at least 10 other “nurses-to-be” in the Samphanwithaya School in Cho Airong district and a number of other sites in Narathiwat. The course was divided into several sessions over a period of several months. One session included practicing sutures on a living cow. In addition to nursery, the basic task of Aishya was to provide money. For Aishya this meant that she donated around 10 percent of the money she earned by smuggling cigarettes and diesel from Malaysia to Thailand to BRN-Coordinate: “Before I made around 5000 or 7000 Baht per day, and from that I donated around 1000 Baht to them. At other times I was asked

¹⁸ For the same reason some Ajak-committees establish rice storages.

to buy medical equipment, medicine and sim-cards for mobile phones. It was easy for me to move around and buy these things, because as a trader I did not attract the attention of the authorities.” When being asked why she donated the money, she referred to it as “zakat”. Besides Aishya argued “I believed in the righteousness of this jihad and felt the obligation to do everything to support our fighters.”

According to Aishya, who joined BRN-Coordinate in the year 2000, the functions of female members have increased over the last few years: “My impression is that since 2008/2009 we take-over more and more of the tasks of the men. Because the men are under pressure from the Thai military, we have to take over tasks such as observing potential targets (chi baumai in Thai) and assessing the probability of a successful attack. Some of my friends teach at tadika schools to win over the hearts of the next generation.” During military operations Aishya also provided regular transport for the local RKK-squad in her village, which included Aishya’s older brother, who invited Aishya to join BRN-Coordinate. Yet although Aishya stressed the importance of female support in BRN-Coordinate, she also noticed that women were clearly positioned at the receiving end of the lines of command: “Our principle is ‘one order-one action’, you never question orders, but act. That is how it works. And as a woman here you grow up learning to do what men say, unless it is against Islam. It is written in the Koran and was taught by my parents.” This quotation seems to support the thesis that the integration of women into the military and armed groups does not necessarily change existing gender hierarchies. Rather, it reproduces them (Schröter 2008).

2.4.2. The Military Wing

BRN-Coordinate’s “conventional” force has an estimated strength of around 3,000 trained fighters who are, if still active, bound into a relatively clear-cut chain of command. Below the military council of the DPP the three provinces are divided into three military areas, with each area under the control of an “area commander” or *kawasan panglima* (KAS) in Malay. In other words, KAS refers to both an operational area and a definite command structure. As in the political wing, each military area roughly corresponds to one of the three provinces in the South. Each *panglima* commands four to six battalions, with one battalion being composed of two or three companies (*kompi*). The companies themselves are made up of three or more platoons (*platong*). In early 2010 it was, however, not yet clear if the separate battalion commanders existed or if one of the company commanders simply fulfilled the position of battalion commander in addition to his regular position. Another open question concerned, for example, whether the battalion commander is appointed by the KAS *panglima* or whether the company commanders selected the best among them to be the battalion commander, and whether their decision was endorsed by the KAS only.

The specific area that a commander controls depends on different factors. It might depend on the commander’s knowledge of the area, his specific skills and other

operational factors. In Military Area Two, comprising of Narathiwat province, one Kompi consists of Rueso, Bajo and, importantly the Waeng district as it borders Malaysia and thus allows fighters to flee abroad after an operation. Significantly, these compositions (battalion, company and platoon) exist only on paper; while there are battalion commanders, company commanders as well as platoon commanders, fighters never unite as an operational force at these levels. For security reasons, it is at the level below the platoon, namely at the regu level and, below it, at the RKK level, that military units actually become operative. One regu, led by a commander, is again composed of approximately two to three RKK squads. Here it becomes clear that RKK is not a separate insurgent group, but rather an irregular military tactic based on the use of small-group assault units. The term itself might be translated as a small group patrol, or commando. An RKK squad is BRN-Coordinate's smallest tactical unit and its primary modus operandi; it serves the same function as the Ajak committee does for the political wing. It is here where independent military action is sustained; operations are planned and performed, and the main military routines (storage and movements of weapons etc.) are handled.

A squad consists of six fighters with each squad member fulfilling specific functions. The unit leader, who has the power to command his fellow fighters, heads the unit and as the most experienced or skilled fighter he is also responsible for planning military operations. A second person in the unit is assigned to be his deputy who has to give orders in cases where the unit leader is injured or deceased. In contrast, reconnaissance is the task of the third unit member, who also leads the operation. A fourth person is in control over the unit's communication and has to, for instance, be in contact with the Ajak-committee chief in order to prepare missions in the Ajak-committee chief's area (e.g. supplying weapons). In cases where the RKK-team has to plant bombs, the chief communicates with the bomb assembling unit or superiors, who provide explosive material. Another RKK-fighter is responsible for equipment, (heavy) weapons and bombs, while the last unit member serves as a paramedic in addition to his combat function.

According to the requirements of operations two or more teams can cooperate and, theoretically, all units can coalesce into a conventional force. However, the key tactical advantages of these commandos are speed, operational independence and low visibility, similar to a conventional army's Special Forces. When more RKK units are assembled for operations, the group risks losing this tactical advantage. Simply put, the more fighters assembled for an operation, the higher the risk that they will draw the attention of state security forces. Hence, usually no more than three or four squads are used at the same time and at the same place. Furthermore, the BRN-Coordinate military wing is almost impossible to infiltrate, as its RKK-squads are composed of only a small number of persons. Therefore, just as with the political structure, the lowest level of the military

wing is tactically more significant than higher levels, which serve only as formal command structures, i.e. command and control are exerted through it. Higher-level commanders have to report to their superiors about the success and failures of their subordinated units and they coordinate bigger operations such as the simultaneous, region-wide attacks on 22 banks on September 1st 2006, as mentioned above.

Such coordinated military action is planned and executed by the platoon, company and battalion commanders. One platoon commander stressed that he gave his RKK squads ample freedom for planning and executing their own operation. For him it was important that the squad commanders and Regu commanders acquired experience in both areas. He stressed that an important quality of these tactical commanders is that they constantly learn to innovate assault techniques in order to evade Thai counterinsurgency measures, which are, accordingly, also regularly improving. To be 'one step ahead', he stressed, is a key feature in any asymmetric war. After listening to their proposals for attacks, he would help them to correctly estimate the advantages and disadvantages of the different attacks. From this it can be assumed that the attacks on trains in Narathiwat's Rueso district in 2006 were proposed by RKK-squads and later meticulously planned and coordinated by their kopi. Those young RKK-squad leaders or Regu commanders, who proved to be willing, were rewarded by their company commander (kopi) by being assigned wider areas of command that were previously under the direct responsibility of the company commander himself. More conventional and less risky attacks such as the assassinations of Buddhist rubber planters on the fields were planned and executed by the squads themselves without their commander's help. Moreover, the commanders serve to implement the instructions of the military leadership within the DPP. Thus, while at least two RKK squads encountered during this study proposed to their commanders, for example, to kill Western foreigners (such as teachers or tourists) in the three provinces, commanders at the kawasan level turned down this proposal. Leadership at the DPP-level obviously spoke out against attacking Western targets, arguing that killing a Westerner would only trigger Western support for the Thai government's effort against them.

Like the members of the political wing, the members of the armed wing are amateurs, which stands in contrast to BRN's former guerrilla army in the 1970s that consisted of approximately 600 professional guerrillas. Being based in the villages, BRN-Coordinate now makes full use of the ambiguous nature of the partisan, who is distinguished from a regular soldier by his semi-regularity. Carrying guns and wearing a uniform, the conventional soldier is always distinguishable from the non-combatant, but the partisan's semi-regularity lies in the fact he or she switches surprisingly fast between the roles of the combatant and non-combatant (Münkler 1992). This constitutes military surplus in the guerrilla tactic and even more so in that of terrorism; guerrillas offer high mobility coupled with low visibility. The ambiguity of the partisan has made it very

hard for conventional armies to distinguish them from non-combatants. Here again, ambivalence enters the equation, a thing which modernity fears so much (Bauman 2004). Even the most technologically advanced army has severe problems with classifying a partisan -except in cases where the state can rely on police and intelligence information; but in those situations, the emergence of a guerrilla army would be less probable in the first place. Indeterminacy is the potency both of the partisan and the terrorist. While visible opposition enables knowledge and thus action, the horror of indeterminacy entails the behavioural paralyses or bloody COIN measures and crimes against the civilian population, as was the case during the American-Vietnam war.

Economically, an amateur force not only allows the group to save money, but, similar to the members of the political wing, fighters can cover-up their military operations with non-combatant everyday life activities. Since RKK fighters are amateurs and are only engaged in military operations part-time, the staff of the military wing are self-sufficient. Yet this dependence on voluntarism brings negative consequences as well, as members still have to be able to make a living. Combatants can usually choose their area of operation. In some cases, like Narathiwat province, it is not unusual that commanders might ask their fighters to move to places where they lack military personal, either for a short period or sometimes long term. Those that are asked to relocate may be new recruits or experienced fighters, depending on the needs of local RKK-squads. The local Ajak-committee can help fighters that are relocating to find accommodation and even, if possible, employment. Yet BRN-Coordinate's use of an amateur force and lack of payments sets a structural limit to such transfers. In Rueso district local villagers supplied the local company commander (kopi) with food, so that he could concentrate on his command and live underground. If the kopi was in need of additional money, villagers allowed him to tap rubber on their fields.

In addition to their "conventional force", BRN-Coordinate has built up a special force/commando section. This section seems to be composed of a highly experienced force that takes over special operations and can be deployed in different locations, working independently or in support of the regular military RKK-squads. Simply put, conventional RKK-squads and commando forces can be combined for certain operations. For the so-called "commando operations" battle-hardened fighters are assessed and selected based on their military performance. As far as Thai intelligence knows, the Special Forces are composed of a special assault unit, a bomb-assembling unit, a nursing unit, and a mountain force called "Harimau" (Tiger) in local Malay. The latter consists of RKK-fighters, who had to flee from state security forces into the jungle areas close to the Malaysian border.

In addition to the sheer size of BRN-Coordinate, its division of labour also determines its effectiveness. Like other insurgent organisations, BRN-Coordinate profits from teamwork and specialisation both between and within political and military wings. If an

RKK-squad places an explosive device at a police station, its accurate planning and safe implementation depends on detailed information about the target's weak points (e.g. times or places that remain un-policed, escape routes, etc), which can be provided by the local political wing. At the same time, the production of the explosive devices by separate, specialized teams allows the conventional RKK-squads to save time and be involved in the preparation of other operations, or simply to disappear under the cover of a "normal life", when necessary.

Specialized training is also provided to selected individuals who are given commanding positions (and function as instructors). Often these commanders go to Indonesia for training where they study, for example, insurgency techniques. In late 2009, intelligence reports suggested that BRN-Coordinate had tried to obtain Indonesian passports for some members, so that they could join the Indonesian military and thereby increase the group's access to military knowledge. In other instances, commanders-in-the-making studied in Southern Thailand, depending on their personal circumstances. This training can take up to three years or more. Furthermore, BRN-Coordinate also offers specialized training for bomb assembling. Recent intelligence indicates that the organisation attempts to increase their bomb-making skills (e.g. car bombs) through cooperation with Jemaah Islamiyah (JI).¹⁹

2.5. Secrecy: the community of the chosen ones

Another organisational feature of BRN-Coordinate is its hyper-secrecy. In the past, Patani insurgent groups claimed responsibility for violent attacks because they competed with each other in order to gain prestige, members and international support (interview with Che Wan Kadir, August 29, 2009). This practice proved fatal in the end, as it provided evidence to state security agencies, which were then able to destroy insurgent groups, once it had identified them. Unlike Central African states Southern Thailand is deprived of a hinterland where armed groups can form and hide without state surveillance. Hence these conditions forced insurgent leaders to adopt codes of secrecy, not only as a key principle guideline for all operations, but also as a fundamental feature of the organisation.

Like other secret organisations, BRN-Coordinate systematically teaches their members to remain silent (Simmel 1992). Internally, the practice of secrecy begins with recruitment and the oath of fidelity that members have to take, in which all of them swear to Allah that they will not give away any information about the group to outsiders (see next chapter). In other words, secrecy is considered a sign of devotion to God. Similar to al Qaida, the sanctification of the group is used to legitimise the

¹⁹ With regard to weapons, RKK's light and fast tactics do not require heavy weapons. Instead units are equipped with assault rifles, usually M-16 and AK-47 that were either captured from fallen soldiers, assaults on army camps or bought on the black market.

communicative isolation of members from an environment that might not support the use of violence. BRN-Coordinate recruiters tell young members that, because the jihad is a religious duty, permission, from parents, spouses, or the local Imam, to participate is not necessary. Here, BRN-Coordinate instructions resemble a transnational jihadist ideology like that of al-Suri's famous "The call to global resistance", in which al-Suri also stresses that the mujaheddin must not seek permission from parents and spouses if the jihad is required. This is, for example, the case, when infidels invade the land of Muslims (Lacey 2008: 175). Secrecy also means that communication is avoided and, if necessary, shortened in both vertical and horizontal directions within the group. Face-to-face contact is generally avoided; phones, mobile as well as public, are employed for communication and covert names are used. Often the real name of superiors or even fellow RKK unit members are not known. Under no circumstances should members talk about their involvement in public places, such as coffee shops or markets.

Before the outbreak of violence in 2004 this secrecy successfully prevented BRN-Coordinate's subversion from being detected and, presently, it still prevents observers from realising the full extent and sophistication of BRN-Coordinate's organisational structure, without which such an insurgency would not be possible (insurgent interview, July 25, 2009; Lt. General interview, September 14, 2009). As a member of the Department of Special Investigations (DSI) explained,

"[t]he fact that the DPP does not reveal its existence, is the best thing they can do to protect their organisation. For a long time even the commander of the 4th Army Area nor the police chiefs believed in its existence. Not to speak of the government in Bangkok. This way they can go on to work in Thailand and Malaysia without being bothered by any of the two governments."

As already mentioned, in this respect the size of the sub-group matters, because the successful arrest or infiltration of only one cell by state security forces will not harm to the organisation beyond that particular unit. Similarly, a defector can do little to destroy more than a single cell. Moreover, an ideal-type normal RKK-squad and Ajak-committee member only knows the identity of one of their superiors and, importantly, they remain unaware of the strategic knowledge of their superiors, as knowledge within the organisation is distributed on a need-to-know basis. A similar practice is used by, for example, the IRA (Hoffman 1999). It is only when a member is selected to take on a higher position that he or she is bestowed with the necessary knowledge needed to fulfil this position. Members of BRN-Coordinate have little or no access to objectified written knowledge pertaining to the organisation. Generally, for the sake of clandestinity, BRN-Coordinate knowledge is transmitted orally (see next chapter). Members are asked not to write down but to memorize the knowledge they gain from the organisation. In an interview with a key member of the BRN-Coordinate's economic section, the informant explained that he had to pass commander training for insurgency techniques (such as

mass psychology or the economic organisation of rebel organisations). He had to learn all of this by heart without taking notes. It was only after his educators fully trusted him that they provided him with an Indonesian-language insurgency manual from which the knowledge was obviously taken. A high-ranking member of BRN-Coordinate's economic section spoke of a BRN-Coordinate manual on the economic guidelines of the organisation, but he stressed that this manual was not to be given to rank-and-file members of the economic sections in the villages. Simply put, as is the case for other formalized organisations, BRN-Coordinate circulates and produces a lot of written material, but tightly controls its distribution. Importantly, when knowledge is not transmitted objectively by books, but by superiors, the social relations within the group are further strengthened. This mechanism is even more significant in societies where personal relations, like patron-client or teacher-student relations, dominate and moral authority is constituted by them and not by abstract institutions like universities, democracy, or a distinguished public sphere.

However, even less formalised forms of knowledge are restricted. Provincial and district level insurgents will usually never let normal Ajak-committee members know about the general state of the organisation in other areas. Rank-and-file members of the political and military wing also remain unaware of BRN-Coordinate's structure beyond their own range of face-to-face experiences. Although, for example, members of the military wing are typically aware of their immediate superiors (even here the rank-and-file may only be given pseudonyms) they do not know the identity of the superiors on the next higher level. Inferior ranks will not be informed of decisions unless they are seen to be directly affected by them. If it affects them in terms of new policies or immediate orders, they are informed not by the leadership organisation but by their immediate superior, who is formally their one and only link to the wider organisation. Thus members can only speculate about the organisation's size. In practice, however, Ajak-committee members might know fellow Ajak-committee members in neighbouring villages. In Songkhla province, where BRN-Coordinate suffers from a dearth of fighters, fighters are often deployed in more than one area in order to fill open positions at least on a temporary basis. As a consequence, RKK-fighters in Songkhla know many local Ajak-committee members or fellow RKK-fighters, which, after officials capture the few existing members, renders BRN-Coordinate there even weaker.

Hyper-clandestine group secrecy is never just a means of responding to external pressure, although it is the most radical and effective way of protection from state detection. As noted by one Malay insurgent, secrecy can be understood on religious grounds as the duty of a "warrior of Allah" (Askew 2009a). Besides, once secrecy becomes a central feature of a group, it heavily influences the non-members' understanding of the organisation. In most cases outsiders remain ignorant of the existence of the group or have only glimpses of knowledge about it. This

‘mysteriousness’ renders the insurgents more mysterious and powerful than they actually are.

However, secrecy also significantly influences the internal relationship between the group members, i.e. the constitution of the group. Not knowing the others seems to be no problem in motivating people to join. On the contrary, as Simmel pointed out, a secret group is not simply the sum of the people who hold a secret. The exclusion of others creates an intensive in-group identity, often a feeling of being member of a chosen group with exclusive knowledge that is withheld from “normal” people. The individual as the carrier of the secret feels a degree of superiority simply due to the fact that the secret is only accessible by the chosen ones (Simmel 1992). Such close epistemological communities thus bestow high moral value upon their members along with the burden to keep the secret. This psychological mechanism can even lead to a point, where the concept of secrecy even outshines its content, which is often only vaguely and ill defined.

These norms of exclusion can even work in social environments where norms of trust and cooperation are absent. For example, the existence of mafia organisations is proof that such organisational capacity is always possible even in societies with low social cohesion. Trust and normative relations can be reduced to an exclusive basis of “the chosen ones”, which continues to reproduce a state of isolation within epistemological communities; “[i]f I encounter no one with contrary beliefs, my own beliefs will tend to prevail by inertia and lack of questioning.” (Hardin 2004: 281).

More broadly speaking, all social organisations are implicitly the creations of social bonds which are based on emotions. Emotions such as hatred or fear not only play a role in the joining of an armed group, but they are also created by the social bonds within the armed group itself. Scheff (1990) argues that a most crucial human motive is the maintenance of bonds:

“Secure social bonds are the force that holds society together [...]. This force involves a balance between closeness and distance [...]. Optimal differentiation defines an intact social bond, a bond which balances the needs of the individual and the needs of the group. It involves being able to maintain ties with others who are different from self.”

Scheff 1990:4

With emotions being part of interaction, understanding implies not only the cognitive task of interpreting verbal symbols that are used within BRN-Coordinate, but also the decoding of emotional expressions. If a group or network successfully develops its own symbolism, these symbols serve as an in-group-out-group boundary and they accelerate processes of communication within the group. Both boundary and increased communication positively influences the ability of a group to act collectively (Korff 1992). Here Scheff uses the term „attunement“:

“I claim that the basic human bond involves mental and emotional connectedness, that social organisation requires (...) attunement between individuals, the sharing of thoughts and feelings. Society is possible to the extent that its members are able to connect with each other in this way.”

Scheff 1991:97

Scheff distinguishes between three types of social bonds: intact bonds, severed bonds and threatened bonds. Attunement is reached in secure bonds, in which those interacting understand each other and experience the bond as something positive. In contrast, threatened bonds imply “misunderstandings” (Scheff 1991). Bonds within secret organisations are threatened, for example, when a member assumes that a fellow member gives away the secret of the group or, for example, when a BRN-Coordinate member does not want to pay his membership fee (see below). The misunderstandings in turn threaten the bond even further. Whereas pride signals a secured bond, feelings of shame characterise a threatened bond. In other words, shame is not an internal affair within an individual, but it has to be understood within the social context of the bond.

2.6. State surveillance and the re-architecture of insurgency

In social movement research the exact connection between structural factors and the emergence of rebellious protest movements is still a contested issue. The mainstream “political process model” assumes that protesters rationally perceive and react to opportunity structures in their environment, that can either be within the economic, cultural or political sphere, in order to attain certain goals (Pettenkofer 2010). But the correlation between both has not yet been fully established, because in some contexts the closure of economic opportunities and political repression fostered the emergence of rebel movements (e.g. Sri Lanka), whereas in other cases the birth or revival of rebel movements went hand in hand with processes of democratisation and development. In Indonesia, for instance, GAM used the reformasi era to re-structure and re-arm their organisation after the more repressive New Order era (Stange & Patock 2010). In the first case lack of access to the political system is said to foster illegitimate forms of protest. Explanations for the latter phenomena have it that democracy provides rebels with a stable political context, including protection against unlawful state repression and the right of association, in which they can also build up systems of illegitimate protest.

In Southern Thailand the success of a more holistic counterinsurgency campaign by the Thai government named *Tai Rom Yen* (“South under a cool shade”), the introduction of development policies that acknowledged the culture of the South, democratisation in the 1980s, and the consequential decentralisation campaigns in Thailand all actually increased the political participation of Malay Muslims apparently led to a pacification. As the chances of an insurgent victory dimmed, the military wings of most groups lost importance. Division regarding on how to proceed led to conflicts within the separatist

movement. Rank-and-file members opted for amnesty or went to Malaysia, while core leaders settled in the Middle East or Europe, where they tried to uphold the spirit of Patani nationalism, although increasingly losing contact with what was happening on the ground (Pathan & Liow 2010). In the early 1990s an attempt to establish Bersatu as an umbrella organisation for the main insurgent organisation failed, because BRN-Coordinate decided not to join and the remaining members could not agree on how to pool their resources (interview Che Wan Kadir, Malaysia, September 2009). Also, newly established organisations such as the Gerakan Mujahideen Islam Patani (GMIP) failed to revive the insurgency. According to Pathan and Liow this apparent pacification “lulled Thai security forces into a false state of security” (Pathan & Liow 2010: 4). Besides, as Thompson (1966) points out, states have a tendency to fail to notice or misinterpret the first signs of insurgency.

Armed groups develop under certain limitations from the social, political and economic spheres - circumstances that thus determine their development. Adaptations made by armed groups are the result of a struggle for survival in a highly competitive environment. In the early phases, they especially depend on niches where state surveillance is weak, for example, spaces and times in which they are not monitored, and times when they can develop support from the population and establish their military capabilities. Adaptations are also influenced by past experiences of insurgency - both success and failure - which in Southern Thailand date back to the first half of the 20th century (Surin 1982) and are tied to current global innovations regarding in the use of violence (Schlichte 2009). Structural determinants, voluntary action, and the capacity to adapt to these structures, play important roles in the ability of an organisation to change (Crozier & Friedberg 1979).

The first of these structural limitations, which shape what is feasible is the general constellation of forces. Here, more than just the military constellation of power is important, as this applies to state surveillance as a whole. Like all social systems, states have inherent modes of control through which some agents attempt to achieve compliance from others, typically by commanding allocative or authoritative resources. If this compliance is institutionalized and stable, it constitutes rule (Giddens 1985). Regardless, if the state’s motivation is to foster development, spread the national language, prevent crime, vaccinate children, increase productivity, suppress a rebellion (or simply the impulses of those who are in positions of authority to be obeyed), the state requires units that are visible and, in the case of citizens, subject to social control (Shils 1975).

The concept of agency assumes that humans are able to make a difference to the world. For example, subordinates in control systems have counter-strategies against those who exert control. State control, on one hand, attempts to undermine, negotiate and create open resistance, while on the other hand, it determines the dialectics of control, with

some control systems being more irregular and volatile than others (Giddens 1985). As mentioned above, the institutionalisation of the Ajak system is a product of these processes. After the failure of their violent struggle in the early 1980s, insurgents probably realized that a conventional guerrilla struggle in the jungle, as, for instance, outlined by Mao's phased insurgency approach, in which guerrillas slowly develop into a conventional fighting force that eventually takes on the enemy in a decisive battle on the same terms, has little chance in Southern Thailand given the preponderance of the Thai military's power. In the hinterland of countries such as the Congo or the Northern part of Sri Lanka the formation of armed groups is facilitated by factors that are not present in Thailand. For example, the Tamil Tigers in Sri Lanka were able to construct a runway in the jungle and operated two planes used for airborne attacks against the Sri Lankan capital (personal conversation Dagmar Hellmann-Rajanayagam, 3 May 2009).

In Thailand the situation is more complex, as the construction of streets cutting through the jungle areas of Southern Thailand coupled with the presence of police and military forces render the success of jungle-based guerrilla war unlikely. However, state surveillance at the local level is not all-encompassing, which is an important condition for insurgent strategists. Significantly, this "freedom" derives from the independent but convergent qualities of state surveillance that are problematic for social control and highlight a weakness in the Thai bureaucracy. On one hand, the demographic structure in the South hampers state surveillance. Although urbanisation is increasing, a majority of the population in the South still live in the countryside and earn a living from agriculture. These conditions exacerbate direct social control in the sense of "optical surveillance", because surveillance depends on the concentration of activities (either over a period of a day or an entire lifetime) within specially constructed spaces and times (Giddens 1985). For this reason, Foucault (1995) chose prisons, asylums and capitalistic workplaces to illustrate the power of the panopticon. In contrast, farmers who reside in widespread villages and work in vast agricultural areas are almost impossible for the state to monitor - apart from patrols, which pass by now and then. Even when compared to the rice-growing villages in Northeast Thailand, whose settlements comprise nuclear households, homes in the three provinces are often dispersed at distances between 40 and 150 metres (Askew 2009b).

On the other hand, the state agency responsible for upholding the law, the Royal Thai Police, is known to be one of the most inefficient and corrupt state agencies in Thailand (Pasuk & Sungsidh 1996). In Southern Thailand, inefficiency is perpetuated by a shortage of policemen, especially those with Malay language skills and informal ties to the Malay communities. When the correlation between space and time is considered, this tendency worsens. In modern, bureaucratic Thailand, provincially based social control is concentrated in the urban provincial capitals and only partially extends into the district capitals. It is here where the federal ministries as well as the police have

their last “outposts”, with the former represented by the district offices (Nelson 2001). At the sub-district and village levels, bureaucratic social control is weakly institutionalized and is replaced instead by the ‘personal rule’ of the sub-district chiefs (kamnan) and the village heads (phuyaiban). Both are what (1990) calls „specialist intermediaries“, relatively independent of the social control of the subject population and of the disciplinary power of the bureaucracy. Consequently, rule of law is rather a matter for the state and not the common people. To many rural Malays, the state is distant, incomprehensible, and its services generally only available to people who have the right connections and are willing to pay the price.

In one village in Rueso district, where the entire village had joined BRN-Coordinate, villagers told me that they hadn’t seen the Thai police in their village for many years, except on very rare occasions. Local police headquarters are contained within the local district towns, a 30-minute car ride on poor quality roads. Police visits to the villages were sporadic and usually for punitive or extraordinary purposes. Police considered the village to be “wild and rebellious” and only came to make arrests, often without evidence. At the same time, the state did not provide any services to the village. Generally, officials from the district office did not dare to visit the village without police protection. District officials told me that development funds from various ministries were actually available to the village, but they admitted to not having ever told the village heads about the funds the villages are entitled to. Simultaneously, this lack of “presence availability” (Giddens 1985) of the state meant that BRN-Coordinate did not have to worry about security. Indoctrinators openly entered the village and publicly held speeches in order to recruit members, so that finally, the whole village would join the organisation. Villagers even dared to publicly “defy” the symbolic power of the Thai state by refusing to raise the Thai flag in the village, except during certain occasions when the district office ordered all villages in the area to do so (e.g. for a royal visit to the district). Some villagers mentioned that they secretly opposed entering the organisation but they felt forced to do so because most other villagers were joining.

However, even this critical faction within the village shows us that they certainly had not thought about informing the police about the insurgent’s activities. Their reluctance stemmed from ties to the organisation, since their own relatives, neighbours and friends, had joined the organisation and, as one of them remarked, “... some of us surely opposed the violence, but the state had never done any good for us, so why should we give our friends away?” For the villagers, justice and protection did not come from the government and the rule of law, it existed in the local community ties. Thus, the weakly institutionalized presence of the Thai state and the lack of state surveillance went hand in hand with a nonexistent state legitimacy. According to Hobsbawm (1991) the project of the nation-state in many states of Western Europe remained a bourgeois project in its first phase; the abstract ideology at the time only mattered to the educated classes. It

only became legitimate among the rural population after the state established its presence in everyday life and provided meaningful services. In many Malay villages in Southern Thailand, state power has not yet been understood as positive in terms of development or the rule of law, which would strengthen legitimacy. Rather the state is seen as a power that enforces corrupt and hostile rule as well as imposing foreign culture from Bangkok on locals. Hence the willingness to obey remains limited, whereas their ability to avoid obeying, especially in the countryside, remains rather high.

Another significant feature of state surveillance at the local level is the demise of the “traditional authority” of the village heads and the kamnan. This authority has been undermined in recent decades, having already been a common occurrence in other parts of Thailand. Short-term market relations between local patrons and their clients increasingly have replaced traditional forms of power. During election times, the population elects the candidate that pays the highest amount for their vote (Arghiros 2001). At the same time the void in local social control has only partly been filled by modern bureaucratic structures. And in some remote Malay villages that are labelled “problematic” by government officials, the void has not been filled at all (McCargo 2008).

Although state surveillance is seen as effective enough to push armed groups into secrecy, it still does not create “general discipline” in Foucault’s sense. Consider the following quote of a village head:

“The Thais have their humvees, helicopters, tanks, all their other stuff, and their guns. They are driving through the area all the time. But it’s funny. They come, ask stupid question and leave, then they come again, ask other stupid questions and leave. They simply don’t know what is going on in front of their eyes.”

Under the surface of conformity people evade power, and develop a myriad of ways to resist it in different situations. Insurgents go beyond this situational, disconnected atomized resistance and “reappropriate the space organized by sociocultural production” (Certeau 2002: xiv) by creating a violent counter-apparatus. On the village level the lack of effective state control allows for the establishment of insurgent organisations and the use of terrorist violence. There is no secret behind the use of violence in Southern Thailand; it follows the simple rules of irregular warfare: fight the war for which you are best prepared. This also includes the strategic use of violence against civilians. Ideologically, the lack of state services provided to many Malay villages renders the local population susceptible to anti-state propaganda.

In this sense, the Ajak-committee system makes full use of the uncontrolled space below the district level and the weak policing capabilities of the Thai state. Hiding among the civil population, insurgents can switch surprisingly easily between their

everyday non-combatant lives and their combatant functions. Not only does civil life provide a livelihood for fighters; insurgents also use the civil population as a shield against government repression. If the government attacks the insurgents directly, they are unable to distinguish between combatants and non-combatants, which can push formerly neutral parts of the population towards the side of the insurgents. In addition to the national environment, the government must also pay attention to the international environment that determines the agency of insurgents. In the case of Southern Thailand, Malaysia provides significant safe-havens for the leadership and the insurgents' general strategy is coordinated within its borders. Many DPP members, and even leaders at the provincial level, reside in Malaysia, and some in Europe.

Besides the general constellation of power, another important condition for armed groups is the given socialisation of members and general customs within a society. Armed groups operate within the moral order of the local society, although they try to manipulate these conditions. This not only is a question of violence - it relates directly to the legitimate use of violence (as will be shown later). BRN's former core ideology centred on what the group members call NASOSI, an ideological blend of nationalist, socialist and Islamic elements, which was formally integrated into BRN's constitution in 1963 under the influence of the socialist-leaning Ahmad "Mat" Bong, who borrowed it from Sukarno's 1945 original five-point version of the Pancasila (Davis 2010). Members envisioned a political republic with a socialist economy and Islam in the cultural sphere. Similar Islamic style forms of socialism were also envisioned, for example, by Syria's Ba'ath party, and in other countries where BRN members often went to study. In order to gain support, other competing groups like PULO argued that BRN's socialism was against Islam. BRN members who drew on ideologies such as Ba'ath's argued that the Koran, which states that there should be no division between the rich and the poor, could justify socialism.

Especially since the rise of Islamism in the 1980s and the end of the Cold War, PULO and other groups that competed against BRN for members and resources, had spread rumours that BRN socialism was "un-Islamic". However, before that time the approach to Islam among BRN and other separatist organisations was different. Many argued that "to be Patani Malay means to be Muslim".²⁰ Yet, this description hides an important change in the construction of Malay identity. Before the revival of Islam, religion was only one element among others that constituted Malay identity. To put it more clearly, Islam was not made too explicit; it was simply assumed to be there. However, as the Islamic religion rose to a higher level within the new urban ethno-religious consciousness, BRN experienced a similar change.

²⁰ Like in any other constructions of ethnic identity, this definition becomes very fuzzy at its borders. First, scholars tend to forget Malays who converted to Buddhism because they married a Buddhist. Secondly, in Narathiwat, for example, a village of Malays resisted Islamisation in the past and instead adopted modern Thai Buddhism. These "assimilated" Malays tend to forget about their ethnic Malay origins and refer to themselves as "Thai-Buddhists".

Furthermore, BRN and other separatist organisations faced a crisis in the second half of the 1980s, when guerrilla forces left the jungle and the pacification of the three provinces rendered them weak. Hard-core insurgents knew that they had to redesign not only their military approach, but also their ideology, in order to mobilise their population. The production of these political agendas was, of course, influenced by pragmatic concerns, intellectual involvement in global discourses, and social change in the region. During the 1980s, more and more Malays had the opportunity to study in the Middle East via oil scholarships. At the intellectual centres of Islamic universities and religious institutions, insurgents adopted and modified transnational Islamist discourses for their own purpose in order to revive the local separatist movement. In other words, the global recession of socialism and the spread of religion as the basis of armed groups also influenced BRN leaders. BRN-Coordinate let go of the socialist element, and instead focused on a dogmatic duo comprised of nationalism (*nationalis*) and Islam (*islamis*), an analysis of which will follow in the next two chapters. This ideological change to Islamo-nationalism partly reflects the end of the cold war, internal struggles over ideology coupled with the transnational rise of charismatic jihadist thought that is now at the centre of the group's legitimacy. Socially, this change in ideology was accompanied by a growth in the Malay Muslim middle class in the general region (Horstmann 2002), and within the leadership ranks of BRN-Coordinate in particular (although the latter point is statistically hard to verify). For example, Che Wan Kadir (1990) noted that although Islamic scholars have been at the forefront of Malay Muslim resistance against the Thai state, few Malaysians before the 1960s and 1970s had university degrees. As a consequence, insurgent organisations had difficulties recruiting intellectual leaders and hence there is a comparable lack of Islamist intellectuals who are willing to support the insurgent movement, either in deeds or in words (interview Che Wan Kadir August 7, 2009).

To put it differently, BRN-Coordinate seems to have changed their agenda from a rather secular, politically rebellious agenda (NASOSI) to religious conservatism, although they remain socially rebellious. This switch also hints at the structural environment of the insurgency; it is no longer the call for food or land that mobilises peasants, as was the case during communist insurgencies. At present, the continuous exploitation of Patani nationalism, and the feeling of being ruled by foreigners, reloaded by a global rise in Islamism as part of current social change act together as motivating forces. As a former Ajak-committee chief from a village in Yala stated, “[i]t's not economic arguments, which help to mobilise the people in my village, but we try to make people join by talking about religion and how cruel the Thais treat the Malays.”

The movement of Islamism into the centre of the group's narratives also allows BRN coordinate to draw on Southern Thai “religious infrastructure”, including basic religious knowledge, cognitive plausibility structures, networks of mosques and religious

schools, etc., in order to mobilise the population. According to Tilly (1978), the capacity for mobilisation is a major factor in inter-group conflict. He stresses pre-existing linkages between persons and groups as a key factor for the intensity and course of the politics of contention. BRN-Coordinate recruiters also try to involve Imams, as well as other local community leaders, in order to use mosques for recruitment and political sermons. Recently, the state-sponsored growth in Private Religious Schools has become another main source for BRN-Coordinate's recruitment strategy (Davis 2004).

However, the shift towards Islamism within BRN-Coordinate also created disadvantages and limitations. An independent, Islamic state of Patani is a relatively abstract concept for the majority of peasants in Southern Thailand. The Viet Cong faced a similar problem in South Vietnam; the unification of Vietnam was an intangible concept for the majority of peasants in South Vietnam. In order to mobilise the peasant's support, the NLF was forced to identify and address the most significant problems for the South Vietnamese peasants (Pike 1968). It was through this method that the Vietcong's promise of a better life became convincing and understandable for local peasants. Yet, despite BRN-Coordinate's intensive campaign planning, its leadership seems to neglect this dimension. For a majority of the Malay peasants in Southern Thailand, issues such as employment, measures against drug addiction among youth, and education, are more important than an Islamic bureaucracy, which is the main interest for many Muslim intellectuals. During this research, Ajak-committee chiefs, as well as other higher-ranking insurgents at the sukum level, had limited knowledge about what issues mattered to villagers. Insurgents have little or no programs orientated towards the world of the locals.

Instead, for mobilization they relied solely on the ideological repertoire of the organisation, although in some villages the Ajak-committee used its young men for collective tasks such as building Mosques, helping poor farmers harvest or prepare village feasts. One commander of the military wing told me that he received a great amount of gratitude from the locals in his home village, because he tried to remove their drug-addicted children from the streets by recruiting them into the movement. Villagers were surprised that he could turn the children, who had been a source of fear for many people in the village, into devout and friendly Muslims.

2.7. A network or hierarchical organisation?

With regards to BRN-Coordinate's status as either a network or an organisation, the literature is marked by disagreement. Reflecting the idea of a shift from "old" hierarchical rebel organisations towards network-based warfare, Liow and Pathan speak of a fundamentally "new insurgency" in Southern Thailand, which is deprived of hierarchical elements:

“While insurgents had previously organised around formal separatist organisations with political and military wings, their successors appear to be organised around a nebulous network of cells and armed groups with no clear line of authority or formal nomenclature.”

Liow & Pathan 2010: xiii

Somewhat contradicting this view, BRN-Coordinate has been described as an (hierarchical) organisation that broadly mirrors the Thai state administrative structure in “Jane’s World Insurgency and Terrorism” (2007) and in Abuza’s “Conspiracy of Silence” (2009). So where can we locate BRN-Coordinate between these two approaches? On the one hand, the latter two accounts are rather scarce in detailed data on the group. Besides, they cannot explain clearly how network elements and hierarchy go together. On the other hand, it is still questionable, whether the thesis of ‘network-like groups’ as proposed by Liow and Pathan is verifiable.

Surely, the increased lethality of the insurgency in the three provinces and the use of religion for its legitimacy have to be explained, but we need to question, whether we are really dealing with a “new insurgency”. Should we really be skipping over old models of hierarchical organisation? The point is not that there have been no changes in the mode of the group’s organisation, but rather that these changes have to be delineated. As already mentioned in the introduction, the past shift from old vertical organisation to network-based warfare is not as marked as the so-called “new terrorism” or “new war” accounts make it out to be.²¹

While a fact-based comparison between the “old” (BRN) and “new” BRN-Coordinate cannot be done here, available data indicate, however, that, like many other insurgent groups, BRN-Coordinate is a hybrid structure with a hierarchical core at the centre and network elements “on the ground” or, as Horgan and Taylor (1997: 3) have put it, “a cellular-based, hierarchically-organized authoritarian structure“. In the analytical triangle of market, hierarchy and network, organisations are often classified in a reducing “either ... or ...” manner. ‘Old’ terrorism is said to resemble top-down military organisation and therefore fits into the “hierarchy”-category, whereas the “new” terrorism of Hamas or al Qaida is supposed to neatly fit into the network category. Yet, as Mayntz (2004) reminds us, one has to distinguish between a network as an empirical phenomenon and as an analytical category, otherwise, contradictory elements can be overlooked.

Although we also find examples of small, unorganised and rather undistinguished

²¹ Crenshaw points out that the current “new terrorism” model exerts a certain appeal, because it serves as a justification for the global war on terrorism: “Defining jihadist terrorism as entirely new is a way of framing the threat so as to mobilise both public and elite support for costly responses that have long-term and uncertain pay-offs” (Crenshaw 2009: 133). Besides, the idea allows analysts to process the very little data they have, which is not only incomplete, but also contradictory. Relying on a framework that easily allows for labelling groups like Hezbollah, Hamas or the LTTE as “terrorist organisations” saves policy-makers and their advising “experts” from coping with the these troublesome groups, of which some are partly democratically-elected.

terrorist groups that either themselves recruit or build up relations with fellow jihadists through the internet, it seems that the “new terrorism” or “net-war” paradigms overlook that many, if not most, guerrilla groups, have an inherent tendency to take advantage of central planning, which is, in contrast to networks, based on a constant flow of explicit commands or codes of conduct, as well as an elaborate system of divided labour (Mayntz 2004; Crenshaw 2009), and which provides its leaders the powers of decision making. Leaders are needed to distribute different tasks, gather and process information, and make necessary adaptations to possible changes in the organisation’s environment, or “adapt long-range goals to immediate demands” (Lichbach 1998: 169). If necessary, they also represent the organisation to external actors, such as international agencies, states or journalists. Gurr, who understands the effectiveness of dissidents as the function of cohesiveness and complexity of organisations, argues that “[c]ohesiveness is the extent of goal consensus and cooperative interaction among members; complexity is the extent of hierarchical and functional differentiation within an organisation” (Gurr quoted in Lichbach 1998: 167).

Even al Qaida, for example, started off as a hierarchical organisation, as without its planning capacity the initial establishment of large suicide training camps would hardly be possible. It was only after the invasion of Afghanistan by coalition forces that al Qaida had to dissolve its organisation, which meant a significant blow to its professionalism, and ability to plan large-scale attacks (Sageman 2008). The addition of network elements in informal organisations like armed groups, who by nature resemble hierarchical military organisations, is apparently a reaction to the necessity of self-protection in the underground and are part of the “auto-dynamic” processes of violence.

The IRA, for instance, reacted to successful state repression by including more and more network elements in their formerly army-like strict hierarchical organisation, with the so-called Active Service Units (ASU) operating autonomously on the ground level. But whereas the “new” network elements have replaced the “old” in al Qaida, the IRA remained a classical organisation (Horgan & Taylor 1997). The tendency to establish and maintain the advantages of a central organisation in warfare was also illustrated by the apparently opposite development in Sri Lanka: small renegade gangs of Tamil youth, who robbed banks, began to build an organisational structure, from which later the LTTE emerged, only after they were repressed by the Sri Lankan government (Hellmann-Rajanayagam 1994). In contrast to the situation in Northern Ireland, however, Sri Lanka had a vaster hinterland and the state itself had much less surveillance capacity control. Together with support from the Tamil population this allowed for the movement towards hierarchy.²²

²² It should be mentioned, however, that some armed groups simply make use of universal hierarchical forms, because they aim at international recognition and support – this tendency is called isomorphism. The actual internal practices of the group can follow very different rules.

Similar to the IRA, BRN-Coordinate seems to be a hybrid structure that started off as a hierarchical organisation and included, in the course of its reorganisation since it split from BRN central in the 1980s, more and more network elements - though it is not clear when exactly this process took place. In other words, the “new” has not been replaced, but rather supplemented the “old” to a degree. The following elements constitute the hierarchical core of BRN-Coordinate: (1) similar to its predecessor organisation, BRN, BRN-Coordinate formalized its set-up through a constitution. The BRN-Coordinate constitution, probably a derivative of the original BRN constitution, more or less clearly defines the functions of different councils, sections etc. thus reducing conflicts over power and competences; (2) a clearly defined leadership committee (DPP) that outlines the strategy and framework for the organisation’s local tactics; (3) vertical differentiations divided into ranks and distinguished functions within the DPP leadership as well as in the military and political wings.

As illustrated above, the resulting roles have clearly defined tasks and responsibilities. For instance, members of the economic sections have clear guidelines, in the form of written handbooks that instruct how to manage money generated from economic activities, offering such guidance as to not leave money in Thai bank accounts so that they do not draw the attention of Thai officials. Moreover, assigned roles link the leadership committee (DPP) and both wings such as the KAS. Vertically, working committees link the political and armed wings, although these are restricted in number in order to avoid conflicts of authority a chronic problem for all armed groups. In contrast to the classical Maoist model of guerrilla organisations, in which political officers control the military wing at various levels, BRN-Coordinate’s political wing’s control of the military is restricted, probably due to security reasons. In this sense, the most important working committee is that between the sukum-committee chief, the head of the ulama section at the sukum level, frequently a recognized Islamic scholar, and the kopi (company commander) of the armed wing. In contrast to other organisations such as the IRA where local cells often seem to deliberately disobey and thus embarrass the head of the political wing (Hardin 1995), RKK-squads appear to be under the broad control of the organisation’s head.

This “big three” seems to constitute a key operational centre below the DPP leadership; here operations are planned and the work between both wings is coordinated. Meetings between them take place approximately once a month. Significantly, as far as is known from Narathiwat and Pattani, the sukum-committee chief and the head of the ulama section have to agree on larger military operations, especially when Malays are assassinated, where the ulama has to issue a fatwa. In other words, the political wing at the sukum level exerts what may be formally sanctioned authority over the armed wing. Beyond that function, as far as information from Rueso district in Narathiwat indicates, the ulama seems to keep out of military as well as political affairs and restricts himself

to the religious sphere. Hence, he can also play the role of a possible negotiator, in cases where conflicts arise between the kopi commander and the sukum-committee chief - a typical situation for all armed groups (Schlichte 2009). This view contradicts the account of Liow and Pathan (2010), who assume that the BRN-Coordinate mainly consists of an ulama wing and an armed wing, which is typical in other Islamic organisations such as Hizbollah (Ranstorp 1994). It seems, however, that despite the increased use of Islamist rhetoric, BRN-Coordinate rejected this model, maintaining the division between military and political wings that was typically used in Asia since the spread of the Mao Zedong protracted warfare model.

The sukum-committee chief also plays an important role in the aggregation of information. Formal information flows from the Ajak-level, via the ligaran, to the komis, who reports problems and assessments of recent policies issued to the local level by the sukum-committee chief. Matters, which are regularly reported include, for example, numbers regarding the recruitment and estimates of popular support for BRN-Coordinate in the villages. These estimates are passed on to superiors in written form - an indication of a rather high degree of formalisation. Simultaneously, orders, instructions or proposals for improvement are transmitted from the sukum level. For example, when the recruitment of villagers into the Ajak system does not proceed as expected by the sukum-committee chief, he can provide instructions in order to improve recruitment. A measure that the sukum-committee chief may take is to send, for example, "charismatic recruiters" from other areas into the desired target villages. The sukum-committee chief can also order the military wing to execute certain military operations that aim to increase or trigger negative sentiments in the Malay population against the Thai state. This can, for instance, take the form of insurgents who dress in Thai military uniforms and attack Malay civilian targets. Because BRN-Coordinate depends on support from the local population, the sukum-committee must also evaluate how the local Malays perceive specific insurgent military operations in the area. In cases where the population does not approve of certain military operations (such as the bombings of a market or the unintended killings of Malays), the sukum-committee must counter this public opinion, for example through the use of rumours or letters (see also chapter 4).

Judging from interviews with military commanders, it is not yet clear what the exact role and function of the KAS is. Does he simply serve as a transmission for information between the DPP and the political wing or does he have a more decisive role in the organisation? For example, in the Pattani province one KAS member maintained a restricted role, hiding in Malaysia because the Thai security forces were searching for him.

In addition to these hierarchical features, BRN-Coordinate also has the features of networks. Firstly, though the form of the political and military cells is specified and

although the BRN-Coordinate leadership frames typical practices, there is no central governance over detailed action. Sub-units on the ground are relatively autonomous in their everyday actions. For instance, the time and place of attacks are not given, but it is important, that there is a regular show of force. Only if this is omitted, will superiors intervene. Similarly, recruiters are given a repertoire of recruitment techniques (both symbolical and psychological) and areas for recruitment. But aside from these two instructions, the rest of the job is up to them. In the area of economics, the Ajak-committees are free to discover and broaden their sources of income as long as they do not threaten the secrecy of the organisation. Secondly, under the selective pressure of violence BRN-Coordinate can quickly react by changing its organisational structure on the ground. The deployment of village-based Thai COIN units over the last few years has increasingly (at least in some successful cases) exposed insurgents to the risk of detection, because it enabled agents, who were constantly present on the ground, to monitoring of local activities. In a number of known cases, insurgents reacted by reducing the Ajak-committee to a sort of “emergency” version, in which almost all members freeze their activities except for a few key members (see also chapter 4).

If we assume that BRN-Coordinate is a hybrid composition, one important question comes up, namely as to what holds these elements together. Mayntz (2004) stressed three elements that, taken together, explain the cohesion of these hybrid structures: Firstly, although the local units exert a degree of autonomy from superior commands and are not monitored all the time, they appear to be generally driven by the objectives of the group. Secondly, hybrid structures like BRN-Coordinate are characterized by a loose coupling between horizontal and vertical elements, which means that relations between units operating on the ground and their superiors exist, but are not always manifested in observable action. Direct interaction between elements is typically rare in a secret organisation in order to protect the group from detection. However, they can always be mobilised (orders for specific operations are given, for instance, by telephone). It is this latent quality of relations in hybrid underground organisations that makes them so hard to explain, and, together with the hierarchical core, distinguishes hybrid structures such as BRN-Coordinate from networks, in which coordination of action is based on negotiation and exchange of certain resources or services.

Finally, a third element might explain the first two specific qualities of the hybrid organisation, namely a strong identification of members with the organisation, and its aims. This identification is partly a product of training. As one BRN-Coordinate military commander explains, his ability to command and coordinate military action on a systematic scale depends on standardizing training:

“If I create a new RKK-squad, I usually compose them of older, more experienced fighters in order to compensate for the less experienced. Sometimes I give them advice, but in general the younger ones need to have passed the same training as the others. They have to know basic

military planning; they have to know how to handle weapons, how to approach a target; they have to know what to do, when their buddies are on the defensive. We can not do all this training only on the job and I can not sit down with every one of them. That is too risky under the current conditions.”

Importantly, this common knowledge and identification of the group enables even strangers to act together within an RKK-squad, in a constellation of squads, and with members of the political wing in certain operations. Hence trust in the context of loose coupling is a central element as a condition for collective agency under conditions of violence, not the least because the cost of failing to cooperate is immensely high. Insurgent military action by autonomous local units is united through this sort of latent connection, too, as Smith points out: “there is no manoeuvre of forces, no design for battle and no immediate connectivity with operations elsewhere. Each engagement is particular unto itself and in its setting, but connected together through a nervous system by an overarching political idea.” (Smith 2007: 331).

However, rational choice approaches to insurgency as Kalyvas or Weinstein propose, appear insufficient to explain why people are willing to risk their lives in an armed struggle against a superior military force, and why they see their single actions as part of a wider campaign. Couldn't it be Mafia members or politicians, who are responsible for assassinations and arson as some conspiracy theories propose (Askew 2007)? Interestingly, most insurgents I interviewed did not believe so. They were clearly convinced that most attacks were the result of their fellow insurgents. In other words, the attachment and identification with the general objectives and codes of conduct of the group seems also to be the result of the mobilizing force of charisma.

Taking into account available data on BRN-Coordinate, it is possible to add surveillance among peers and by superiors as an additional factor that contributes to the group's cohesion (for details see next chapter). Although recruits are typically not forced to join the group, and rather act with intrinsic motivation, they are kept in line by the permanent threat of being punished (in the case that one should give away a “brother in arms”). This way the group can lower the risk of defection. Such a repressive element seemingly contradicts the high-commitment voluntarism of activist rebellions, but, as mentioned before, in practice the combination of internal self and external control significantly contributes to cohesion and trust within (armed) groups.

Although this mode of organisation explains why BRN-Coordinate members act professionally and adhere to certain codes of conduct (e.g. there is no pre-mortal torture or indiscriminate violence against Malay civilians), this does not mean that there is no behaviour outside of what superiors expect from rank-and-file members. Behaviour that contradicts the formal expectations of organisations can be dysfunctional, but at other times, it can also lead to innovation, or solve organisational problems that cannot be solved by conventional behaviour (Luhmann 1976).

For instance, Thai security forces, and the various self-defence groups in local Buddhist communities constantly attempt to improve their protection against insurgent attacks. Hence, within the given organisational conditions, the military and political wings exert certain freedoms that allow them to attempt to locate new opportunities for potential targets. For example, RKK units can decide the time, place, forms and targets of their attacks, although members of the political section and military commanders must explicitly allow for bigger operations. Here, new forms of attack or methods for transporting weapons can be invented and the successful experiences are shared with other units.

Behaving under conditions of secrecy also means, however, that members can mask their activities in order to protect themselves against sanctions by superiors. Scholars indicate that cloaking strategies of informal networks within complex non-secret organisations do exist (Vaughan 1999), but under conditions of secrecy that limit monitoring capabilities, cloaking is even easier. For instance, in one district in Narathiwat province, the Ajak-committee chiefs reported to superiors that they had built up strong support networks and that members in their villages were highly loyal to BRN-Coordinate.

However, the actual situation was quite different. Among other deficiencies, the responsible sukum-committee chief and the head of the sukum's ulama section often refrained from consenting to the killing of local Malays who directly supported the enemy. In other districts, these people would have been killed. In this region, however, the sukum-committee chief and the ulama apparently had personal connections to the potential victims, such as through informal networks like friendship, kinship or acquaintance, which overlapped with and contradicted formal loyalties to the organisation.

More often than in other parts of Narathiwat, military operations (e.g. bomb attacks, assassinations) planned by the local armed wing were called off or undermined by members of the local political wing, under the pretext that the risks were too high. As one RKK member commented about the situation, “[similar] military operations had been executed in other districts under the same conditions. But here they just didn't dare”. It is probable that Ajak-committee chiefs feared a tightening of state security and an increase in security presence, which would lead to interrogations as well as counterinsurgency measures - a common occurrence after such attacks.

Superiors above the sukum level had to rely on “local knowledge” provided by the district's political wing, which reported that “everything was fine” and that BRN-Coordinate had a strong presence in the area. For security reasons, superiors on the provincial level, responsible for the district, often lurked in Malaysia, hiding from Thai prosecution. Therefore they could hardly confirm on the local political wing's report on membership numbers or the degree of members' loyalty. However, after some period of

time, the local armed wing began to complain about the political counterpart to members of the armed wing in the Pattani province, whom they knew personally. Only then did the BRN-Coordinate's leadership intervene in the district, sending a skilled kopi company commander from the Pattani province to restore the military efficiency in the sukum-committee chief's area. Among the BRN-Coordinate's leadership the kopi probably enjoyed a high degree of trust, since, on one hand, he was married to the daughter of one of the KAS chiefs, while on the other, he had proven to be capable military commander.

Trust is a crucial issue in secret organisations: since BRN-Coordinate leaders who reside abroad failed, to some degree, to control the past performance of the sukum chief, they were also equally limited in attempts to control and properly assess the kopi's performance. Hence, they had to trust him based on his past achievements and his informal relationship to his father in law. As discussed in the next chapter, peer monitoring at the lower level of the organisation is easier and prevalent within Ajak-committees and RKK squads. However, the same kopi faced difficulties, as he was not entangled in personal relationships in the problematic district, which were obviously responsible for the sukum-committee chief's tendency to call off or not allow military operations. This case illustrates the ambivalent nature of informal relations within BRN-Coordinate's organisation; they can obstruct the recognition of organisational goals, as was the case with the sukum's personal relations, while at the same time they may improve the chances of such success, such as the kopi's endorsement by his father-in-law.

2.8. Centrifugal forces and centripetal mechanisms

With regard to the bureaucratisation of armed groups, Schlichte argues that there are several "centrifugal forces", which potentially threaten the hierarchization and integration of armed groups. Some of these forces are related to specific conditions of armed groups, while others are faced by all organisations. An important "centrifugal force" is the delegitimizing effect of violence, as outlined in chapter four. This section will focus instead on the question of power struggles and differentiation within armed groups. The reverse side of functional differentiation and growth of (armed) groups is that it usually leads to conflicts over competence, power positions and resources among units, branches and individuals (Schlichte 2009). This is especially true for chronic conflicts between armed and political wings that threaten the cohesion of armed groups. The latter seems to have played a role in the split-up of BRN into BRN-Coordinate and BRN-Congress in the early 1980s.

Schlichte (2009) discusses three mechanisms that armed groups can use as "counter-forces" against the centrifugal forces, which work against disintegration and support the cohesiveness: Firstly, armed groups subject their members (which includes the double-

edged process of indoctrination where members are turned), on the one hand, into conscious activists, and, on the other hand, into subjects of the organisation. The following chapter will illustrate how BRN-Coordinate moulds its recruits into highly obedient and disciplined forces. Secondly, armed groups can shuffle power positions in order to mitigate conflicts over power. Currently, there is no information about whether BRN-Coordinate makes use of such practices at the leadership level. Thirdly, armed groups can formalize, which basically means that power is depersonalized and executed by formally defined roles, paying attention to rules as well as procedures (Schlichte 2009).

One feature of formalization is, for example, that BRN-Coordinate divides the field of action into different combat zones. Furthermore, there are few cashable resources in these areas, making the emergence of patrimonial warlords improbable, limiting the desire of expansion of responsibility. Formalisation concerns not only areal responsibility as a form of division of power, but also includes definitions of roles and responsibilities as mentioned above. The BRN-Coordinate constitution is said to demand, for instance, that in the case of the death of the Chairman, the Vice-Chairman will become chairman for life without election, in order to reduce power struggles. This stipulation seems to be a reaction to past power struggles within the organisation. Organisations that rest on the charisma of a single leader are prone to disintegration resulting from struggles over succession, once the leader dies or becomes ineffective. It is not only the size of BRN-Coordinate that demands formalisation, but also the increase in potential conflicts for power.

In addition to these mechanisms secret organisations have some specific mechanisms that address potentially destructive conflicts over power within the group. Rather than channelling conflicts these mechanism avoiding them in the first place. Generally, the growth of secret societies is less driven by what Simmel (1992) calls “organically instinctive forces”. Rather it is directed by intended rationality, as expressed by its clear-cut hierarchy. In cases of armed groups, these forces can be, for instance, the demands of foreign donors. Foreign funds as well as cashable resources such as diamonds, if they exist in a large quantity, tend to undermine the discipline of armed groups, as Weinstein (2007) has shown.

Here it is notable that BRN-Coordinate has not yet successfully established formal rule over a territory. Direct rule over an area leads to a significant increase in conflict, as rule over territory implies power over resources such as administrative positions, distribution of land, etc. Yet, if clandestine groups are both formalised and cohesive, they can also protect themselves against the corrupting influence of ruling governments and local mafias. Interestingly, the most successful “insurgent hunters”, the Thai police and military, stressed that local Mafia figures usually remain ignorant of who the insurgents are, even in their “own area of action”. Since members of organised crime

offer no information about insurgent suspects and their hideouts, they play almost no role in the investigative practice. At the local level at least, both groups seem to avoid confrontation as well as cooperation. A systematic cooperation between, for example, drug traders and insurgents would undermine the self-perception of insurgents, who believe that they are devout Muslims fighting for an Islamic order and thus believe that the spread of drugs represents the moral disintegration of society.

Concerning politicians, the picture appears different; although evidence is still patchy. Many rank-and-file insurgents seem to consider politicians to be the corrupt henchmen of the Thai political system. However, at the DPP level, there are personal overlaps. For instance, the head of BRN-Coordinate's economic council is also a founding member of the so-called Wadah faction of the Malay Muslim politicians in Southern Thailand. Moreover, groups acting undisclosed generally limit conflict over its members' loyalties to other organisations or social units. Usually bonds, such as family, job, and religious community, openly compete for the time and strength of the individual. In contrast, clandestine organisations hardly collide with such open loyalties due to their secrecy (Simmel 1992).

Nevertheless, secrecy also serves to protect clandestine armed groups against a significant centrifugal force within the organisation, such as those highlighted above between the military and political wings. Research about armed groups indicates that warriors may gain 'symbolic capital' from successful military campaigns, and thus potentially question the higher ranks or leaders of the political wing (Schlichte 2009). The charisma of the warrior often undermines those leaders who have intellectual or political backgrounds and this can even lead to outright competition within the group. It is difficult for single commanders to amass significant amounts of social capital under conditions of secrecy, for example, simply because BRN-Coordinate claims no external responsibility for its violent acts. Even within the organisation, the amassment of warrior charisma is limited simply due to the fact that fellow warriors remain unknown to most members. From the warrior's point of view, as they usually know only a limited numbers of fighters and vice versa, it is hard for them to build up vast informal patron-client networks that cross, or even contradict, formal relations within the group and which are otherwise very typical for organisations in Southeast Asia (Eisenstadt 1984).

According to Simmel (1992) the outstanding cohesion that results from this avoidance of conflict is also reflected in the thoroughness of centralisation, a mechanism that further affects the cohesion of clandestine groups. Secret societies demand blind obedience to their leaders, obedience that is not contradicted or undermined by the fact that leaders are unidentifiable by lower ranks. On the contrary, the concept of the "secret leader" exemplifies

"[...] the most extreme and abstract sublimation of dependence upon a center: the tension between dependent and leader reaches the highest

degree when the leader becomes invisible. All that remains then, is the pure fact of obedience – merciless, as it were, and unmodified by any personal nuances – out of which the superordinate as a subject has vanished.”

Wolff 1964: 372

For example, in reference to the founding of the original BRN, a BRN-Coordinate commander’s manual states that “on August 13, 1964, the tenth anniversary of the death of Haji Sulong²³, two Malay Patani youths came together to swear that they would unite for the revolution of gaining the independence and fraternity of Patani Malays, although both never knew the leaders of the revolutionary movement.” Interestingly, not only does BRN-Coordinate relate to and constitute a continuity of the original BRN, the insurgents seem to have no problem with not knowing the identity of their leaders, and most do not even ask who the leaders of their group are. Indeed, they seem to be attracted to the intangible power that, put into an imaginary focus, might be suspected to be everywhere.

2.9. Conclusion

BRN-Coordinate has proven to be astonishingly capable of learning and long-term planning, placing it as the leading insurgent organisation in Southern Thailand. Whereas other groups gave up their military struggle in the mid 1980s, BRN-Coordinate went through an incredible transformation, which had at least three dimensions. First, violence was redistributed towards part-time guerrilla-cum-terrorist fighters instead of full-time guerrillas hiding in the jungle. Second, the group introduced village-based mass indoctrination using a mixture of nationalism and jihadist thought that was becoming globally prominent at the time. Thirdly, BRN-Coordinate represents not a wholly new type of network insurgency, but rather, as a reaction to state suppression, introduces network elements to its hierarchical core that work autonomously on the local level. Together with its obsession with secrecy these elements increase the chances of survival in an environment marked by the selective force of violence. Latent relationships protect the group from external detection and infiltration, while, at the same time, the specific features of a hybrid organisation protect the group’s cohesion from any possible internally caused disintegration.

²³ Haji Sulong, also known as Haji Sulong bin Abdul Kadir Muhammad al-Fatani, was a Muslim intellectual and the Chairman of the Patani Islamic Council in the 1940s, who is considered by many insurgents as “the father of the Patani Struggle” (To’mina 1979 quoted in Surin 1982: 146). In 1947 he officially petitioned for self-rule and the recognition of Malay language by the Thai state.

3. Making insurgents: Recruitment, training and control

Popular discontent or a “crisis of legitimacy” are often assumed to stand in direct causal relation to the outbreak of insurgencies, regime changes or revolutionary action. Such an explanation is, however, problematic. Rebellious attitudes or preferences for a change in the status quo of a regime are unlikely to translate into collective action in a quasi-automatic fashion without the recruitment of insurgents who are willing to take the mortal risks of fighting an incumbent government. Every dissident who aims at generating collective action has to respond to the following question: what kind of appeal is most promising in getting people to join an organisation seeking a public good? Particularly in societies with low capacity for horizontal organisation, recruitment poses an immense challenge. While some armed groups solve this problem by relying on less committed members who are motivated by material gratification or are coerced to fight, groups like the IRA, the Vietcong, the LTTE or BRN-Coordinate, which work under the conditions of secrecy, must adopt a different recruitment strategy. Since clandestine groups are under a constant threat of defection and betrayal, they tend to draw on individuals that strongly identify with the organisation’s objectives.

Thus mobilization, military instruction and political indoctrination of members are key factors for the cohesion as well as success of armed groups (Weinberg 2005; Schlichte 2009). Drawing on Foucault’s (1995) concept of subjectivation, Schlichte (2009) argues that armed groups put their members in a double-edged process, socializing recruits into their symbols and practices. On the one hand, training turns recruits into mobilised members, who are familiar with the symbolic codes of BRN-Coordinate, helping them to communicate with other members, and making them willing to turn against the ruling order - using violent means and risking their lives. In other words, any cultural values and social institutions that inhibit the use of violence or suggest peaceful solutions to conflict must be overcome (Moore 1978; Elwert 2003). On the other hand, recruits are subjected to a new system of domination within the armed group, namely, a disciplinary apparatus that includes the use of force.

In exploring this process, I will first show the contexts in which BRN-Coordinate recruits new members. Then I will point out the “cultural repertoires” of agitation, which are used by recruiters, as well as the role of pre-existing social ties for gaining new members. Then, the chapter goes on to explain the mechanisms the group established in order to screen candidates and select “reliable individuals” from those who would potentially pose a threat to the group’s secrecy. In the last part of this chapter I will try to describe some selected parts of the BRN-Coordinate obligatory training process that recruits have to pass through after they have been sworn in as members. Within months, recruits are moulded into the milieu of a secret society, in which ideological indoctrination – centred on the charismatic idea of the holy war for an independent Islamic Patani state – transforms even less sustainable individual

motivations like hatred or excitement (see next chapter) into a shared sense of mission that can sustain BRN-Coordinate for years to come.

3.1. Recruitment as a collective action problem

Collective action is always the result of relatively autonomous actors who, drawing on given resources and abilities, try to solve a specific problem. In other words, collective action never arises simply from circumstances (Crozier & Friedberg 1976). It is not simply a result of “objective structures” such as exploitation and state repression - although sometimes the organisers of collective action create such images. Neither can humans, especially in clientelist societies, be considered *homo sociologicus*, who organise automatically. Indeed, many Malay communities share the same values and have a sense of local Patani patriotism pitted against the Thai colonizers, but these beliefs, no matter how strong, are not the single determinants of social action. Although ideologies like (Islam)-Nationalism are insufficient to coordinate collective action (Hardin 1995; Kalyvas 2006; Tilly 2003), insurgents can use their charismatic appeal for mobilisation. Equally, a lack of legitimacy hardly explains a sustained violent campaign. Przeworski (1991) even claims that explanations of regime change based on the legitimacy approach are either tautological or outright false. Political actors first have to create opportunities for collective action to be available.

In contrast to, for example, the peasant communities of pre-revolutionary France, Malay peasant communities are rather weakly organised. Contrary to popular views local Malays are characterized less by their spirit of communalism than by individualism. Malay villages are so-called “open” villages (Wolf 1957): there are not self-sufficient, but decidedly integrated into the world-market economy; mobility in and out of the village is high. The few anthropological data we have suggest that in Southern Thailand’s rural Malay localities the nuclear family is the basic social unit (Fraser 1966). In the Southern Philippines, for instance, political mobilisation of violent resistance is based not so much on ideology than on the social capital of the clan system (Kreuzer 2005). In Southern Thailand agricultural work involves little collective cooperation – households tend to work independently (Cornish 1997; Fraser 1966). As in other parts of Southeast Asia with only a limited capacity for horizontal self-organisation, social or political institutions in the villages remained rather unstable and sporadic (Embree 1969; Eisenstadt 1984). Modernisation, democratisation, decentralisation and the rise of Islamist movements have led to a significant rise in economic stratification and community conflict, while at the same time traditional conflict-resolving institutions and practices (e.g. the authority of village heads) are undermined. Under current structural conditions, these factors render the Malaysian countryside too weak for autochthonous, spontaneous revolution.²⁴ In other word, actors

²⁴ Historical and anthropological evidence from Southeast Asia seems to support this thesis. Conflicts between the state and its citizens were often avoided, though this does not imply that peasants are apolitical (Kerkvliet 2002).

that provide an organisational capacity for enduring violent action are needed.

While activist armed groups typically have a more or less clear vision of a better future with which they try to mobilise participation (in the case of Southern Thailand this is an independent Islamic state), the problem is that this promise is a collective benefit, i.e. all Malay Muslims in Southern Thailand will potentially benefit from it. Thus it is not clear how the promise of a “better future” motivates individuals to join the violent organisation, especially, when most farmers are economically relatively well off. The so-called “new wars” paradigm has argued that economic incentives have replaced ideological goals as the prime driving forces in collective violent action (see for example, Collier & Hoeffler 2004; Kaldor 2007). Yet, empirical evidence suggests a more complex picture (Crenshaw 2009). According to Weinstein (2007) the initial mobilisation of rebels is basically an organisational issue for armed group leaders who have to choose between strategies of recruitment, which fall into three distinct categories:

First, armed groups can recruit members through pure coercion, as Mao Zedong’s famous dictum stresses: “Political power grows out of the barrel of a gun”. Here we should distinguish between forced recruitment of members and coercion used merely to ensure compliance and cooperation among the local population. With regards to BRN-Coordinate, it seems that the latter is more widespread than the former, since the morale of coerced members is naturally low. For armed groups that have a professional standing guerrilla army this poses no problem. They can partly draw on coerced recruits, because superiors and fellow soldiers are constantly present and can therefore monitor forced recruits. The LRA or Renamo, an armed group in Mozambique, for example, make use of such practices (cf. Vinci 2005). Yet for clandestine groups, which base their whole strategy on secrecy, the mass use of coerced individuals is dysfunctional, since they must rely on highly disciplined individuals, who have an intrinsic motivation to hold a secret. Infiltration and defection to the government’s side are basic organisational challenges that, if unsolved, can easily bring clandestine organisations to an end.

However, there seem to be exceptions to this rule. As seen from the Vietcong, even underground organisations use a combination of propaganda, conviction and selective terror (Pike 1968). In one case an Ajak-committee member told me that he was forced

Instead, people move into spheres where the state has no interest or where the state has not fully institutionalized its control: e.g. frontier areas, black markets, neo-tribal communities (dawah, tabliq Jamat), and, in the case of the Malays, the use of Malay as a language that is not understood by most of the Thai government officials (Schiel 2007). When social interaction with officials is necessary, villagers often avoid conflict by, for example, “acting the fool” or simply avoiding encounters with officials. For instance, Malay village heads in Southern Thailand often undermine their “cooperation” with Thai security agencies, by claiming that they have no information about the insurgency. Whether their claims are actually true is doubtful. What this shows is that feelings of suppression and inequality lead to avoidance and retreat into a “hidden transcript”, or to forms of private religiosity more so than to rebellion. This view does not totally exclude the existence of lonely wolf insurgents, the self-ordered recruitment into virtual collectives of “holy fighters”, or scattered, uncoordinated violent resistance (Tilly 2003). I suppose, however, that these cases are the exception rather than the rule in Southern Thailand.

by existing Ajak-committee members and armed RKK-members to participate in the political wing in his village (insurgent interview, November 2, 2009): “They told me everybody in the village joined and that I couldn’t be an exception. If I didn’t join, they argued, I would pose an unacceptable security threat to them.” It was, however, not clear, if he intended to downplay his own motivation or if he was indeed forced. BRN-Coordinate can only force villagers to join if a majority of other villagers have already joined.

Second, from a rational choice perspective Olson (1971) has argued that individuals only join in costly collective actions in larger groups, when they receive “selective incentives”. Insurgent groups that have a certain amount of economic resources at their disposal can only offer their members a regular salary. Others offer short-term, material incentives by letting them plunder and loot their victims. However, such groups based on contracts tend to attract recruits with rather low commitment. Even though paid recruits might have higher motivation than coerced recruits, empirical evidence has shown that they rarely reach combat efficiency (Weinstein 2007) and they, again, pose a special risk for clandestine collective action: members who are likely to join the group for material benefits are likely to switch loyalties, in case that the state offers these benefits as well.

Other factors also suggest the limited “explanational value” in applying pure rational choice approaches to Southern Thailand. Initial data suggest that BRN-Coordinate usually does not gratify its ordinary members with any material resources (insurgent interviews, August-December 2009; intelligence officer interviews, July 2009). On the contrary, both members of the political wing (e.g. indoctrinators) and members of the military mostly pay for transport related to BRN-Coordinate operations themselves, often using their own vehicles. Youngsters, for instance, who constantly patrol their villages on foot or on motorcycle, usually receive neither food nor money for gas or food.²⁵

This is also the case during special missions. In one case I talked to a student of BRN-Coordinate who received an order to survey a hotel in a known tourist area in Phuket for a possible bomb attack. He insisted that he received no financial support for his travel expenses (insurgent interview, February 2, 2010). Besides, every recruit has to pass a time-costly training process that is not paid in any form (see below). In selected instances members (of the military wing) receive food and shelter, when they are, for example, on the run from state security forces or if they are deployed in areas other than their home areas for longer periods of time, thus restricting earning a livelihood. Occasionally, families of killed or wounded RKK-fighters receive financial support, though not as systematically as the families of suicide bombers in, for example, Palestine or elsewhere (insurgent interview, October 29, 2009).

²⁵ For more on individual motives for joining the insurgency, see chapter four.

These benefits can hardly be considered a justification for the risk they are willing to take in the line of military operations. Yet, as in any organisation we can find here the causes of misuse of resources among ordinary members. It is possible, for example, that local heads of economic sections personally misappropriate resources they generate from BRN-Coordinate's "membership fee" or business activities that are financed by the group, which cannot always be controlled from higher-ranking economic sections of the political wing. In one case two RKK-members extorted "special donations" from locals in the name of the organisation, but they acted without permission from superiors and kept the money for themselves. Both were consequently punished by superiors (insurgent military commander interview, March 7, 2010). Another argument of the rational choice theory refers to the exploitation of easily extractable natural resources, which is a key motivation in violent conflicts (Collier & Hoeffler 2004). Yet, directly capturable resources are relatively absent in Southern Thailand and thus, in contrast to the conflicts in Congo or Liberia, they are unlikely to be a decisive motivation for the insurgency.

What seems more interesting is to focus on the motivations for the insurgency at the leadership level. Here we should not dismiss the utility approach so hastily. At present, little is known of the conscious motives at BRN-Coordinate's leadership level (DPP) since they rarely communicate with the outside world. Have the wordsmiths of this elite rummaged through the toolkit of Islamo-nationalism to fit their needs, or does the pedigree of local ideology, coupled with the charisma of the jihad, exert a force on the leadership level, too? At the moment this question is a subject for further research. Although there is no intelligence yet that suggests that DPP-members receive monthly salaries, it is known that they receive travel expenses to attend leadership meetings taking place in, for example, Malaysia, Europe and Mecca.²⁶ Furthermore, they control the income from members taxes and other sources, but it is unclear, (yet not totally improbable) whether they use these resources for their personal interest. We know from the history of other armed groups that the longer an armed campaign lasts, the higher the chance that political motives will be replaced by economic motives and other non-material motives like power or prestige (Waldmann 1995).

While the rank-and-file usually invest personal resources, leaders (and occasionally others) may have improved their personal funds through the insurgency. If it is true, as current intelligence suggests, that the majority of DPP members and many of the cadres come from a religious elite (ustadz, religious school owners and teachers, Imam) this group would clearly profit, in the long-term, from an independent Islamic state. As religious gentry they would take over leadership positions in the bureaucracy of an Islamic state. And even forms of autonomy involve concrete elite interests such as the

²⁶ In late 2009 a DPP-meeting was held during the hajj-pilgrimage in Mecca, Saudi Arabia (intelligence officer interview, 27 December 2009).

power to ensure that resource and commercial developments are undertaken according to elite interests, or gaining increased funding from the central government for education, development projects, and welfare. To summarize, although systematic evidence for Southern Thailand is inevitably patchy, the “self-interest” approach is, given Southern Thailand’s specific conditions, only of limited value, when explaining why the majority of rank-and-file fighters join the organisation. This now poses the question: how can the successful recruitment of BRN-Coordinate then be accounted for?

A third strategy of recruitment that armed groups draw on is the mobilization of collective action through appealing to common identity (Weinstein 2007; Lichbach 1998). Such identity-based mobilisation has been successful for both gaining new members as well as serving as a “glue” for the internal cohesion of armed groups. Making use of identity-based recruitment strategies, including selection mechanisms, allows armed groups to engage members by stressing the benefits of patience and future orientation, in the absence of economic endowments: “Such high-commitment recruits, dedicated to the cause of the organisation and willing to make costly investments today with the promise of receiving rewards in the future, are investors. Low-commitment individuals are consumers, seeking short-term gains for participation.” (Weinstein 2007: 102). According to Weinstein we cannot underestimate the importance of the nature of how a group draws recruits, because it determines both the combat efficiency of the group and the support insurgents can gather from the local population. This is especially functional for secret organisations that are under a constant threat of betrayal. Individuals, who join an armed secret group in order to receive material benefits and thus identify less with the political aim of the group, are much less attracted by identity-based recruitment. Founding the Bolshevik party organisation in early twentieth century Russia, Lenin was well aware of the advantages and disadvantages of restricting an organisation to strongly motivated individuals: “In a country with a despotic government the more we restrict the membership of this organisations to persons who are engaged in revolution as a profession and who have been professionally trained ..., the more difficult will it be to catch the organisation.” (Lenin quoted in Coser 1974: 129).

Identity-based mobilisation has successfully been used in Colombia, El Salvador, Nepal and Northern Ireland. Ideological motives (“moral commitments”) often go hand in hand with psychological motives such as hatred and prestige (Graham 2007). This melange of motivations seems to be typical for Southern Thailand, too (for details see next chapter). Instead of offering short-term material benefits BRN-Coordinate draws on these emotional motives and refers to a “shared Patani Malay identity” based on a common language, understanding of history, and religion. Such an identity, even if just imagined, can link people within an existing similar frame of reference and eases the

mobilisation of collective action, because it reduces the cost of organising cooperation and develops a promise of a better life (Weinstein 2007). Both ideological and emotional elements became fused into the agitating scheme of the group, as shown by the construction of Patani nationalism, in which the memory of the violent Siamese occupation became a constitutive element, suggesting a duty of vengeance (Helbardt 2010).

3.2. Patterns of Recruitment

In practice, recruitment starts rather profanely. Recruiters have to look for candidates whom they approach in different contexts (insurgent recruiter interviews, September-October 2009). Like for other BRN-Coordinate operations, recruitment follows the principle of secrecy. Hence the recruiter will usually not introduce himself as a member of BRN-Coordinate. Instead he begins, for example, to talk about a general topic, drawing a connection to the agitation proper as one senior indoctrinator notes:

“In the case that I’m at a market and see a fellow Muslim who I want to recruit for us, I start a conversation on, for example, high prices of groceries and gas. I continue to propose that Malays pay taxes to the central government, but get nothing in return. Then I ask him, if he thinks so, too. If my counterpart agrees, I try to raise other points against the Thais.”

Afterwards, the recruiter might ask the candidate if he can visit him at home. As BRN-Coordinate has no material incentives to offer, much depends on the rhetorical skills of the recruiter to lure the candidate into further indoctrinating talks. This challenge is made easier, if the recruiter and the candidate stand within pre-existing social ties (see below). Sometimes recruiters and agitators are sent into a village mosque under the pretext of holding a prayer. The visits to the homes, mosques, schools or elsewhere usually take place several times, with each visit lasting for up to several hours, if the candidate agrees. During these visits the recruiter has to persuade the candidates to join their cause. For this purpose the recruiters have a certain “cultural repertoire” of agitation, centering on identity and emotion at their disposal:

First, they can use selected parts of BRN-Coordinate’s main identity narrative that is composed of historical, ethno-nationalist and religious elements as mobilisation levers (see Helbardt 2010). In each of the areas the recruiter tries to raise the consciousness of the candidate and to induce a duty to act upon them. How BRN-Coordinate endorses Islamo-Nationalism in order to create violent sentiments might be illustrated by the following quotation from a BRN-Coordinate manual for commanders:

“In 1932 Thai officials began spreading the Thai language in Schools and forbade Malay as an official language. This was the beginning of the destruction of our language and our religion that we inherited and we have to protect... revolution for independence on the basis of jihad is our highest duty... Patani is the heritage of our forefathers that we

have to re-erect.”

Just like Islam, Patani nationalism preaches “a meta-individualistic” time horizon: insurgent rhetoric celebrates the subordination of individual interest to the collective good of the jihad, as is shown in the oath that every member has to take (see below).

Depending on the special interests of the candidate, the recruiter will vary the different components, leaving out some and stressing others. As will be shown below, once the candidate becomes a member he has to study each of three components in a rather detailed fashion (see below). The specific impact of each component of this ideology is thus hard to assess. It seems that many of the rank-and-file typically understand the Islamo-nationalist narrative, not in abstract terms, but in terms of immediate social reform, such as a ban on alcohol, prostitution and revival of an Islamic way of life. For instance, one of my interviewees, a 28-year-old member of BRN-Coordinate’s military wing, commented on his motivation to enter the ranks of the group in 2005 using the following words:

“What I thought about before joining was the state of my society. When I was 14 years old, I began to realize that drugs were destroying my friends in my village. Even my relatives began to take drugs. The drugs changed the nature of all these people. It was like you took all the spirit out of them. Over the years I thought that the state of my community was unbearable. I had to do something. I blamed the Thais for the drugs. I thought this was a strategy of the Thai state to destroy us Malays. My recruiters told me that, we would change Patani society now, if we just fought the Thais. Under the sharia we will abolish all kinds of drugs.”

Second, the recruiter can draw on the so-called “kesedaran ummah”, which is Malay for “knowledge of the community”. While other forms of BRN-Coordinate knowledge are highly secret, the “12 Points” are supposed to be for “public use”. In other words, the 12 Points is the easy-to-remember formalisation of BRN-Coordinate’s exclusionary rhetoric of “othering”, which can be used both for the recruitment of individuals as well as for mass agitation of the general Malay population (insurgent interviews, September 2009). They are as follows:

1. The intrusion of ethnic heterogeneity, especially Buddhist government and the Thai influence, cause social ills such as apostasy, prostitution, corruption etc.;
2. Malays are the legitimate owners of the Patani land;
3. It is natural for humans to divide among (ethnic and religious) lines;
4. Malays are seen as an inferior ethnic group and are discriminated against by Thai people on the basis of their ethnicity and religion;
5. The Thai state blames the Malays for any violent incident or anything that goes wrong;
6. The Thai state exploits local resources that belong to Malays and gives them to ethnic Thais;

7. The Thai state wants to destroy Malay ethnicity and religion in order to transform Malays, especially future generations, into ethnic Thais;
8. Malays were independent in the past, now they are dominated by the Thais;
9. Thai policies towards Malays are unjust, fundamentally flawed and violent;
10. Thai officials clearly look down on Malays;
11. Thai power holders have a record of treating Malays in an unjust way;
12. Thai officials treat Buddhists like their real children, while they treat Malays like adopted children.

BRN-Coordinate members are supposed to disseminate this “knowledge” among all other local Malays, even those who won’t be invited to join the group as members. This is done orally and in different locations and contexts such as in teashops, during private conversations and, before and after prayers in local mosques. If an Ajak-committee is strong enough or has connections to a local village tadika, it tries to propagate kesedaran ummah among young pupils:

“It is our aim to anchor the division between Malays and Thais in our children’s hearts from an early age onwards. It’s the foundation for further work. If we teach them from an early age onwards, we can mobilise their support for our group later. Otherwise we loose our people to the Thais. We have to teach children to resist the Thais in every way, whenever possible.”

Similar to Vietcong fighters who were asked to engage in agitprop work (Pike 1968), members of BRN-Coordinate’s military wing had a duty to teach the kesedaran ummah at local tadika schools before 2004 – with or without the knowledge of the tadika owner. As mentioned above, later female members seem to have taken over this role. Pupils are given a separatist view on Patani history. In one BRN-Coordinate-related school teachers expressed their defiance against Thai rule by telling pupils that they declined raising a Thai flag in front of the school, even though their district officer had ordered the school to do so. Establishing control over communication in educational institutions, religious institutions, and coffee shops, as well as other means of persuasion is considered central to any success of any propaganda effort.

Often being redundant, the kesedaran ummah focuses on very similar questions: legitimacy, discrimination and destruction of local Malay culture by Thai officials, with the aim of inducing a feeling of injustice. The first, fourth, fifth and the sixth points especially illustrate that not only that Thai state officials are subject to the agitation, but that Buddhist civilians on the basis of their ethnicity are included as well. Bangkok’s strive for majoritarianism and homogenization has led to the suppression of local culture elsewhere (Chaiyan 1984). However, BRN-Coordinate’s recruiters construct an anti-system frame that portrays ethnic pluralism itself as exploitative and threatening. It seems that both sides, the Thai nation state as well as the Malay Muslim insurgents, at least in the case of BRN-Coordinate, are equally obsessed with the idea of cultural

uniformity. Again, it is up to the improvisation of recruiters to apply the propaganda points with the right examples and bring them up in the right situations. Skilled recruiters evaluate the interest and emotional reactions of the candidate and focus on discussing issues that stir up the most emotional responses.

Figure 3.1. Drawings by tadika pupils (Banangsata District, Yala Province)

Source: 4th Army Area

Third, BRN-Coordinate makes use of emotions like hatred and pride. When I asked a 26-year-old female member of BRN-Coordinate about when and why she joined BRN-Coordinate, she described the siege of the Kru Se mosque on April 28, 2004 in her own words: “After the Thai soldiers had violently entered the mosque, everybody surrendered and laid down their weapons. But then Thai soldiers ordered the Malays to kneel down in the mosque. Then they shot every single one of them in the head and killed them” (female insurgent interview, November 2, 2009). I could feel how emotionally involved she was as she began to cry and, at the same time, had an expression of anger in her eyes. Later I learned that the woman had lost her boyfriend in the described incident. Although the young woman did not know the recruiter before she was approached, the recruiter obviously studied the background of her candidate. The recruiter, also a female, knew that the woman lost her boyfriend at the hands of the Thais and offered her “a chance for revenge”. Recruiters often deliberately overestimate the number of deaths in order to increase people’s hatred against the Thai state. An insurgent recruiter told me that he told his recruits that the Thai officials massacred more than 1000 Malays in Tak Bai and that this number was later covered up by Thai officials, even though he was aware that in fact much fewer people were killed in the event. Furthermore, he used video footage of the event to further foster the emotions of the young men he wanted to mobilise.

These examples illustrate that we should not underestimate the role of hatred as a form of motivation for joining violent groups (Schlee 2002). Internal group solidarity can go

hand in hand with resentment and feelings of hatred towards outsiders (Sen 2006), especially if a group does not feel recognized. Yet hatred based on ethnicity or religious affiliation is not rooted in primordial sentiment. Such a metaphorical thesis based on a deeply rooted “Patani nationalism/identity” has its appeal, not the least, because it is hard to disprove and fits into the paradigm of the cultural turn. However, hatred based on ethnic affiliation is nothing primordial, but rather an “outcome of specific constructions of conflict” (Elwert 2004: 2542). It is a social construct that has to be learned within social networks and which can be manipulated by political actors.

The artisans of terror are well aware of the emotional energy that these “techniques of hatred” (Silva 2002) can generate and hence use different mechanisms to foster and channel them: stereotyping the Thai “other” as infidels and brutal colonizers, distorting historical events, the employment of rumour mills (see below) and last but not least acts of provocation that lure Thai officials into confrontational situations in which they use violence against Malay civilians (Tak Bai) or symbolic sites (Kru Se). The brutality, the site of violence and the lack of law-enforcement in the aftermath of the latter two events further reiterated the image of the Thais as ruthless colonizers. The fallout of the events was that many young men (and probably also women) swelled the ranks of BRN-Coordinate. New recruits came in the form of alienated and revengeful Malays, as one BRN-Coordinate indoctrinator commented: “We almost didn’t have to convince them (new recruits, S.H.). They simply joined us and couldn’t wait to get a gun in their hand to shoot some Thai pigs.”

Hatred against “the other”, that serves to activate Malays individually and as a collective, can only exert a mobilising function if the content of the hatred corresponds to common ideas. It must appeal to communal memories or personal experiences, otherwise the propaganda remains without significance for a larger part of the population. A case in point is the RKK-fighter mentioned above whose personal experience of drug addiction fitted into the frame of the *kesedaran ummah* (“Thais use drugs to destroy us”). All insurgents I interviewed had heard about past Thai atrocities against Malays – either from relatives, teachers, Imams, internet homepages or history books. On the collective level, the memories of many Malay communities seem to be full of deep injustices of Thai officials (Bin Mohamad 2007). Partly, these memories are connected to events experienced and remembered at the local level, and also partly from region-wide memories of events such as the killing of Haji Sulong. It has been suggested elsewhere that at least for the majority of people, the emotional power of such memories will not last over generations. Herein lies the importance of events in Tak Bai and Kru Se: not only do they seem to suggest that the violence of Malays against state officials is a reactive and not proactive form of violence- a form of “authentic” self-defence understandable to the outside world – but rather, that both hostile events also bolstered hatred.

To put it differently, insurgent recruiters and indoctrinators often don't need to do a remarkable job of distorting the religious and historical understanding of their recruits. With the Islamo-nationalism of Patani partly rooted in the collective memory of the Siamese invasion, recruits do not need to leave the "epistemological comforts of their homes" in order to participate in the insurgency, although they still have to be mobilised and organised.

3.2.1. Recruitment inside the educational system

Mass-based separatist organisation just like the Moro National Liberation Front (MNLF) and the Moro Islamic Liberation Front (MILF) in the Southern Philippines has been somewhat lacking for Malay separatism in Southern Thailand. Because effective government policy and internal rivalries have successfully hindered Southern Thai resistance from becoming institutionalized, religious schools, which remain largely unmonitored by Thai government officials, have taken on the role of reproducing the ideas of separatism necessary to strengthen the resistance (Liow 2006). Nevertheless, more formalized militant separatism like that of BRN-Coordinate coupled with the ideological apparatus of the religious schools is a good combination that successfully strengthens the overall aim of the movement.

As young men are a key resource for any armed group, recruitment often takes place within schools. It seems that most young recruits, particularly members of the military wing, are recruited through the Pondok and Private Islamic Schools in Southern Thailand that were infiltrated by BRN-Coordinate (which does not, of course, mean that Islamic schooling is a breeding ground for militarism per se). Indeed in only a rather limited number of cases, entire schools were infiltrated and fully instrumentalized by BRN-Coordinate. These schools include, for example, Thammawitaya in Yala's Muang district, Islamburapah in Narathiwat, Pondokjihad in Pattani's Yaring district (Lt. General & intelligence officers interviews July-August 2009). In these schools, owned by higher-ranking BRN-Coordinate members, sometimes whole classes of male students were recruited and trained. When both teachers as well as a majority of fellow students get involved in insurgent activities, immense pressure is put on the others to follow. A student that was recruited at Thammawitaya School in 2003 told me that he "had to" join BRN-Coordinate against his will, because all of his male classmates joined the organisation: "When I was sceptical, the others looked at me strangely and asked me accusingly, if I had not felt loyalty to the Patani people."

In most schools, however, it is rather single teachers who recruit for BRN-Coordinate, often without the knowledge of the school owners or directors. Especially in these schools teachers must carefully identify possible candidates. A common method involves talking about the violent invasion of the Islamic Sultanate of Patani by the infidel Siamese in the context of the regular history curriculum. After doing this several times they are able to identify students who demonstrate a special interest (e.g. by

asking where they could read more about Patani history) or show other emotional reactions to the lecture. The teacher might then invite the student to a private talk after the class in order to further confirm the commitment of the students or directly invite him to join. In schools where BRN-Coordinate has no teachers who recruit students or where the group has to protect its teachers, elder students who are already members indoctrinate and recruit their fellow students. A third channel of recruitment combines both schools and local level Ajak-committees in order to protect the schools or individual teachers. Screening and selection is done at the school while the actual recruitment, operated by the Ajak-committee, takes place close to the home of the student.

In addition to schools, BRN-Coordinate has also infiltrated university campuses, especially at Rajaphat Yala, Prince of Songkhla University (both Pattani and Hat Yai Campus). However BRN-Coordinate student committees are also active in other universities in Southern Thailand (e.g. Rajaphat Songkhla, Thaksin Univeristy in Hat Yai) - even in Bangkok and Chiang Mai. Their tasks comprise keeping the student members of the organisation who were already recruited in the schools and villages, as well as recruiting new members. At least in Yala and Pattani student committees have also been involved in military operations. For the first task, senior BRN-Coordinate students receive lists of freshmen BRN-Coordinate students who will enter the universities. The senior members will then, for instance, organise camps or private talks to uphold the morale of the young members and possibly engage them in missions. In order to remain undetected, the senior students use official university activities and student clubs as a cover for their activities and communication. According to a former leading student insurgent, BRN-Coordinate had infiltrated, for example, the Thai Muslim Student Association before 2004.

Another example from around 2003/4 illustrates one of the recruitment techniques of BRN-Coordinate among female students: an Islamic university club (chomrom) at the Prince of Songkhla University (Pattani Campus) invited a handful of selected female Malay Muslim students to a so-called Islamic camp, under the pretext of studying the Koran and its meaning for a righteous Islamic woman's lifestyle. However, once the students arrived at the camp, which was organised at a remote site in Pattani, the students not only recited and interpreted the Koran, but were subjected to intense physical conditioning by senior students: they had to run and do gymnastics until late at night and were forced to get up exceptionally early in the morning in order to cook for themselves. The organising students gave instructions in a military-like fashion. Overwhelmed by fatigue on the second day the first students began to complain about the camp. At this point of time the senior student began their indoctrination: "Is that all you can endure? Our sisters in Palestine have to bear much more than this...". Only then did it become clear to the invited junior students that they were selected to join an

insurgent recruitment camp.

Recruiting university students has at least two effects. On the one hand, BRN-Coordinate can foster the future elites of the group. Thai Intelligence suggests that BRN-Coordinate sends some of its most promising students to, for example, Ramkhamhaeng University to study political science in order to use them as future political administrators for an independent Patani state. These students are well linked in Bangkok and highly skilled in administrative affairs, national Thai as well as international politics. After their return they occupy commanding positions within the political and armed wings of BRN-Coordinate. This elite can be used to infiltrate local government organisations (such as the district and provincial administrative organisations, district offices etc.) or local branches of state companies such as the Electricity Generating Authority of Thailand (EGAT). On the other hand, many students return to the local communities as teachers and thus guarantee the mobilisation of the next generation of young fighters. For instance, a former senior student recruiter at the Prince of Songkhla University (Pattani Campus) set up his own Private Islamic School, after finishing his studies.

3.2.2. Recruitment outside the educational system

While it is highly probable that the majority of male youngsters recruited through the school system were channelled into the military wing, recruitment outside the school system was also necessary to establish BRN-Coordinate's political wing and its presence at the village level. In order to build up the Ajak-system since the mid 1990s, qualified members were given areas of responsibility in which they had to find suitable locals who could staff the Ajak-committees in the villages. In Pattani and Narathiwat, for example, these "pioneers" had to coordinate this task for two districts.

Social movement research has stressed the mobilizing role of the combination of a mobilizing organisation coupled with pre-existing social ties (McAdam et al. 1997). Mobilizing organisations depended on the latter, because pre-existing community ties lower mobilisation costs and imply trust into the organisation, which is otherwise unknown to the candidates. Yet, the local mobilizing power that insurgents draw from varies across time and space. It is harder to say "no", if friends, fellow students, neighbours, teachers, relatives, colleagues or the Imam ask an individual to participate, because one is afraid to lose respect, reputation and possible cooperation. While candidates are not aware of how the organisation looks on the inside, the person who invites them to join invokes confidence in the new members, because they are familiar with him or her.

In this sense, the pioneers looked for so-called "natural leaders" (phunam thammachat in Thai) in Malay villages, such as Imam, ustadz and or persons with special skills that could be of use to the group (e.g. economic knowledge). Imams are the most suitable

candidates for BRN-Coordinate, because typically they demand religious as well as personal authority over the population and know the village population very well - these are both important factors for mass indoctrination and recruitment. Besides, having influence over the local mosque as a symbolic space in the middle of the village, again, invokes the idea of a religiously sanctified group. Village heads, although they are also approached in some cases, are less apt, because their constant contact to the state is a significant risk to the hyper-secrecy of BRN-Coordinate. When finding candidates for the Ajak-committees, recruiters usually draw on personal, family, educational or other networks. In addition to these figures of authority, BRN-Coordinate's recruitment efforts then focus on the young men in the villages, as they are a most crucial resource for the group. Although BRN-Coordinate members are not keen to talk about this, reports from some villages suggest that, if an Imam was not willing to join, youngsters in his own village would threaten him to enforce cooperation.

Initially, the recruiter approaches the Imam or village head alone and engages them in innocuous talks. If the candidates seem sympathetic to the secessionist cause, the recruiter will continue to visit them several times (e.g. at home) thereby indoctrinating them. In some cases, the indoctrinator brings a local politician, sub-district head or other locally known person who is a member of BRN-Coordinate to the home of the candidate in order to show him that other local figures of influence are already members of the group, inducing the image of a wide-ranging membership network. Ideally, the Imam and village head are asked to bring around three or more other people from their village that might be willing to "work for the movement". These teams of people are then indoctrinated collectively and, if considered willing and suitable to join the group, they are invited to become members of BRN-Coordinate. After these rudimentary Ajak-committees are established, higher-ranking members visit the village regularly, e.g. once a week, and teach basic tasks to the committee members. The members then have to run the committee by themselves and take responsibility for recruiting further villagers into the group. For security reasons, the committees are apparently restricted to a maximum of twelve committee members in one village, while other villagers may join as ordinary members of the organisation.²⁷

In instances where the recruiter has no personal link to a village, he might turn to BRN-Coordinate student members who were recruited through the schools system and who live in the target village. The student member would then arrange, for example, a meeting between the recruiter and the local village Imam or another elder village member who could be recruited. Once an Ajak-committee is recruited into BRN-

²⁷ Participation can encompass multiple roles beyond the membership-non-membership distinction. At least two of my informants were not members of the group, but took active roles in supporting personal friends who were actually BRN-Coordinate members. My informant did not want to join directly, because he was aware that it was hard to leave the group once he had entered it. Instead he preferred to exercise some logistical functions for BRN-Coordinate. He claimed to have bought five M-16 machine guns and in another case he bought solar battery chargers for mobile phones used by insurgents who had fled into the mountains.

Coordinate, it can help the coordinator to find possible recruits in neighbouring villages or other villages with which committee members have personal networks. Therefore recruitment accelerates over time. Efficient Ajak-committees usually recruit youngsters in the village who can then be channelled into the military wing.

In one village in Narathiwat's Rueso district the Ajak-committee seemed to be a family affair, as the Ajak-committee chief mainly recruited other committee members among his own relatives. His wife was established as the head of the Ajak women section. Another cousin of the Ajak-committee chief was recruited and trained as a member of the military wing. In the attempt to eliminate competing power structures, the village head was shot dead and never replaced. As a consequence, BRN-Coordinate had no difficulties penetrating the village and conducted propaganda sessions openly at the mosque. However, usually before BRN-Coordinate can openly propagandize in mosques or teashops (Pathan & Liow 2010), it must be certain that a majority of villagers are on their side. In some selected cases even complete villages entered the BRN-Coordinate.

It seems that broader processes of social change eased recruitment on the village level. Malay villages, which already comprised of fragmented and loosely structured communities (Fraser 1966), apparently continued to lose their capability to control. Disobedience among youngsters can lead to very ambivalent developments within the one community. A Malay villager opposed the militancy points out:

“Many parents and grandparents even fear their sons. In my village more than half of the teenagers regularly take drugs. There is a clique of around 20-25 youngsters. They disappear with their motorcycle gangs for days, they steal money for new drugs from their parents, some even have threatened them in order to get money. Another clique of youngsters go in a very different direction. Maybe ten teenagers or so joined the militant movements. Some parents prefer their kids to join the insurgents more than to be drug addict, because the movement teaches them discipline and to respect religion. But in my view both situations are equally worrying. And the authorities do nothing about it. The district office does nothing except put pressure on me to solve all problems. How can I do this? In the past I could solve such issues by myself. The young men respected my word, but presently the teenagers show no respect.”

When I asked the village head what role politicians could play in solving this problem, another Malay village head, who had expressed a similar worrying picture of local society, laughingly replied: “The politicians? They come here for elections, give us money for the votes and come back during the next elections. They don't dare to fight no-one, not the militants nor the drug dealers.”

In sum, there is still no database that would allow for evaluating the success of the different recruitment channels. An insurgent on the provincial level suggested that from

the mid-1990s until the beginning of the 21st century, most recruits came from within the schools, because BRN-Coordinate controlled a number of schools in the three provinces, but it had not yet established the Ajak-committees. Around the years 2001 or 2002 in his area of responsibility alone, the Ajak-committees spread so rapidly that they generated more new members than the schools.

3.3. Screening and selection of recruits

Above, I talked about “suitable” candidates. From the point of view of BRN-Coordinate leadership it is clear that the individuals joining the group must fulfil certain conditions. In order to protect itself from low-commitment individuals who might pose a risk to the group’s secrecy and its discipline, clandestine organisations must screen and select candidates. With regard to recruitment, group leaders face an information problem: since a look into the candidate’s mind is impossible, leaders cannot be sure about the real motivation of individuals (Weinstein 2007). Identity-focused mobilisation is only BRN-Coordinate’s first recruiting mechanism that serves to identify and separate high-commitment members from low-commitment individuals.

A second mechanism to identify potential members is to gather background information on them from people close to the candidate’s environment. Thus screening of candidates through family, friendship, school or village networks could ensure secrecy and protection against hostile penetration. At the university level, for example, fellow students who are also BRN-Coordinate members can give information on the reliability and trustworthiness of a candidate. In particular the ability to keep information secret is crucial. Hence candidates, who are talkative or pretentiously display “their connections” or networks, a typical feature of societies ridden with patron-client relationships, are inappropriate for membership. The candidate should not have loyalties to the Thai state, either ideologically or, for example, because he (or she) is married to a Thai official. Usually these individuals will only be invited to the group after passing a security check; this also counts for Malay teachers at Thai government schools. As a rule, soldiers and policemen cannot become members, which does not exclude, however, that they can be recruited as informants for the group. In selected cases, when candidates are known and trusted by established BRN-Coordinate members, they can be immediately be sworn in as members without a background check.

A last mechanism used by BRN-Coordinate to screen and select candidates is the so-called “costly induction” (Weinstein 2007). Recruits do not get a gun in their hands immediately, but have to pass a time-costly training phase that can take up to two years. In other words, the candidates have to make a private investment in the organisation before they are deployed, indicating their patience and future orientation. Time is a key resource for any social movement. Therefore rubber planters and students are more suitable than, for example, entrepreneurs.

The success of high-commitment recruitment of sub-leadership members is reflected in the socio-economic profile of fighters. University-education is one indicator of the high-commitment recruitment strategies (Weinstein 2007). Groups that draw on selective incentives or coercion to recruit tend to have less educated members than groups that build on conviction. For instance, let's take the example of Renamo, an armed group in Mozambique that used both material benefits and coerced young men to join the organisation. Only around one percent of its fighters had a university education. In contrast, a sample of BRN-Coordinate insurgents showed that 13% were enrolled in or even had a degree from tertiary educational institutions (see next chapter). Moreover, "crooks" do not rank prominently within the rank-and-file of BRN-Coordinate and there is not yet substantial evidence to assume that BRN-Coordinate makes systematic use of extortion, bank robbery etc., which is typical for low-commitment groups. This also stands in contrast to past insurgent organisations in Southern Thailand, when, according to a former PULO guerrilla, leaders also recruited the staff of their military wings from among (former) criminals or people linked otherwise to the illegal economy (interview former PULO military commander, Yala, September 9, 2009).

3.4. Entering the organisation: the vow of fidelity

Before selected candidates join the organisation, BRN-Coordinate mandates that they have to pass an oath-taking initiation ritual. As for other rituals, this vow of fidelity (supoh in local Malay) is staged according to certain rules. It demarcates not only the border between membership and non-membership but draws on religious elements in order to convey the aura of religious sanctification of the organisation.

This begins with the timing of the supoh, since, as far as it is known, the ceremony is usually held on a Friday, the day of collective worship in Islam. Another element of the ceremony that invokes its sanctification is the location. Both mosques and prayer rooms in schools can serve as locations, yet in one case almost the whole Malay village took the oath at a waterfall nearby the village. At least one BRN-Coordinate member attends as a "master of ceremony", while the oath itself can be taken by individuals or whole groups (e.g. class of students, Ajak-committee). A 27-years old RKK-member who was indoctrinated and invited to join by senior students at his Private Islamic School, described the invitation to the oath:

"The senior students who indoctrinated us asked, if we were ready for the next step. Except two of my classmates, everybody in our class agreed. The(y) (senior students; S.H.) told us to come to the school's prayer on Friday. Each of us was given a specific time to enter the prayer room, so that we wouldn't attract attention."

In another case a 41-year old Ajak-chief reported that his whole Ajak-team took the oath together at the local village mosque: "After I found four friends in my village who were willing to join, we were asked to come to our mosque and there a person was

waiting who asked us to sit down and take the oath together.” Continuing his account of the oath ceremony, the RKK-fighters explained: “When everybody was in the prayer room, the senior students asked us to form a circle and kneel down. Then they put the holy Koran in the middle on which we all put our hands and the seniors spoke the oath, which we had to recite. After this, we were told that we would be contacted for further training. We left the prayer room, just as we entered, one by one. I felt very excited, but while other guys in my group were obviously proud, I had thoughts whether my decision to join was right and what implications the oath would have for me. Actually, I wanted to tell my parents or somebody else, but I knew I couldn’t.”

In personal interviews as well as interrogation records the exact wording of the oath varies. In one person’s recorded version the oath consists of three passages that might be translated into English as follows: 1) “I swear that I will act according to the rules of Islam”; 2) “I swear that I will not reveal the secret to outsiders”; 3) “I swear that I will sacrifice everything to Allah”. Each passage had to be repeated by recruits three times. At the end he recites the common formal declaration of faith “Allah Akbar” (“God is the Greatest”). Another insurgent recalls his oath in the following words: “In the name of Allah I swear to sacrifice everything to free my nation and religion from the rule of the Thai state. I will not give away the secret even if it costs my life. I will listen to my leaders and act according to their orders. I will fight the jihad according to the principles of Allah in order to the righteous.”

There are some known cases in which recruits decline to swear with their hand on the Koran, for some reason or another. Instead they put their hand on a gun while repeating the usual oath, which, as far as is known so far, still contains the usual religious codicil. In at least one case a RKK-fighter refused to take the oath, because he wanted to be able to leave the organisation if necessary. In his view taking the oath and swearing absolute loyalty to the organisation in front of Allah would not allow him to exit BRN-Coordinate afterwards. However, he was accepted and even received a high rank within the armed wing, probably because of his military skills and the fact the he was married to the daughter of senior BRN-Coordinate member.

While such a denial of the supoh seems to be an exception, it illustrates the binding effect that the ritual has for some members. Taken together with the disciplinary code that demands members sacrifice both material possessions as well as their life to the group (see below), the vow of fidelity illustrates that BRN-Coordinate attempts to confine the whole individual into its structures. The group demands a total change of lifestyle in which body and mind are subjected to the regime of secrecy. In this sense, the oath being staged as a religious ritual serves as an expression, fixing and reinforcing the shared values of the secret community. Not only is giving away the group secret to the enemy conceptualized as an infringement of the oath and thus of the religious duty (swearing on the Koran invokes a divine witness), but it is also clear for members that

major betrayal is sanctioned with a death sentence (see below). In this sense, fighters do not seek fame or reputation from fellow Malays (cf. Askew 2009a). Rather, not divulging anything about the organisation and one's task in it is a sign of devotion to God who observes their deeds. Secrecy and religiosity are thus interlinked.

3.5. Obligatory training

An organisation must always ensure that the loyalty of its members overrides competing loyalties from the wider social structure. Threats against BRN-Coordinate come from various sources. First and foremost, the organisation must protect its members against the threat of defection to the government. On a lower level the organisation must compete with other loyalties for the members' limited time resources, and also protect them against any competing views from fellow Malays who oppose the use of violence. In this sense armed groups can be referred to as "greedy institutions" (Coser 1973) who face a classical "principal-agent problem". A BRN-Coordinate instructor remarked on the aim of the training:

“Our task is to build unselfish Islamic revolutionaries in every village who are willing to give up their possessions and their life to the independent state of Patani. Yet to other villagers it must all be secret. We must protect them against the world outside the group and outside God. To other people our revolutionaries shall only appear as role models for a good Muslim. Their main task is only known to God.”

In addition to building a motivated fighter, the main function of the training is to strengthen the group's cohesion. Every organisation has to build a set of formal common expectations and goals for their members (Luhmann 1999: 240). Social movement-based organisations have the advantage that they can easily build up strong "We-group" identification among its members. For this purpose the group has formalized a training programme that is obligatory to new (mostly male) recruits. Patchy evidence suggests that each of them has to pass a total of five levels.²⁸ In addition to some physical conditioning and basic military training, the five levels embrace mostly ideological instruction, which provides for the common sense of mission among the insurgents. Later those members, who are chosen to join the group's armed wing, receive special military training. Moving through the different levels is a slow process that can take up to more than a year, depending on the time available for the trainers and recruits. Sometimes a single level takes more than a month. The indoctrinator visits his recruits once or twice a week, as one trainer stressed:

“It is important not to put the recruits under too much pressure or to take too much of their time, because we don't pay them and they still have to go to school or work. If I come to a recruit and see that he is

²⁸ In an earlier paper I started to trace elements of the training process that every member has to pass through (Helbardt 2010). During the last few months data on the training process have emerged that allow for a more detailed picture of the process, although there is, of course, still space for error.

busy, I just ask how he is and to come again next week. If we force them too early, it does not work.”

When training takes place in the context of schools, each candidate may pass through the levels faster. Theoretically, during the first few levels the recruit can leave the process at any time. However, during my interviews I only learned of one individual who took the oath and left the group during training. Due to the tight screening and group pressure the number of people who ‘back out’ before the outbreak of violence is relatively low. Generally, for security reasons, the passing on of knowledge within BRN-Coordinate is on a “need-to-know” basis. Members are allowed to know only as much as is necessary to bind them to the group and sufficiently fulfil their function, because strategic and tactical knowledge that falls into the hands of the enemy threatens the combat efficiency of the group. Therefore, recruits are also asked not to write down the lessons they learned. Moreover, recruits are not supposed to know the real identity of their instructors or superiors. For everything that recruits do, the guiding principle is that they shall never furnish the outsider with knowledge about the organisation, not even their closest relatives and friends. This applies in both everyday life as well as emergency situations. If they run into a comrade on the street, they are not supposed to give the public any hint at their “special connection” and in case, when they are captured they shall never give in to the interrogation. Simply put, a common expectation is established in the group: recruits learn that not only the success of the group, but their personal survival depends on the ability of every individual to keep the secret. When trust becomes a matter of life and death, the less that is spoken, the better for all.

3.6. Ideology

On the first level, members are introduced that the three basic ideological elements of the group that are used also partly for agitating recruits: 1) history and the constitution of the Patani Nation; 2) the construction of ethnic differences, or better, the construction of local Malay identity; 3) religion:

3.6.1. Patani history

History is one of the key elements that constitute and legitimize nationalism. BRN-Coordinate begins its indoctrination of members with history, yet indoctrinators do not lecture on Patani history in great detail (except if the new member wants to). Instead, they all draw on existing historical knowledge and use this to trigger historical awareness of nationalistic difference. The example of Ismail, a member of the political wing who indoctrinated and then trained indoctrinators for almost 10 years, illustrates the use of the historical narrative. As an introduction Ismail confronts recruits with a seemingly simple question: “How was Patani in the past?” According to Ismail most Patani Malays, even those with little education, could answer this question. They would respond that Patani was once an Islamic state (i.e. a country that was based on Islamic

principles). After listening to his recruits views on Patani history, Ismail would stress how well known Patani's Islamic scholarship was in the Islamic world and that trade with the Arab region made Patani one of the most prosperous countries in the region. Indoctrinators would then emphasize that Patani Malays were highly devout, strictly following Islamic principles in everyday life, because state and society (in contrast to the present-day) would allow them to do so.

In this narrative, non-Malay aspects of Patani history such as pre-Islamic Malay culture or the multiethnic nature of Patani as a former international trading place that included Indians, Europeans, Chinese, Siamese etc. are omitted with intention. So is the pre-Islamic history. This selective historical narrative begins with the Islamisation of Patani in the early, or mid 15th century (Syukri 1985; Gilquin 2005). BRN-Coordinate's historical narrative also stresses the painful subversion of Patani by Siamese colonisation. Siamese colonisation is remembered not only as an end to national sovereignty and a truly Islamic way of life, but also as a painful humiliation of the "Malay body". To reinforce their message indoctrinators tell youngsters how their great-grandmothers were raped by Siamese soldiers and how their great-grandfathers were tortured and killed or kidnapped. An example that is regularly raised in this context is that Patani Malays were captured at the beginning of the 20th century and had to dig Bangkok's Saensaep canal with their bare hands. BRN-Coordinate's best indoctrinators are able to describe these events in such graphic language that some of the candidates begin to cry.

In other words, in the quasi-colonial cognition of history, violence becomes constitutive of the Patani nation in a retrograde way. Similar to almost all the European nationalist movements which referred to phases of foreign rule, real and alleged historical violence by aliens is a structuring element of the present-day cognitive structure. Interestingly, it is not common for BRN-Coordinate recruiters to make explicit reference to the heroic figures who defended Patani against the Thai invaders, although locally such a memory may play a role, as Bin Mohamad (2007) stressed in his research.

Following the question of "how Patani was in the past", Ismail might ask the candidate: "What is Patani in the present? Is it how it was in the past?" Again, the main implication of this question is a consciousness of the fact that Patani, now ruled by the unbelieving Siamese, has lost its sovereignty. Moreover, the present-day consequences of this foreign rule are stressed, such as economic exploitation, political corruption and moral decay, which imply probably the most important of all consequences of foreign rule: the destruction of the Islamic way of life and apostasy. As a third and conclusive step in the historical narrative, Ismail raises the question of how Patani should be in the future, in order to link the historic narrative with the mobilisation of action. He finishes his indoctrination with an appeal: "Be with us! We have to fight to regain control over our history!" Then Ismail leaves the candidate alone for a week before continuing the

indoctrination.

3.6.2. Constructing Patani nationalism

The subject of the second step of indoctrination is the raising of a Patani Malay national consciousness. Again recruiters (are supposed to) refrain from long scientific recourses to the ethnography of Malays, which would only bore the new members. Instead they raise, for example, two seemingly simple questions: first, “What is Malay?” and, second, “What is Siamese?” To ask these questions Ismail, if possible, meets his recruits in a place where, for example, there are both Thai Buddhists and Malays. They sit down drinking coffee and Ismail simply asks his candidate to compare Malays and Buddhists on the streets. He poses questions such as “Do they wear the same cloths as we do?”, “Do they speak the same language as we do?”, “Are they relatives?”, “Do they have the same customs?” These rather rhetorical inquiries serve two purposes: first, they are intended to make members conscious of their own ethnic identity by stigmatizing and stressing cultural differences of other groups. Such framing of conflicts in “we vs. them” terms is referred to in social anthropology as “othering” (Ashcroft et al. 2007).

Secondly, the inquiries not only function to discredit practices of inter-ethnic coexistence, but they are also related to an opportunity, or better, a duty to action. Constructing the adversary as an enemy is used in order to force people to choose sides. For this purpose Ismail and other BRN-Coordinate recruiters continue to associate all present negative social phenomena in the region with the rule of ethnic Thais. Prostitution, drug addiction, corruption, alcohol, crime or whatever else at hand are externalized and alleged to be part of the alien Thai culture. In this context Buddhism, a key constituent of the Thai nationalism, is often said to be a weak, or inferior religion, not only because it does not recognize Allah, but also because it does not demand a strictly devout lifestyle from its lay members – a lifestyle that is, together with the corresponding political order, central to the constructions of Muslim modernity.

However, the stigmatisation of the Thai Nation as morally corrupt and weak is not so much about misrepresenting the essence of Buddhism, but rather “that it operates as representations usually do, for a purpose, according to a tendency, in a specific historical, intellectual, and even economic setting” (Said). The master narrative of Thai nationalism claims that the ethnic Thais legitimately rule Thailand, because of their ability to lead the nation into civilized modernity without being colonized. For the 1904 Louisiana Purchase Exposition in St. Louis, for example, the Siamese government published a catalogue which speaks of different “sub-divisions” to the “great Thai race” - the “Shan”, “Laos” and the “Lu” – but it was the Siamese, who “alone have assimilated Western civilisation and maintained an independent position among the nations of the world.” (Streckfuss 1993: 143). Insurgents try to reverse this stigmatisation of ethnic minorities in Thailand and the power differentials associated with them by pointing out the apostatic effects of ethnic Thai rule. To illustrate his

narrative, Ismail then takes his candidate on a motorcycle ride through Pattani city and shows him karaoke bars, pubs and other places that are considered detested symbols of moral decay and corruption. After that he would ask the candidate if these places and practices are compatible with local Malay culture or not and whether it was the Malays or the Thais, who brought these influences to the Malay land. Ismail summarized the purpose of the indoctrination as follows: “It is all about showing that this place is ours, while the home of the Siamese, the oppressors, is somewhere else. And it is better for us to keep that separated.”

3.6.3. Jihad or no jihad: the role of Islam

The role of Islam in the conflict in Southern Thailand is a widely discussed issue, especially the question of how far the insurgency is fuelled by (international) Islamist or (local) nationalist ideologies. However, such an either-or perspective might not be helpful. As is shown here, both elements can indeed go together. If we want to understand the religious appeal of BRN-Coordinate, as with most violent Islamist groups, we should not ask for the theological content of its teaching or the logic of the arguments, because according to Ismail, religion for BRN-Coordinate is about motivating people to act. At the core of BRN-Coordinate’s religious narrative is the idea of the holy Islamic war or jihad. Indoctrinators tell the new members that the fight to free Patani from Thai rule is a jihad as outlined in the Koran, because the Thais invaded Muslim land and persecute Muslims. Once the “cradle of Islam in Southeast Asia”, Islamic tradition is historically rooted in Patani and provides the backbone to Patani identity. It is argued that the infidels who are referred to as kafir, invaded the holy land with the objective of destroying the Islamic heritage in order to replace it with a national Buddhist-dominated culture which is defined in Bangkok. This narrative portrays the Thais as intelligent enemies - instead of killing Muslims directly, they have been trying to melt down Islam for over a century. Although, according to indoctrinators, the Thai Buddhists allow the Muslims to superficially follow their faith (e.g. praying in Mosques), they eventually aim to destroy Islam through “Thai-ization” programs and establish the sole rule of Buddhism. The Thai “other” – associated with apostasy and a brutal form of local colonialism - especially aims at the young Muslims who they need to take over the Thai culture. Government programs are slowly extinguishing Malay Muslim culture by spreading Thai customs and Thai language, with the latter being obligatorily taught in government primary schools that all Thai citizens have to attend. As an insurgent comments: “The whole (educational, S.H.) system serves only one purpose: they want to destroy us through culture. Just as they destroyed Lanna culture. But here it won’t work” (insurgent interview, July 23, 2010)

Schools, once a pillar of Islamic culture and centre of local identity, are thus forced to become not only a form of cultural alienation, but also a strategic means in the enemy’s attempt to destroy local culture. Thus the authentic features of Patani Malay culture are

at an immediate risk of extinction. Just as the Algerian independence movement viewed the French educational system in Algeria as a key pillar in France's attempt to break up local culture, many Malays view Thai schools as crucial to the destruction of local Malay culture. According to the recruiter's narrative a second more indirect strategy to destroy Islam is the spread of Thai media, drugs, prostitution etc. with the consent of the Thai government in order to destroy the Malays and their culture in the South. According to this narrative, Muslims became spoiled and began to drink alcohol, have premarital sexual intercourse and the like.

The first dimension of the religious narrative refers to the suffering and humiliation of the Muslim community in the three provinces, while the second dimension revolves around the responsibility of the individual members to act. In this way, the fulfilment of the "holy order" on earth is put into the hands of every recruit, even if he or she fights as an individual against the Thais. Thus in order to defend the sanctity of Islam the recruit has to act now, because to not act is a sin. Jihad is not presented as a means to an end (independence), but as an end in itself; it is not only legitimate, but a holy duty for every Muslim in Patani.

In contrast to de-territorialized Islamist groups like al Qaida that reject the idea of nationalism and instead embrace the idea of the worldwide community of Muslims (umma), BRN-Coordinate pictures the Patani nation as a sacred religious community, or Patani Darulsalam. Indoctrinators try to intrinsically link the historical, nationalist and religious elements of the narrative through connecting them with Patani territory. Referring to the territorial dimension of jihad, BRN-Coordinate emphasises why the holy war must only be fought in the three provinces and not, for example, by Muslims in Bangkok or Chiang Mai. Here indoctrinators introduce an additional term that is deeply rooted in Islamic tradition and which is central to BRN-Coordinate's religious narrative: darulkuffar. Darul is Arabic meaning land, while kuffar refers to the unbeliever. Simply put, Patani is an Islamic land that has fallen under the rule of the "unbeliever" and thus all Muslims are obliged to liberate the darul from it in order to re-institutionalize the rule of Islam. In order to support their call to jihad, BRN-Coordinate's ulama also issued a fatwa (Islamic legal ruling) that stated that Southern Thailand is a darulharbi, (land of religious conflict), or darul jihad. As members of other jihadist groups, BRN-Coordinate recruits are supposed to study and memorize certain passages of the Koran that legitimize the idea of a holy war (Askew 2009a).

The second level of training consists of three different elements:

(1) As a continued purveying of ideas, the members have to learn in detail why the fight against the Siamese is a jihad. The idea of the jihad is not simply a thrilling hyperbole conveyed to the recruit, but it condensed symbols of Islam implying non-reconcilability between "Thai Buddhist culture" and "Malay Muslim culture". Recruits are told that jihad is not only a means, but also a religious duty imposed by God on Muslims. Killing

the enemies of Islam is not considered a sin, but the refusal to fight in the name of God is. Indoctrinators try to instil a shared sense of duty and mission. At the centre point of this “We-group” stands the self-ascribed task to fulfil God’s will on earth as understood by BRN-Coordinate ideologues - the creation of an Islamic state. To put it in the words of a BRN-manual: “We are the ones who proceed in God’s way.” Ismail remembers telling his recruits that:

“[...] the immoral rule of the Siamese led to the apostasy amongst Muslims. The prophet said: ‘Jihad is your duty!’ It is the holy duty of all Muslims to free their land from the rule of the infidels. Every breath you take under the rule of the infidels is a sin.”

Among other factors, the internal authority generated by the use of the charismatic idea of the jihad also serves to increase the individual’s readiness to use violence (Grossman 1995).

(2) The recruits have to study BRN-Coordinate membership rules:

1. Uphold religion and faith in Allah
2. Cooperate with and work for the group
3. Keep the secrecy of the group
4. Uphold the principle of resistance
5. Avoid doing anything that is of disadvantage to the group
6. Act according to religious principles
7. Be obedient to the leaders
8. Be on time
9. Be ready to give their lives and property whenever necessary
10. Do not contradict diverging opinions publicly

In different intelligence documents and interrogation records the ten provisions might appear in a slightly different order and with slightly different content. Regular praying and a devout lifestyle are stressed as trademarks of the community of insurgents. As the disciplinary code outlines; every member shall not adhere to worldly desires and subject his or her life to the organisation. In other words, the indoctrination aims to transform an imperfect individual into a disciplined and devout fighter (Schröter 2008).

In a sense, the community of the chosen ones and its strict lifestyle anticipates life in the imagined Islamic state of Patani: a state that unites the God-given otherworldly order with the present worldly order. The fighters try to avoid the surrounding world of seduction and apostasy. Thus strict codes of behaviour are not only to be applied within the organisation, but also in the private realm: ideal BRN-Coordinate members shop at BRN-Coordinate owned shops, such as minimarts that are run by other members, where they can be sure that the group receive parts of the shop’s profit; they visit special schools or Imams that reproduce the strict religion and narrative of the group, and spend

their free time with the group. As with other fundamentalist groups, BRN-Coordinate rejects an artificial border between the public and the private realm.

(3) Physical exercises are introduced, which includes, for instance, running, push-ups, jumping-jacks and chin-ups. Exercises serve both as a means of discipline as well as basic military training for the preparation of younger members. Older members usually fulfil duties in the political wing and are therefore exempted from the physical conditioning.

At the centre of the third level stands a sort of “life-style training”, which can be interpreted as an attempt to construct a common “Patani Malay” identity using symbolic markers such as local holidays, dress etc. The level is sub-divided into three topics: a) culture (kebudayaan): here the recruits learn, for example, about Malay holidays and customs such as hari maulid nabi muhammad (birthday of the prophet Mohammad), as well as the proper behaviour associated with these holidays. Here it is also stressed that members should not adhere to Thai public holidays, because most of them are holidays associated with the Thai state, the monarchy or Buddhism; b) recruits learn that they should not wear Western fashion, but dress in the traditional Patani dress (pakain Patani), which includes, for example, the sarong, the talok belenga (Malay shirt), and the songkok (Malay cap). Although no obligation to wear this dress exists, recruits are recommended to do so in order to openly distinguish themselves both from Thais.

Coupled with the Islamic lifestyle, such markers do not only fulfil the narrative on local Malay identity for BRN-Coordinate members, but within the multiethnic context of Southern Thailand they publicly denote ethnic divisions. Here it becomes clear that ethnicity, at times of social movement, denotes less a social reality, but rather demands from individuals a certain behaviour that accords to his affiliation with the ethnic groups (Elwert 1989). This behaviour is expected to give rise to a new social order. Inevitably, the concept of the “invention of tradition”, which is defined as a “set of practices, normally governed by overtly or tacitly accepted rules and of a ritual or symbolic nature, which automatically implies continuity with the past” comes into one’s mind (Hobsbawm 2003: 1). Simply put, the Patani Malay lifestyle is constructed as a sort of invariant natural law. The point of teaching here is not to teach how to dress in a technically correct way, but rather to ensure that it serves its ideological function. BRN-Coordinate thus becomes the conveyor and interpreter of the past and decides about the implications of the past for the future. Both revived Islam (especially the idea of the jihad), and the heritage of ancestors are adapted for the strength of the insurgency – it is what recruits have to fight for. In times of rapid social change, such a stress on the continuity of the past exerts a special appeal (Hobsbawm 2003). At the same time recruits continue with physical conditioning, which will be tested at the fourth level. For instance, the test comprises running 5km, push-ups etc. Usually all young men pass this level, since even physically weak recruits or individuals that are otherwise *hors de*

combat, can still be used for work in the political wing (e.g. local pemuda sections).

At the fifth and last level recruits are brought closer to a more concrete situation of war. They have to pass a kind of basic military training embracing, for instance, elements of martial arts. For this purpose teams of two are formed and within these teams recruits refer to each other using the English term “buddy”. The buddies have to practice self-defence practices and martial arts such as Taekwondo. Instructors, moreover, teach basic knowledge on weapons as well as fundamental first aid techniques such as how to apply a (pressure) bandage or give an injection.

In one case recruits in Pattani province reported that they were asked by indoctrinators to watch a war movie in order to bring the practice of war closer to them. Ideally the movie will show the defeat of a major power by a formally inferior insurgent movement such as the defeat of the Americans in Vietnam. “Apocalypse Now” has been shown in the past along with another film that deals with guerrilla activities in Indonesia during the war of independence. Afterwards the indoctrinators ask the recruits to analyse what they have seen, with they aim of building an understanding of why and how people fight as well as what “the nature of war“ is like.

At the end of the training course special commissions select those young men who show physical strength and seem generally apt for the combat situation from those who are more suited as *hors de combat*. The latter remain in the political wing, while the former receive additional military training and are channelled into the military. Basically, the decision whether a recruit is channelled into the military or not, is made by the cadres of the military wing, although the recruit is also asked and can formally refuse it. However military commanders claimed to me that most selected recruits agree to fight because they regard the military struggle as the most honourable part of the jihad. A number of RKK-fighters whom I interviewed, stressed that although they considered the political wing as necessary, one could only prove to be a “real mujaheddin” on the battlefield. They had a tendency to consider members of the political wing as “big-mouths” who would not dare to risk their life in a gun battle with Thai soldiers. In Panaræ district, Pattani Province, there seemed to be a conflict between some Ajak-committee members and the local military, in which they struggled over the control of young men. The Ajak members claimed that the military wing absorbed most young men and very few were left for them.

3.7. Military training

Once selected, the recruits of the military wing have to pass a phase of intense military training. In contrast to the ideological indoctrination outside the school system, in which the indoctrinator usually visits new members, different generations of fighters convene at a single site for a period of time. From the second half of the 1990s to 2004 at least, military training took place in camps lasting about one month. These camps were

organised in schools such as Islamburapah (Narathiwat) and Pondok Jihad (Pattani). In these camps and other sites different cycles of fighters were regularly trained until 2004, with a cycle consisting of approximately 20 or 30 recruits. Recent interrogations suggest that due to the risk of being exposed, the training curriculum is currently reduced to around 15 days and lesser numbers of recruits are trained at the same time.

Since the period of military training is relatively short, it is intense, with a focus on conveying the military skills needed for combat. As far as interviews indicate, the military camps do not stress ideological indoctrination as much as during the obligatory training beforehand. Thus from the very beginning recruits are put under immense physiological pressure, thus establishing a regime of discipline and obedience to superiors:

“We had to meet at Thammawitaya School on a Friday morning. I remember that we had to dress up in Dawah outfit, so that we would attract no attention from the authorities. They had prepared a pickup truck that drove us to Islamburapah School in Narathiwat. Immediately, we had to act like soldiers. The instructors whom we did not know came up to us and began to hit and kick the first person in the line. The person broke down, but we were ordered to stand still and watch forward. I stood pretty much at the other end of line, but I could see from the corner of my eye how the instructor worked through the line bashing every one of us. I was so afraid and wanted to run away, but we all just stood there.”

Secrecy and obedience are rigidly enforced during the training: students are not allowed to leave the training area or speak to outsiders. In addition to intense physical conditioning, sleep is often reduced by instructors to only one hour per night. Recruits usually report that they are not to question either the authority of the instructor or the content of their teachings. Different instructors and assistants supervise training, with each trainer a specialist on various aspects of insurgent knowledge such as guerrilla theory, shooting, intelligence gathering etc. Yet as the quality of the political wing varies from area to area, so probably does the military training due to the lack of qualified instructors etc.

The camps provide fighters with advanced knowledge on guerrilla warfare, with a special focus on unconventional RKK "small group tactics", which comprise, for example, tactical manoeuvres: a) Identification, observation and assessment of static as well as moving targets (including creeping up on the enemy, hiding, and cover techniques); b) Establishing rounds or control corridors, c) Planning the correct timing and method of assaults; d) Shooting techniques in defensive situations. One member of BRN-Coordinate's armed wing told me that he had to learn special combat breathing techniques that help in high-adrenaline situations such as being shot or being interrogated.

As fighters will later operate in RKK-squads composed of six fighters, six-man teams

are arranged for the training. Although instructors try to simulate real combat situations, shooting cannot be practiced with real bullets, due to the danger of being detected by government forces. Instead recruits aim and “fire” with wooden guns at their fellow recruits who run through nearby jungles or rubber fields simulating enemy targets. Since BRN-Coordinate mostly possesses small arms like assault rifles (mostly M-16 and AK-47), handguns and a few rocket-propelled grenades (RPG) captured from raids on Thai army camps, weapon familiarization is rather limited and mostly done “on the job” in the local units. However, real guns are used for teaching weapons handling: “We learn how to handle the guns, how to take them apart and what we have to do to maintain them.” Recruits also have to learn where to rightly hide guns before and after the mission.

Reconnaissance work, planning and intelligence are also practiced intensively, because they meticulously underpin all BRN-Coordinate combat missions. Persistence and patience dominate RKK-tactics that can be put into the “Four fast, one slow” formula as used by the Vietcong: “This meant fast advance, fast assault, fast clearance of the battlefield, and fast withdrawal – all based on slow preparation.” (Lanning & Cragg 1992: 173). Knowing the enemy’s movement and capacity as well as the area of operation in detail is the key to the RKK’s tactical advantage over Thai government security forces. Hence recruits learn how to study the terrain of their area of operation meticulously: they walk on virtually every possible street, way and footpath in an area and clock the time needed to walk between certain points. This is done during the day as well as during the night, during different weather conditions (rainy/dry) and, if possible, with different vehicles (such as motorcycle, pick-up truck), when the route allows for these forms of transport. Recruits are supposed to be able to fix certain points at which the RKK-squad members meet before an assault and they must plan escape routes thoroughly, so that the police or military are not able to capture them. Before attacking a target or planting a bomb, often the area of operation is observed for weeks ahead, in order to know the patrol pattern of security forces, the traffic situation and how to devise a possible ‘plan-B’. A military commander remarked on the principles of BRN-Coordinate’s military tactics: “Every mission must be a 100% certain. We cannot afford to fail. This is why the training and planning is so important”.

All these measures make violence predictable and less risky, which is an important condition for overcoming confrontational fear (Collins 2008). Hence preparation eases the tension between the individual’s fear of death and injury, which always persists, and the organisation’s aim to use violence. In contrast to the fighters of the LRA or the Taliban (Vinci 2005), BRN-Coordinate fighters avoid long-lasting, open gunfights and never march forward through enemy fire with a rifle in hand. Most ambushes in Southern Thailand end after a few minutes, because the insurgents fear back up of government forces. These practices of violence contradict the simplified religious

understanding of violence, which assumes that insurgents are not afraid to depart this life, because they are willing to die in a jihad or because they make use of Holy Spirit tactics (Nidhi 2005). Thus they must be trained step by step and approach violent actions gradually (Human Rights Watch 2007). Insurgents in Southern Thailand are indeed afraid to die and they lack the military knowledge to overcome the fear of close combat as the LRA or Taliban do. But, of course, they want to create an opposite image. The intense training allows insurgents to define the time and space of the attacks and thus gain a significant tactical advantage, just as it is laid down in classical insurgency handbooks (Smith 2008).

Being a clandestine organisation, BRN-Coordinate must utilize covert communications. If a guerrilla can move and communicate, he can kill. As secrecy is essential to the movement, BRN-Coordinate must rely heavily on what militaries refer to as operational security. For the recruits this means that they have to be hyper secretive about everything they do:

“Our principle is not to tell anyone about our organisation or our special activities, not even our closest relatives and friends. And under no circumstances should we give away information when we are caught and interrogated by the police. We learn that this is not only a betrayal of our brother, but an offence against God.”

On a practical level, secrecy means that recruits must overlay their insurgent activities on top of normal day-to-day activities. For instance, going to the market every day may also be a way to drop off a secret communiqué to the higher command and vice versa. Hence during training recruits are also taught how to code gathered information safely. This is done by coding the information in numbers and writing them down in small letters. Secret codes resemble, for example, mobile phone numbers, so that they cannot be understood by outsiders and do not attract attention. But they actually contain important information: 0237-1-4-4 can mean that at 14:37 one (1) car or pick-up manned with four (4) soldiers equipped with four (4) automatic guns were observed. This type of information is communicated through mobile and public phones as well as personal messengers, and the group also has walkie-talkies at their disposal.

Other irregular warfare techniques that are taught in the military camps are guerrilla theory, operational planning and close quarters combat, in which small units engage the enemy with personal weapons at very close range. Like Special Forces, RKK recruits practice in detail, entering and shooting in rooms. Here, the hand-to-hand combat techniques and martial arts skills that were already part of the basic military training are further developed. Also, important during the training is the concealment and detonation of roadside bombs.

Throughout the training recruits are constantly examined and punished if they violate disciplinary rules or (significantly) fail the tests on their acquired knowledge. Penalties

can include push-ups or other forms of physical punishments. As one insurgent remembers:

“I and a few comrades had to sit down in a fish pond, so that the water line came up to our mouths. It was just enough to breathe. We had to stay in there the whole night and were not allowed to make any sound. All the time the fish were biting us, but we had to keep still until dawn.”

As we know from other instances, such collectively shared sufferings reinforce feelings of solidarity among group members. For some time, at least, the “elite” of insurgents come together and live together, eat together, march together and go through the same pain. Recent intelligence suggests that in at least some areas recruits have to finish their training by being assigned the assassination of a target person “for practice” by superiors. As a sort of final examination the young fighters have to observe the target and plan how to eliminate it, applying the knowledge they gained in the weeks before. Superiors prefer this target person to be an official (policeman, soldier etc.), yet young men who seem unsure or show strong signs of fear can also be told to shoot civilians. One RKK-fighter explained to me that just after he had passed the training, he was ordered to shoot a Chinese owner of a rice-selling shop in Yala city:

“I had to coordinate my team. First we alternately observed him for hours and noted all possible escape routes from the target and checked how often police or army patrols passed by as well as with what weapons they were equipped. It was really hard, because we had to watch and remember everything without writing it down or staring at the target area, because this would have attracted attention. We had to act as normal pedestrians. Then we came together and began to discuss the operation. We had to choose the right type of gun and plan how to divide tasks. The question was how to transport the weapons without being controlled at police checkpoints.”

Then, the fighter and his superiors called off the mission, because there were too many police patrols passing the area that day, rendering the risk of the operation too high.

After finishing their training, fighters are assigned a personal identification number and then can choose the local military units in which they want to be employed, depending on where they will move after the training. In order to introduce new fighters local commanders can deploy them in “easy operations” or assign them to more experienced fighters from whose “know-how” they profit.

In one case a commander reassured his new fighters that they would not be punished if “something goes wrong” during the mission. The commander told me that he had once ordered an inexperienced fighter to assassinate a targeted person at a local market. However, the untried assassin missed his target with the first shoot allowing the target person to run away into the bustling market scene. Firing rounds at the escaping man, the assassin unintentionally shot a young Malay boy who died from the injuries. High cadres of both the political and military wing were obviously unsatisfied with the

outcome of the operation, as it posed a threat to the insurgent's reputation as a restraint force among the local Malay population. Inexperienced fighters fear such operations that can turn out of hand, not the least because these failures may invoke punishments from superiors. Having experienced this, the commander began to reassure those fighters who just passed military training and were deployed on their first mission, that he as their superior would take the whole responsibility for possible mistakes.

3.8. Communicative isolation

Many fundamentalist groups uphold loyalty to the group by isolating individuals from divergent views in their environment. The mandatory secrecy is not only an operational necessity, but it also helps to protect insurgents from Imam, parents or other figures of authority who might oppose the use of violence. As contrary views among the larger society of fellow Muslims in Southern Thailand are kept at bay or are simply labelled as "false understandings" of Islam, simply because they differ from the "truth", radical norms exclusive to the group are simply not questioned. Communicative isolation also involves the avoidance of Thai media, or its interpretation according to certain ideological patterns. Recruits are asked not to consume Thai media under the pretext that it is just "rotten enemy propaganda" and, if they consume the media, they must only to watch reports depicting the successful results of the group's military operations (e.g. pictures of assaults against government forces). These images of demonstrative violence help to instil a sense of self-efficacy among fighters, which is crucial to uphold the ability to act collectively (for details see last chapter).

As with all dissident groups BRN-Coordinate creates a mystifying perception, in which the power, effectiveness, and invincibility of the insurgents and God's divine provenance must eventually lead to victory. Therefore insurgents only attack in those moments in which they cannot be defeated, i.e. they avoid head-on confrontations with superior units of the Thai army and they retreat when they are attacked (Lichbach 1998). Such a "crippled epistemology" (Hardin 2004) is also maintained by sanctioning those religious leaders in Southern Thailand who defy the idea that the conflict in Southern Thailand is a jihad by issuing fatwas against them. It is argued that Islamic scholars with opposing views seither do not dare to say the truth or are simply ignorant. The intended result is a form of trust that is restricted to the in-group and an inertia of views towards violence.

Yet, although BRN-Coordinate intends to demand total loyalty, it can demand only "segmental commitment" (Coser 1973). Communicative isolation - as is typical for the milieu of suicide bombers - is hardly achievable. Since the group is based on an amateur force that has to continue to provide a living for itself, it is impossible to prevent members from committing to other local affiliations. In particular, the exclusive commitment to a woman poses a danger to the dedication of an insurgent. Commanders

seem to lose a painful number of fighters after they marry women who, not supporting the insurgency, successfully dissuade their husbands from risking their lives in military operations. As a countermeasure, BRN-Coordinate, just like its predecessor organisation BRN, arranges marriages between male members and female members or sympathizers.

3.9. Monitoring and sanctioning defection

It has been so far stressed how BRN-Coordinate makes use of consensus-based measures to foster internal structures. However, this is only one side of the coin, as monitoring and punishment are also used to maintain cohesion. Groups or organisations with high cohesion usually institutionalize both internal (e.g. moral constraints) and external sanctions (Crozier & Friedberg 1979: 25). Mutual control (monitoring and sanctioning) is as necessary for the group solidarity as fostered “We-group” sentiments based on the idea of the “chosen ones”. Members who want to defect are considered apostates and corrupters who deserve the punishment of death. Although BRN-Coordinate members don’t usually live together as a community of fighters, control over the individual’s will is maintained by a system of surveillance of their individual behaviour by other RKK-members and the political wing at the local level. For small groups it is relatively easy to guarantee secrecy, but once power and function are delegated within bigger groups, leaders have to entrust members with this resource. Here the small size of the RKK-squads (six) and the Ajak-committees (max. twelve) fulfils another important function: any professional Mafiosi knows that a small-size, tight-knit group facilitates secret operations and enables the monitoring of the other members, which is impossible in larger-sized groups (Krauthausen 1997). If members control each other, police infiltration is hardly possible, (Weinstein 2007). A former RKK-fighter told me he had the impression that after entering the organisation, he was under constant surveillance:

“A short time after my supoh, I flirted with a girl and invited her to have a drink in my village. Someone must have seen us together on a motorcycle, because afterwards my superior told me to stop such activities. It’s like their eyes and ears are everywhere. I had to stop doing what I usually did in the past.”

This system of supervision basically serves to guarantee the loyalty of its members and also prevents them from defecting to the government. Especially in villages, where the BRN-Coordinate has mobilised a strong Ajak-committee, both political and military members can be mobilised for surveillance. If, for example, an Ajak-chief suspects a member of the Ajak-committee to be collaborating with the government, he can ask the military wing to observe the suspect. Members of the military wing, who are not known to the suspect, can then observe him. In addition, those networks that help to mobilise candidates also help to monitor them and recognize, for instance, changes in the

suspect's behaviour.

Another type of monitoring involves the observation and evaluation of military action. Commanders want to know if fighters have internalized the lessons of training. In some cases, at least, military commanders gather "independent information" on the military performance of their squads either through the Thai media, personal friends or relatives that they have in the area of operation, or those who have witnessed an insurgent military operation. RKK-fighters report on the success or failure of their operation to superiors of the military wing. Yet pressure can, theoretically, also come from the political wing itself: if the sukum-committee, for example, notes that there has been little or no military activity in a certain area for some time, he might demand representatives of the military wing to take action. In other words, surveillance is supported by both peer monitoring as well as hierarchy (Weinstein 2007). Still, total surveillance is impossible, as members still have to carry on with their everyday life practices outside the insurgency, which necessarily gives them uncontrolled room to move. In this regard members cannot always be easily monitored nor their behaviour easily evaluated by superiors. Hence surveillance is naturally limited, but still seems to be effective when combined with the mechanisms of selection and training.

The fact that the group members are "locked up" in the organisation is also crucial for the Thai counterinsurgency campaign. In their attempt to eliminate the Ajak-committees, Thai security forces must first identify the members of the political wing at the village level. However, even if intelligence has received the names of one or even two Ajak-members in a village, security forces can hardly "convince" them to stop their involvement in the rebellion. A single member or two Ajak-committee members that defect BRN-Coordinate and collaborate with the incumbent power would be treated as traitors by the organisation and face death. Therefore COIN units in the villages usually must wait until they find a "critical mass" of Ajak-committee members (ca. 4-6) before they can paralyze the Ajak-committee as a whole (see last chapter). Usually BRN-Coordinate refrains from punishing such a high number of civilians on pain of death, since it would undermine the support of the local population. Any massacre against Malay civilians that is not convincingly blamed on the Thais could turn the tide against the insurgents within their population. Herein lies an important difference to other armed groups whose power is based on a reputation for unrestrained use of violence against civilians (Vinci 2005).

As a consequence, members who want to leave BRN-Coordinate have at least two exit options: either they defect "en mass" (e.g. a whole Ajak-committee) or they flee to somewhere outside the three provinces in order to save their lives. A third, most commonly used option, is to simply stand still and ask superiors, if one could "temporarily" pause insurgent action, without formally leaving the organisation. Often members do this under the pretext of personal affairs or Ajak-committee members, for

example, can argue that the presence of the military in their village render such activities currently too dangerous. In order to prevent such defection the group makes use of at least two additional mechanisms: on the one hand, the simple fact that fighters were already involved in homicides casts them into outlawry and make them fear criminal prosecution. On the other hand, they stress among their members that Thai state security will torture or even kill them when they are in custody. To bolster this claim, gruesome stories and pictures of apparent torture victims are circulated among insurgents.

Simply put, even though members seem to start from a position of moral indignation, they not only subject their bodies to the dangers of collective violence, but their commitment reaches a point where members lose the right to make moral judgement. Obedience to superiors and group pressure couples with the intrinsic logic of circles of violence and counter-violence.

3.10. Conclusion

Instead of relying solely on structural explanations of the mobilization of insurgents in Southern Thailand, I argue for an organisation-based view on participation. Gaining a critical mass of members, especially fighters, is crucial for the success of any insurgent group. While it is not possible to draw a definitive conclusion on the motivations of insurgents in Southern Thailand, it becomes clear that BRN-Coordinate, being a secret organisation, has to balance the demand for manpower with the necessity to defend the group's secrecy. The group therefore adopts a strategy of selective recruitment based more on a hostile Islamo-nationalist identification with an imagined Patani nation-state, pitted against the Thai enemy and, at least among the rank-and-file, less on short-term material benefits and coercion. Such an appeal to in-group solidarity can go hand-in-hand with a deliberate fostering of a sort of sanctified hatred against the enemy, which is enhanced by BRN-Coordinate's symbolic exploitation of Thai state atrocities through exclusionary (religious) rhetoric and rumour mills.

Since recruiters have no direct information on the motives of candidates, different mechanisms are used additionally to screen and select potential recruits. Through a combination of these methods the group is able to rely on rather dedicated individuals who identify with the group's struggle. To put it simply, not just anybody is accepted as a member of the organisation. In addition, I demonstrated that BRN-Coordinate developed a regime of combined physical and psychological methods that fosters the re-socialisation of those who are selected as members, into subjects who diminish their fears of death, and maintain the secrecy of the organisation, even against the closest loyalties. Thus the intense formalized training of the group not only serves to impart unconventional combat skills, but also attempts to shape individuals around a common set of knowledge and expectation, which is eased by the common ethnic background of

the recruits as well as the use of charismatic ideas. The resulting group coherence is also maintained by communicative isolation and the monitoring of possible defections.

4. Bringing the actor back in: who are the insurgents?

A study on an armed group and communication cannot leave out an analysis of the actors who fill the organisation with life and commit the violent acts. However, moving down the scale of observation from the meso-level of organisation, two fundamental questions typically arise. Whereas the first question focuses on who the organisers of violence are in terms of an insurgent's social, economic, political as well as psychological background, the second question asks why. Here, there is a tendency to develop theories about prime motives such as honour, material resources, hatred or the fight for a God-given or traditional order.

In order to answer these questions in the face of the incomprehensibility of fanaticism and violence, there has been a tendency to search for a “terrorist profile” – a pattern of abnormality, which is thought to explain the involvement of an individual in a campaign of collective violence. Unfortunately, however, none of the research approaches that have thus-far tackled this question, including individual psychological models and the so-called root cause research, have substantially supported the thesis of a terrorist profile (Horgan 2008; Sageman 2004). Albeit no such profile has been found yet, profiling remains attractive in the face of a lack of data.

The first part this chapter considers the little statistical evidence available on insurgents in order to challenge the assumption of a homogenous insurgent profile, one that supports the view of an economically, or educationally deprived stratum as a recruiting ground for insurgents. In order to present the insurgency in a clearer light the chapter then proceeds to lay down the routes of three BRN-Coordinate members, who worked in different functions of the group. The aim here is to depart from the simple picture of BRN-Coordinate as a homogenous group that moulds all its members – in a totalling fashion – into brainwashed members (as the last two chapters, which described BRN-Coordinate rather as a formal model of a smoothly functioning system, may have indicated). Instead of focusing on how the “system” works, it will be shown from an actor perspective that motives and routes of involvement are marked by complexity as well as significantly diverging meanings, and that members can retain a degree of agency within the organisation.

4.1. Socio-economic characteristics

Studies on the socio-economic background of Southern Thailand's insurgents are rarely available. Drawing on state interrogation records of captured insurgent suspects (as done here) certainly contains flaws, but currently these sources remain one of the very few available data pools (probably the only one) that allow for insight based on a representative sample. Standard records used by the police and army were not drafted by social scientists, but rather by security agencies and thus they often leave out very basic variables such as income, political attitudes, psychological disorders etc. In other

words, the decision to draw on police records, although it is a very pragmatic one, helps us to approach the insurgents by excluding certain simplified structural explanations of violence.

Similar to other armed conflicts, the perpetrators of violence are young, unmarried males. The age of the insurgent sample ranged from 16 to over 50 years. Their median age is 26.6 years, but most had been insurgents for some time before they were captured and consequently this was incorporated into the survey. Since most of the insurgents sampled are rank-and-file they are rather young. However, if we look higher up in BRN-Coordinate's hierarchy the picture changes. The first generation of RKK instructors and commanders seem to be in their mid - to late thirties, while the DPP leaders are aged between 40 and 70 (Colonel interview, August 12, 2009). In other words, while BRN-Coordinate's fighters are indeed a new generation, the group itself consists of at least three different generations. BRN-Coordinate's oldest generation of leaders mostly originate from its predecessor organisation, BRN. They still seem to command a significant degree of authority, because they founded BRN-Coordinate as a split-up group of BRN and re-organised it from a jungle-based guerrilla group to the current village-based guerrilla-cum-terrorist group that currently dominates the insurgency.

With regard to the socioeconomic and generational background, it is also important to note that insurgents can now draw on a large pool of two generations of students, teachers, academics as well as professionals who emerged as a result of the expansion of the educational system in the 1980s through Thai government programs and scholarship programs from Arabian as well as Middle Eastern oil-producing countries. This generation, often with degrees in Islamic subjects such as Islamic Studies, Islamic law etc., have access to Islamist knowledge and organisational resources such as communication techniques, access to the internet, libraries etc. At the same time this new middle class often lives in conditions of un- or underemployment.

Unfortunately, the interrogation records contained no data on the income situation of the suspects; so their socioeconomic status can only be indirectly established via variables like occupation. Here again we find a very heterogeneous picture. A majority of the sampled insurgents come from a rural peasant background: 54% are peasants, with most of them probably owning their own field or working on the fields of their parents. Only around 1% said that they were unemployed. Another 5% are owners of small businesses, among them are owners of local minimarts, motorcycle garages, mobile phone repair shops etc. Close to 12% work in rather more precarious economic conditions, for example as hired labourers or in the agricultural industry or for construction companies. Only 2% of the sample works as religious teachers (ustadz). This number might be misleading, because within, for example, the BRN-Coordinate hierarchy, ustadz as well as religious scholars seem to play important roles as recruiters

as well as cadres in the political wing. Besides, they seem to dominate the DPP: the suspected chairman of BRN-Coordinate, for example, is the owner of a Private Islamic School in the South, while the suspected vice-chairman is an Islamic scholar (ulama) and member of an Islamic Council in one of the three provinces. BRN-Coordinate's leading figures, its secretary-general Sapeing Basoh and vice general-secretary Asae Chaelong also belong to this section of the middle class, with the former being the ex-principle of Thammawitaya Foundation Private Islamic School in Yala and the latter having established a local pondoh school (Colonel interview, September 28, 2009). Another 8% of the sample work as employees for private and even state companies.

Moreover, it seems that a significant part of the rank-and-file still live with their parents and thus are not too occupied with their economic survival. One of the key features that distinguishes the old BRN from BRN-Coordinate is the shift from a professional guerrilla group to a part-time guerrilla-cum-terrorist group. As part-time fighters provide for their own livelihood, the group can externalize the costs of reproduction and maintaining its fighting force. When members of the armed wing have free time, they disappear from their civil life for a period in order to participate in military activities, only to return to their normal lives in the villages afterwards. This new 'time economy' coupled with mingling in the civilian population makes counterinsurgency very difficult. In contrast to the past, the state at present can hardly isolate insurgents nor hunt them down in the jungles.

With regard to a possible rural-urban gap it should be noted that 88% of the suspects live in rural areas, while merely 12% live in the urban contexts of Yala, Narathiwat or Pattani city. Therefore "psychosocial models" which argue that, for example, urban migrants are susceptible to the propaganda of violent groups, because they are cut off from their rural backgrounds and experience a different value system in the urban context, seem not to be applicable here (Hafez & Wiktorowicz 2004). Moreover, none of the insurgent suspects were born outside the three provinces and four insurgent districts in Songkhla province. Thus the insurgency is still clearly spatially defined for the local recruits.

As to education, the sample is very heterogeneous. There is no single profile of an "uneducated" insurgent. Although most of them come from rural backgrounds, 74% completed secondary education. A quarter of them has only primary education, while a top 13% had been enrolled in or even had a degree from tertiary educational institutions. All of them had attended universities in Thailand. One of the two Hat Yai bombers that killed at least four people on 16 September 2006, for example, had a Master degree from a university in Thailand (Lt. General interview, September 14, 2009). This relatively high level of formal education is also reflected in the insurgents' language skills. The sample shows that a majority of the captured insurgents were able to speak Thai well, although during interrogation suspects tended to understate their Thai

language skills or simply “act dumb” in an attempt to evade the interrogator’s questions.

It should also be noted, that contrary to what is often reported in the media or assumed by popular narratives, very few insurgents have a criminal background: only around 1% of the sampled insurgents have criminal records with the Thai authorities. Two RKK commanders whom I interviewed also stressed that they would not allow drug-usage among their fighters, because drug-addicts are unreliable and thus unsuited for insurgent attacks. Here it seems that the typical “crook” does not rank very prominently among the lower strata of insurgents. This speaks clearly against, for example, former Prime Minister Thaksin Shinawatra’s assumption that attackers in Southern Thailand are only a bunch of criminals (McCargo 2006). This is despite the fact that intelligence has, until now, gathered little information on any possible link between the illegal economy and higher-level insurgents (*ibid.*).

Another question that often arises in the discussion on the insurgency is the extend to which Muslim insurgents understand or misunderstand Islam. Considering the formal religious knowledge of the insurgents sampled there can be no straightforward answer to this. Islamic studies in Southern Thailand are ranked from level 1 to level 12, with 12 being the highest degree of religious studies completed. Suspects achieved an average 5 out of 12 and thus have at least some basic religious understanding. A handful of the sampled insurgents, especially those with university degrees, passed level 9 or even higher. In other words, this heterogeneous educational background, in both secular and religious dimensions, including highly educated insurgents even at the staff level, speaks against the argument that insurgents are stupid and susceptible to manipulation, although it has been shown that even high educational levels correlate with authoritarian personality structures (see below).

Clearly, more detailed analyses on the socioeconomic context of insurgents is needed. Nonetheless, the data allows for some tentative conclusions. Politicians and popular accounts of collective violence in the media have a tendency to assume a correlation between collective violence and poverty.²⁹ Generally, although in recent years there has been an influx of econometric studies on civil war (see, e.g. Collier & Hoeffler 2004), few robust results have been reached. Usually, factors such as unemployment, poverty or cultural discrimination are said to add up and lead to an explosion of violence. But such econometric attempts to explain violence remain subject to fundamental methodological flaws (Kalyvas 2008). Contrary to a commonsense understanding, the increase in economic performance usually goes hand in hand with an increase in the general level of violence (Elwert 2003). And even the socioeconomic backgrounds of insurgents should not be overestimated, because the socioeconomic profile of insurgents tells us little about the patterns and motives for violence for a number of reasons, not the

²⁹ Politicians, bureaucrats and local Malay elites, such as local school owners, can get their piece of the pie, if the state invests enormous sums in development projects. Who can say anything against these honourable aims?

least because militants and moderates share several of the same characteristics, including levels of education etc. So the question remains: why do some become involved in violence, while others do not?

With regard to the insurgency in Southern Thailand, the abovementioned, preliminary data seem to confirm Srisompob's analyses (2006) which, using macro-economic indicators, argued that poverty and violence do not clearly correlate (although the region overall still belongs to the poorest in Thailand). Poverty or a lack of education seem not to be at the core of violence, although different strategic groups might have an interest in suggesting this.³⁰ In other cases such as the rebellion of the Tamils in Sri Lanka, the minority problem is essential - the group had to fight, not for a better life, but merely to avoid the decline of the current status quo (no matter how miserable the current status is). This is illustrated by the generational conflict among Tamils that contributed as much to the violent conflict as did the discrimination by the central government (Hellmann-Rajanayagam 1994). In that case, a younger generation had fewer or worse prospects than its forefathers, but in Southern Thailand, although the bureaucracy is still dominated by Buddhists, the younger generation seems to have better overall prospects than the previous one, a consequence of economic growth, the expansion of the state-sponsored education system (including the "not-so-private" Islamic School sector) as well as scholarships since the early 1980s (Horstmann 2002). However, the perception of inequality may differ from these developments. In Malaysia, a country that often serves for comparison, university graduates earn higher incomes than the Malay Muslim graduates in the three provinces. Expectations appear to be higher than what is actually on offer.

In contrast to other conflicts in which whole economic structures are undermined, the Malay middle class in Southern Thailand can still seek employment and pursue typical status symbols like cars, houses and a good education for their children. With regard to the peasant sector, the fall of income from rubber production was more significant during the Asian crisis than in, for example, 2004, when the world prices had recovered. Social scientists often assume that violence destroys social relations and economies, but in the South the violence led to a decrease in local agricultural production of only around 5 % only (although numbers are not too reliable) (interview SBPC officials, September 7, 2010).

4.2. Case studies

Many studies of armed groups and of violent conflicts in general, pitch their

³⁰ Another more subjective argument might support this view. Interestingly, none of the BRN-Coordinate members I interviewed personally considered him – or herself "poor". When I asked them to describe their economic status in their own words, all of them answered, in separate interviews, that they considered themselves neither "rich" nor "poor", but rather as "normal income farmers" and that their motives were clearly more political and religious than economic (Insurgent interview, 12 November 2009).

explanations in terms of violent collectives, talking about “the IRA”, “the Tamils” or “the insurgents” in general. In other words, these accounts have a tendency to homogenize the violent collective through “languages of patriotism and betrayal in popular representations, which is then mimicked in anthropological accounts of this violence” (Das & Kleinman 2000: 11). In Southern Thailand this bias is perpetuated by the fact that scholars and journalists, lacking direct access to the performers of violence, tend to turn to local informants, who are willing to interpret the motivations of those who are actually the perpetrators of the violence. These “interpreters of violence”, often local Malay-Muslim intellectuals, tend to make reference to “history”, “nationalism”, “religion” and “ethnicity” or state repression - factors that, drawing on transnational discourses, appear self-explanatory and of which the interpreters themselves are partly convinced. This interpretive capacity allows even some to accumulate immense symbolic and social capital that, in turn, influences for example, media and scholarly accounts of the conflict.

However, not only are the socio-economic and educational backgrounds of insurgents very different, but their motives, routes of involvement and functions within the organisation are also marked by complexity. Thus we should be reminded of the distinction between emic and etic views, i.e. between local accounts of events and motives drawing on the subject’s own language, and a seemingly more objective description in scientific categories. As will be shown below, even among a highly selective group like BRN-Coordinate, being ‘involved’ has different meanings for different people. And importantly, even for one person these meanings (and motivations) can switch over time (Horgan 2008). Hence, the aim of the following section is twofold: first, I want to move beyond the abstract treatment of insurgent groups as anonymous and give participants a face, by analysing three BRN-Coordinate members and their routes of entry into the group in detail. Taking up the viewpoint of each member concerned, I follow Hogan’s proposal to overcome the not so fruitful static search for a terrorist profile and instead seeks to understand involvement in terrorism as a staged course of action.³¹ Secondly, biographical data shall throw light on the relations between the violent collective and the individual member, as well as on the relation between the violent collective and its environment.

A note on methodological difficulties: beyond the standardized ideology of the group the discourses at the level of the individual are often hard to decipher, because they are not openly discussed in the public sphere. Rather, they take the form of incessant murmurs of rumours, jokes, stigmatisation, conspiracies or fantasies. James Scott has argued that any system of domination produces its own dialectics between public

³¹ Instead of seeing the involvement in terrorism as a manifestation of some (psychological, religious, socio-economic or political) state, Hogan understands such involvement as process in which “someone seeks out (initially for reasons that differ from the subsequent reality of what being involved actually delivers) and strives to sustain while moving from some unfocused peripheral state to something more focused, narrow, and unambiguously terrorist related” (Hogan 2008: 81).

discourses, shaped by the national centre and its powerful elites, and the hidden transcript of the less powerful (Scott 1990). This distinction, which may also be applied to the level of armed groups themselves, helps us to understand, for example, why people join and how they negotiate between local particularistic nationalism and more universal concepts such as worldwide communities of Muslims, the ummah. Another basic difficulty in using ex-post statements of BRN-Coordinate insurgents is that these statements are, directly or indirectly, marked by the socialising process that they had to pass through. Members, especially those, who are still active, tend to interpret this juncture in a sense that throws a positive light on the movement as a whole. To put it differently, by asking the “why”-question we tend to get more information on the group’s internal usage of propaganda than on the individual’s reasons for joining (Horgan 2008). Explaining violence with the help of self-proclaimed motives and emotions is further hardened by the fact that violence creates its own motives, as will be shown below. This means that actors can formulate motives for their violent actions ex post, even if these were affective (Elwert 1998). An illustrative example is the following quote from an RKK-fighter:

“Once you are within the military wing and become involved in an operation, it’s hard to get out. The police searches for you, they interrogate your parents and put pressure on your brothers. And once they kill or arrest someone from your group, a new round begins, because you want to take revenge on them.”

Emergences of motives as well as violence are produced concurrently in the same process and ideas of why people fight emerge and shift over the course of time as the conflict heats up.

4.2.1. Ding: The excitement of violence

Ding, aged 28, commanded a RKK squad in one of Pattani’s sub-districts. In his area of responsibility Ding was involved in the planning of numerous bombings and assassinations. To me Ding seemed calm and friendly, and when talking about his involvement in military activities he even seemed shy. In the beginning we talked about how he got involved in the insurgency as well as his motivation to participate. On both topics he was directly outspoken and could easily respond in Thai. After we met a couple of times, however, he began to talk relatively openly about his role in acts of violence, even taking pride in being interviewed by a foreign scholar.

Ding is far from the classical picture of a pious or politically motivated militant. Born as the son of rubber farmers in an all-Malay village, Ding was more interested in chasing girls and making night trips to Hat Yai, returning to Pattani the next morning after long nights in bars and discotheques, he told me laughingly. Whereas another clique of kids from neighbouring households went to study in Hat Yai, Bangkok or even in Chiang Mai, Ding’s friends and fellow youth in the village often joined motorcycle gangs, and

cruised around. Two of his Malay Muslim school friends, also sons of small traders and Thai rubber peasants, even became government officials, one in the local district office and another in the local Thai police. Though Ding respected their careers, he never thought about taking the same route. After finishing secondary school he did not intend on continuing his studies at a university level, since he was not a keen student (neither of religious nor of worldly studies) and his parents had already offered him a rubber plantation, which would generate enough income to guarantee his lifestyle. In one interview he even admitted to having sold amphetamines (which he had regularly bought from a dealer in Hat Yai) to people in his village, thus helping him to save enough money to buy a second-hand car.

Ding stressed that he personally had never had any bad experience with Thai Buddhist officials or Buddhists in general, nor were the people in his village very religious or nationalistic. Sometime he and his mother even talked Thai at home and watching Thai television was common for them. For several years Ding had a Buddhist girlfriend in Hat Yai. Like other fighters (Askew 2009a), he never attended a private religious school or a pondok and thus his religious knowledge was restricted to what he had learned at the tatika school as a young boy. His involvement in the insurgency began when Ding's uncle, a BRN-Coordinate member himself, invited him to join the group:

“Actually I was never interested in politics before I entered Coordinate.³² As everyone else, I knew about the Thai atrocities against us, but this never aroused much interest in me. I preferred hanging around with folks from my village and other areas who were also not interested in politics or religion. We never talked about these things. I had heard before that my uncle was with the movement, but I never asked him anything. But when I was 23 or 24 years old, things changed. My uncle came to me one Sunday and wanted to know, if I would want to know anything about the movement. Since I did not want to resist, he began talking. He spoke of the many different ways in which the Thais repressed Patani Malays and how they tortured our ancestors and friends in the prisons. What I found more thrilling was how he talked about joining the group and what life as a secret fighter would be like. He mentioned that I would get a military education and that there would be many challenging missions for me. My uncle did not mention what these missions would be. But maybe that made it sound even more interesting.”

Initially Ding had no clear motivation to participate except for a feeling of excitement. He claims that it even took him some weeks before he agreed to his uncle's proposal to join. He never considered himself an “intellectual” or a very religious man. Only after his recruitment did Ding begin to become interested in matters of politics and the call to jihad specifically. However, in contrast to the fellow newcomers, who passed training with him, he disliked reading books: “I think my motives for joining changed. At the

³² Some members refer to “BRN-Coordinate” simply as “Coordinate”.

beginning it was because of the thrill. I wasn't really a supporter for independence, but now I'm aware that my fight really helps the people here and I know that I do something good for my religion." Explaining the last two points, Ding argued that any Muslim nation has a duty to defend itself against an infidel invasion, and he considered the Thais as an infidel colonial power, despite the fact that on an everyday basis he had good relations with them.

An additional benefit that he associated with his involvement was the attainment of a new status, even outside of the organisation. Ding stressed that being an insurgent changed his social status within his village: "Since the kids and elders in my village began to realize that I must somehow be associated with the movement, they began to respect, and even fear me. Even the village head is now afraid of me. In the past they never listened to what I said, but now they do." This example shows that insurgents can consciously infringe the rule of secrecy by divulging to others the secrecy of their membership when they are sure that it safe to do so. For Ding, disclosure was not tactical behaviour. On the contrary, he admittedly acted against explicit orders by superiors solely in order to increase his personal power within the village. In other cases, insurgents reveal their connection to the insurgency, for instance, when they recruit other people in their village or threaten the village head to cooperate with the movement. But in the case of Ding he simply told youngsters in the village that he now was with "the movement". Doing this Ding was well aware that these youngsters would tell their parents and the village head, but he stressed that he did not feel unsafe: "I was sure that they would not give my name to the police, because they are afraid to die. Too many things have happened in the past."

Even though Ding clearly enjoyed the new power and recognition that his involvement in the insurgency had brought to him, he also seemed to be burdened by the contradiction between his personal lifestyle and the image of the 'pristine fighter', whose motivation is devoid of personal references:

"I know I'm not a mujaheddin with a pure heart that Coordinate always talks about. Other people really changed in the movement, but I still take some drugs from time to time and I still go out in Hat Yai. Though I don't take heroin and I never went to see a prostitute. People in my kampung died from heroin. It's really a dangerous stuff."

Ding told me that he felt like he was living two lives between which he had to constantly negotiate. On the one hand, he was an RKK-fighter and a mujaheddin, commanding two squads and also according to the group's ideology, a role model for the younger fighters under his command. On the other hand, he was not able to quit living his former life of going out to discotheques and consuming drugs, which clearly was the opposite of what he was supposed to behave like:

"On the weekends, I tell the other Coordinate guys in my squad that I have to work in Hat Yai or Songkhla, but in fact I go out there and

hope that none of them see me there by chance. If they knew, I would lose all of the respect they have for me. They don't know that I still have non-Muslim friends there, which I'm supposed to give up. That is also why I'm not married – I don't want to lose my freedom.”

At various times Ding condemned the spreading drug consumption, prostitution among Malays and the political system, while at the same time, he was also leading the worldly “Buddhist” lifestyle he fought against: “After being arrested the Buddhist drug dealers simply pays off the damned corrupt officials and then they can leave the prison. Even Thaksin’s war against the drugs didn’t change a thing.”

Ding is not clear on whether the Siamese are solely responsible for this state of affairs: “Maybe our own people share responsibility for what has happened, but it will get better. Once the Siamese leave, people will return to Islam.” Notably, his image of what an independent Patani would look like remained vague and unspecific beyond ideological generalities, such as the introduction of sharia and the end to social ills. Although he admittedly could not really distinguish whether he is fighting for the Patani nation or for religion, he is clear on who the enemy is. His reading of the Patani Jihad does not include the “West” in general or countries like the United States or Great Britain, though he is, like other Malay Muslims, suffused with hatred for Israel in particular. Ding simply wanted the Siamese to get out of Patani so that Patani Muslims could reshape the country according to local principles. For him personally this quest meant “following the orders of his superiors, even if you might not understand the sense of every operation. But I trust the leaders of the group. They have long term vision and overview.”

Not only did Ding continue his “worldly”, hedonistic lifestyle, but he was apparently able to limit the degree of his involvement as well. When his immediate superior in the military wing asked Ding if he was willing to take over command of two RKK-squads, Ding refused, arguing that he was not yet able to bear such high responsibility. Yet this, he revealed, was only an excuse. In reality, he simply liked what he called “easy operations”, such as assassinating village heads or unarmed civilians: “not much planning is involved. I have clear instructions and nothing can go wrong, but I dislike planning bigger operations and being involved in assaults on the military. Others in our group are proud if they are given higher positions, but that’s nothing for me.” From this it appears that it is not the violence itself that poses a problem for Ding, but rather the specific risks involved in operations.

In Ding’s view, the killing of Buddhists and Malays (in which he was admittedly involved) was not a sin, because he believed in the righteousness of the group’s fatwa, which stated that Patani was Darulharabi and that the fight against the Siamese was a jihad:

“How can one deny the two points that matter here: First, the Siamese

invaded an Islamic land. And, second, they slowly destroyed the Islamic culture. Although they allow us to pray, they have many ways of destroying Islam: It starts with the school system, then you see temples being built everywhere and they also bring in more and more Buddhists from other regions. They think we are a disturbing minority that needs to be extinguished. They want all to speak Thai and pray to Buddha statues.”

Before he entered BRN-Coordinate, Ding thought that it was wrong to kill Buddhist civilians and he thought that it was against the Koran to kill Muslims. However the group’s Islamic scholars, he insisted, taught him differently. Ding stressed that he took a long time at first to learn the basic principles of jihad, especially regarding what is permissible and what is not permissible. Albeit, he confessed, he was no Islamic scholar, he is sure that killing civilians for a better future is morally right and permissible. One particular principle he learned, is that anyone who aids the infidel rule over the Islamic land is an infidel no matter whether he calls himself a Muslim or not and thus, he can be killed. Indeed it is the duty of the Mujahid to do so: “Those Malays, who say something different, do not know or they don’t dare to speak the truth.” However, he declared, the killing of a Malay collaborator is still a procedure that has to follow certain rules in order to be morally right. First and foremost it is important to gather information on the collaborator from independent sources. Ding was sure that before his superiors ever order him to undertake such a mission, they will have checked that the Malay person who is the target, is really working for the “infidel suppressors”, and the only with the sanctification of a fatwa will he be allowed to proceed to plan the operation.

4.2.2. Abdulloh: fighting for merdeka³³ in the name of God

Abdulloh, now aged 37, was recruited in 2002 by the Ajak-committee chief in his village. Both lived in a Malay village close to a market district town in Yala. Abdulloh’s father died in a car accident when Abdulloh was still going to elementary school and his mother, a market vendor, raised Abdulloh and his sister with the financial support of their uncle. This enabled him to finish secondary school, a local Private Islamic School. Abdulloh’s recruitment story did not begin at his home or school, but rather within his village. After BRN-Coordinate successfully established the Ajak-committee there, members began to look for more members, in the village, as they had been told to recruit as many young men (and women) as possible. Unlike other children, Abdulloh held adult responsibilities, having to support his family economically. Because of this economic burden, from his teenage years onwards, he sought income by helping a smuggler: “It was not because I liked smuggling, but rather because I had a feeling of responsibility. This helped us a lot. Together with the income of my mother, we could even afford to buy a fridge, TV-set and a car. I could send my

³³ Merdeka is the Malay term for independence.

sister to school.”

When Abdulloh finished secondary school, his mother wanted him to go to a university in Thailand or Malaysia, but Abdulloh himself wanted to wait, because smuggling was too lucrative to give up. As his boss (a local Malay) became older and unable to conduct the smuggling himself, Abdulloh began running independently his own smuggling tours. He knew how the business ran: buy frozen chickens in Hat Yai and transport them illegally to Malaysia in order to sell them to Pattani Malays who owned Tom Yam Gung shops there. From his years of assistance he had acquired the necessary connections to businessmen, Malay border police and local buyers.

Since Abdulloh had a lot of time in between his tours, he was often in his village. After joining the Friday prayer in late 1999, a fellow villager and the Imam approached him:

“They asked what I thought about the killings of Palestinians by Israelis. They involved me in a long talk to check my attitude, but at that time I did not know. Nothing happened after the first talk. Only a few weeks later they invited me to another mosque, where another Imam, whom I did not know, waited to talk about the suppression of Muslims all over the world and the need to act. He said that we had to do something, and that there would be no other choice.”

After this indoctrination Abdulloh was invited by yet another person to participate. Abdulloh finally agreed to join, because being convinced by the Imam, he considered, that it was his religious duty to do so. Thai officials had harassed neither Abdulloh nor his family, though from early on in school he had the impression that “the Thais generally look down on Malays”. Justifying his decision to participate in BRN-Coordinate, Abdulloh stresses that he had a great deal of sympathy for his fellow Muslims, who were victims of violent state repression in Southern Thailand during earlier times, when “they defended the independence of Patani with their blood.” Although Abdulloh had felt this resentment before, the recruiting Imam had expressed the need for action in such “clear and convincing terms, that it could not be denied.”

Although, at the time of his recruitment BRN-Coordinate had not yet started the violent campaign, Abdulloh did not hesitate to use violence. Rather, Abdulloh had second thoughts about joining, because as the “man of the house” he still had to financially care for his siblings as well as his mother, and was therefore not sure how far his involvement could potentially affect his economic activities. The recruiter, however, guaranteed that his involvement would still leave him enough time to work. Abdulloh was made responsible for the economic section within the area of his home sub-district, whereby he established a BRN-Coordinate trading shop using his personal savings funds. He proudly claimed that he donated almost 100% of the shop’s earnings to the group and that he kept nothing for himself. Furthermore, he was made responsible for supplying BRN-Coordinate affiliated Tom Yum Gung shops in Malaysia with smuggled frozen chickens, which allowed him to combine his smuggling skills with the group’s

economic network.

Abdulloh stressed that at the time of his recruitment he was pious but had not yet “really understood the meaning of Islam”. He joined the Friday prayers, followed the general rules of an Islamic lifestyle and believed in God, but beyond that he did not consider himself a ‘man of God’. In this sense, Abdulloh experienced his involvement in the insurgency primarily as a religious act and revelation, and not due to the ‘excitement’ of having a gun in one’s hand:

“It was Coordinate. They opened my eyes. The trainers showed me that the real essence of life for every faithful Muslim is not only the adherence to the five pillars of Islam, but that every Muslim must fulfil God’s will on the collective level as well. I learned a lot about being a shaded (martyr), a big issue in the Koran. But I also began to inform myself by reading books on the jihad, the situation of America and Israel, Afghanistan, Iraq all that. Before we initiated our violent campaign against the Thais in 2004, when the situation was not so dangerous as it is now, I also used the internet regularly and spent some time with members of the ulama section discussing religious matters as well as the meaning and implications of the jihad.”

Abdulloh remarked that BRN-Coordinate showed him that the current social and political system is inept and is incompatible with the Thai rule. “Infidel’s rule” is only one, though the key, aspect of the violation of Islamic principles: Patani Malays have accepted the rule of the faithless, Thai and Western law-codes have suppressed the sharia, and local Muslim politicians are as corrupt as their Thai counterparts and have done nothing to reinstate Muslim institutions. Even worse, Abdulloh believes, is the fact that the Thai rulers and local politicians corrupted the Muslim clergy in the South as well: “Imams and Islamic teachers help Malay politicians to buy votes. They become swallowed into the system and lose their sense of being a Patani Malay.” When asked, if a federal democratic order or autonomy would be a solution for the conflict in the South, Abdulloh responded that he viewed democracy with suspicion because of its Western origin. Thailand claims to be a democracy, which in his view is cunning: “Thailand tells the outside world that they are a democracy, but it’s all a trick. They not only give us no democratic rights, but they also constantly destroy us.” For Abdulloh, Muslims who are satisfied with Thai democracy are false Muslims or only “Muslims by name”. According to Abdulloh, it is no wonder, that the consequence of this is moral decay, poverty, illiteracy and the spread of radhila (vices in Arab).

Although Abdulloh’s main goal was the institutionalization of the transcendental into the worldly order, like other Islamists, Abdulloh was highly “modern” with regard to education, technology and the organisation of BRN-Coordinate (he mentioned, for example, how important it was to learn the techniques of rebellions from other insurgent organisations around the world). More fundamentally, Abdulloh himself is modern in the sense that he shares the key assumption of modernity, namely that the world can be

formed by human agency, i.e. by a conscious moral choice (Eisenstadt 1999), which, to him, meant not to accept the “colonisation” by Bangkok and rather to fight it. The centrepiece of this true Islamic society is the implementation of sharia, seen as a panacea for all social ills, which must be applied to every aspect of society, including the law, economy, and politics. Although, he admitted, the Thai state allows for the application of sharia in some areas like family or heritage law, for Abdulloh, this is not enough: “the whole public administration must be Islamic. I don’t know exactly what the economy or the taxation system of an independent Patani would be like, but it doesn’t matter, because the basic guidelines for everything are in the holy Koran.” What the BRN-Coordinate offered to Abdulloh was also sense a of greatness and the feeling that power relations between Thais and Malays were now reversed in favour of the suppressed Muslims.

However, Abdulloh did not simply copy these transnational Islamist objectives - he rather applied them to the local context. Although he stated that Islam is supranational, even universal, and he emphasizes that support for Patani’s independence also comes from other Islamic countries, his understanding of Islam is framed within the particularistic and imagined Patani national context, “I fight primarily for Islam, but Patani is the container for Islam here. Without the Patani nation Islam is shapeless and abstract.” Abdulloh appropriated images of modernisation and used a universal (Islamic) identity to strengthen, or construct, a particularistic “Patani Malayness”³⁴:

“Islam in Patani is not the same as Islam in the Arab world, which is a purer version of Islam that the Patani Malay should attempt to embrace in the future, when the education of our people is better. But in some aspects we are also Patani Malays, we have our own Islamic scholars and Islamic traditions that can also be maintained, as long as they don’t constrain pure wisdom and development. I imagine Patani after merdeka not to be like Thailand, or the West or Arabia, but more like the industrialised and modern-educated Malaysia. In contrast to Arab countries we have no oil and in contrast to the Thais, we must have a more orderly and disciplined progress. But again we are not Malaysia and we will not be a colony of Malaysia. Patani will be independent at a later stage, and that allows us to take the best ideas of all and apply them here.”

The successful appropriation of the global flow of Islamist ideas and images is, however, not only illustrated by Abdulloh’s version of a “better life”, but also reflected in his construction of the jihad, which is used to achieve his version of a better future, “enemy” that it is directed at as well as being the justification of its violent means. More

³⁴ A similar process can be observed in Malaysia, where modernisation created the need to “invent” Malaysian specificities, distinguishing Malay modernity from Western modernity, which is an attractive and repulsive force at the same time. Within the country, social change also meant that the definition of Malayness, which in the past was associated with either a rural peasant or court society, had to be “modernized”, especially in an urban context where Malaysian cities were associated with Chinese economic dominance and a strong Indian professional sector. Hence with the help of modernizing Islam, the equation “a Malay is a Muslim” was changed to “a Muslim in Malaysia is a Malay” (Korff 2001: 282).

than Ding, for instance, Abdulloh tended to position the conflict in Southern Thailand as just another feature of the global “clash of cultures” between the West and the Islamic world.

Here again, though, we should be reminded not to mix up emic and etic views of jihad. Indeed, if one takes up a scientific definition of jihad as a global network made up of local branches of local tribal fighters (cf. Kilcullen 2005), the case of Southern Thailand does not fall under this definition. An alarmist view that locates Southern Thailand as just another hotspot of international terrorism is certainly simplifying and misleading, but taking the opposite view – as did the 2005 ICG report – seems to throw out the baby with the bath water, because even the political programmes of territorial movements are typically embedded in the global flows of ideas (Appadurai 1990). It downplays the charismatic appeal of transnational ideas such as the idea of the jihad on the ground in Southern Thailand. Local factors play a crucial role in the insurgency (as already pointed out, the insurgency was planned long before the US invasion of Afghanistan and Iraq), but as the case of Abdulloh (and interviews with recruiters) indicates, the sympathy for the apparent suffering of Muslims elsewhere around the world is also a key mobilizing apparatus and the term jihad has been manipulated by insurgent ideologists into a catchy term, along side local ideas of historical discrimination.

In this sense, the important point about Abdulloh’s use of the term jihad is not so much, whether it is a correct picture or interpretation of the conflict in Southern Thailand, but rather that it influences his perception of the conflict. With the help of certain prominent ideas locals can make sense of what is going on in their societies and communicate “their case” to an external audience, which may potentially support them. This was earlier the case in Southeast Asia with Maoist ideas of social revolution. At that time China was seen as a successful predecessor and supporter. In the case of BRN-Coordinate, the ideological orientation now focuses more heavily on the Middle East and elsewhere in the Islamic world, adopting their methods and interpretations of resistance. Being aware of this, the architects of the Thai COIN campaign in the region were very keen to find a well-known and respected Islamic scholar in the three provinces, who would publicly issue a fatwa, declaring that insurgents were not fighting a jihad.

However, locals are not simply copying the ideas and graphic images of the global Islamic movement. Intellectual concern and more pragmatic considerations influence the local appropriation of global ideas (Schlichte 2009), which are assessable by global educational networks or through the media or chat rooms in the Internet. However, as Abdulloh’s testimony of a locally defined Islam shows, they are selectively chosen, interpreted and convincingly communicated in vernacular languages through personal networks. The same counts for the idea of jihad. Abdulloh, Ding and others emphasize that only the local ulama can judge the status of jihad, because, according to Abdulloh,

“ulama from the heart of the Islamic world know less about our national history and our suffering. We know best.” Abdulloh also stressed that he would respect a fatwa from the Middle East, indeed in his attempt to prove to me that his fight is really a “religious war”. He referred me to a homepage on which apparently 120 Islamic scholars from around the world signed a fatwa labelling the fight for liberation in Southern Thailand a jihad. Yet it was only Patani Malay Islamic scholars, who, in his view, could righteously make such valid judgement. However, Abdulloh would not reveal the name of those who he considered to have the corresponding authority.

The idea of a global Islamic holy war had significant influence on his definition of the enemy. According to Abdulloh the aim of this jihad is to create a “true Islamic society”, or better, an Islamic state through political action, which

“[...] has to be violent, because this aim can never be negotiated with the Thais; just as peace cannot be achieved with the Israelis or the Americans. Thais say that they are Buddhist, but they are actually not much different from Americans or Israelis in the way they oppress Muslims. Their religion is very weak and can be cruel, too. For me America is also the enemy, but our leadership says, we are not yet ready to make America our enemy.”

Certain bookstores in Pattani city, to which Abdulloh went regularly, offer Thai and Malay translations of anti-Jewish and anti-American literature from the Middle East, which in turn influence his justifications of violence. He likes to read, for example, the works of Yusuf Al-Qardawi, a well-known Egyptian Islamic scholar, who legitimizes suicide attacks against Israel, including on Jewish women and children, who are deemed unworthy of being protected. During one interview Abdulloh showed me a book of Al-Qardawi’s and attempted to convince me that the Jewish-American system also dominates Thai politics. One argument was that Jews in Bangkok had a great influence on politicians in Bangkok, indicated by the fact that the Thai government sent soldiers to Iraq. Besides, Abdulloh argued, the Thais treated the Muslims in the South so bad, because they are inspired by their anti-Muslim allies to do so.

With regard to possible “suicide bombings” by Malay insurgents, Abdulloh pointed out that istishad (martyrdom in the service of God) represents the highest level of jihad proscribed in the Koran. In fact BRN-Coordinate is currently training dozens of suicide bombers in Indonesia, supposedly with the support of Jemaah Islamiyah, one of Southeast Asia’s most notorious terrorist groups. According to Abdulloh these BRN-Coordinate suicide bombers would come and carry out the missions in Bangkok, once the Thai king was dead: “Such bombings against civilians are not done because we are bloodthirsty or we hate Buddhists as such, but they are a necessary means to bring the jihad to an end.” In another interview Abdulloh exclaimed to me that, because Buddhists in Bangkok support the occupation of the Islamic land Patani, they must carry the full consequences of their decision, thus justifying attacks outside the three

provinces.

Yet such local appropriations of global ideas do not come without dispute, even within individual organisations. Abdulloh as well as a BRN-Coordinate Imam claim that there were conflicts among the group's ulama regarding the role of religion and the legitimate use of violence. A number of important clerics are said to have laid down their active membership in BRN-Coordinate after 2004, since they did not agree that the insurgency was a jihad, because, as they argued, the Thai state did not systematically persecute Muslims nor forbid the practice of Islam in the South. Abdulloh commented that the fear of being persecuted by the government or the "manipulation of Islam" by the Thai government through state-sponsored Islamic institutions like the Provincial Islamic Councils might also have played a role in these defections: "Most Imam may secretly be on our side, but they don't dare to speak out and declare that our fight is a jihad. This is because they fear government spies among the attendants of the Friday prayers." According to Abdulloh at the time of the interview, opinions on the use of violence among the BRN-Coordinate ulama were divided: there were those, who secretly opposed the practice of issuing a fatwa that allows for the killings of Buddhist civilians and who specifically opposed the killings of woman, children and the elderly. They argued that the armed wing should kill only Thai officials. Abdulloh, however, did not side with this faction, because according to his understanding of the Koran the extraordinary state of the holy war allows for the killing of all infidels, who are associated with "the enemy", i.e. Siam, albeit they are not as directly involved in the suppression of Muslims as government officials are. In other words, he understands the religious precepts as sanctifying violence and the destruction of the religious enemy.

4.2.3. Hama: the strategist and nationalist

Hama, 37 years old, was raised the son of two rubber farmers in Patani province. Though his family had never lost a family member through government forces, his father was a staunch Patani nationalist. Hama remembers coming home after learning some Thai language at elementary school and, proud of his new knowledge, greeted his mother in Thai. His father, who was also present in the room, immediately turned to his son and told him in clear local Malay to "never speak a word of Thai in this house again." Hama and his sister were even told to leave the Thai schoolbooks in a box in the backyard – everything "Thai" was to be excluded from the house:

"Both my parents were not so keen about religion as on local nationalism. Of course, my father and I went to the mosque, but Islam was never a topic we talked about. When we talked about politics it was rather from a Patani perspective. He often mentioned that this land did not belong to Thailand and that the Thais would, one day, have to give it back to its righteous owners. But he never mentioned jihad or anything in that direction. It was very common in our village to have disdain for anything Thai. Our neighbours, too, never sent their

children to Thai schools, or to study in Bangkok; all are simple peasants, who usually don't like going to the cities. Also, the village was very proud of their sons, who fought against the Thais earlier."

Besides his father, it was mostly his grandfather and the local Imam, who taught Hama, at a very young age, about "the golden age of Patani independence" and the eventual shameful loss of it. Later Hama learned that the Imam was a member of BRN. Yet although Hama heard all the stories about the painful submission to the Siamese kingdom, his direct contact with "the enemy" was actually very restricted. Except from his time at the Thai elementary school and when he needed an identity card, Hama had almost no contact with government officials and thus, he admittedly never had a bad experience. However, despite not having problems with Thai officials personally, he insisted to me that he was totally aware of the thuggish nature of the Thai rule over the Malays. His trajectory towards BRN-Coordinate was set furthermore, when his father sent him to a rather small secondary Private Islamic School, whose director, (which the father already knew), was also a Patani nationalist: "My father did not want me to get a job in the bureaucracy or in a Chinese-owned company."

His nationalist education, which became, according to Hama's own account, the prime motive for becoming a member of BRN-Coordinate, continued during his secondary schooling, where his teachers advised Hama to read specific books on Patani history such as biography of Haji Sulong. Being a diligent student he read as many as he could, and eventually he knew more about Patani history than his father. Moreover, his teacher also taught him about the religious necessity of the jihad. For Hama, himself, however, the latter aspect of the struggle was never as interesting as the nationalist dimension, which for him meant the duty to recover the land of his forefathers.

Hama is a typical example of an insurgent joining the fight within the context of the discipleship of religious schools (Sageman 2004). In the mid 1990s, when he was around 15 or 16 years old, his teacher asked him in a confidential talk after class, if Hama was willing to "go a step further". Hama was not really sure what this meant, but he had a rough idea that this had something to do with joining "the movement", although the teacher never mentioned the name of an organisation or any other details. Hama was proud to be asked, as there were rumours in the schools that only the best and brightest students would be invited to join the movement and Hama was unaware of any other pupil in his class being invited. The teacher had obviously invited only very few pupils, most of them were in higher classes. Moreover, for him it was the logical conclusion of his pride of being "Patani Malay" and an opportunity to do something for his nation, although, at that moment it was not clear to him, what this involvement would mean. So eventually he came back to his teacher a few days later and agreed to join, as he thought that this would be in the spirit of his father. However, as Hama claims, he did not ask his father before making the decision, because the teacher had asked him not to consult anyone, though he gave him a few days for the answer.

After taking his vow of fidelity, Hama's teacher and other older BRN-Coordinate members, introduced him and other recruits, to BRN-Coordinate:

“At the school we regularly studied after the usual lessons and also on weekends. At the beginning it was not really clear to us, what we could expect from the group and what they expected from us, but then, after a few weeks, it became clearer. At the beginning we only had to meet and study about Patani history, religion etc. At that time Coordinate did not yet start to mobilise people systematically, as we would do later. Most people were recruited at schools back then, just like I was.”

Initially, involvement meant studying the group's ideology as well as reducing the newcomer's uncertainty by telling them what to do. Hama was to experience the totalizing requirements of the group: “We were asked to give up any non-Muslim friends. For me this was no problem, as I only had one Buddhist friend from primary school. One of my BRN-Coordinate brothers had more difficulties, because this meant giving up his best friend, who was Buddhist.” During the following months, Hama remembers that a couple of new recruits simply left the training, arguing that they would have to take care of their families or giving other excuses.

Hama's superiors demanded more commitment from him than from other recruits, and Hama slowly realized that he was being prepared for a future leadership position within the organisation, when, around 1996, BRN-Coordinate superiors asked him to go to “study” in Malaysia. The superior would not offer Hama a scholarship, but BRN-Coordinate members in Malaysia provided him with a part-time job and free housing in support:

“When I finally got there, a man waited for me: a guy from Patani who had studied in Malaysia and had great knowledge in military affairs and politics. We met regularly in the evenings and in the term break. I had to learn and memorize. I didn't know why I had to learn all this. It was all too theoretical. They told us not to ask much and that this knowledge was only given to a small elite.”

Whereas a dozen or more people attended his previous “special lessons” at school in Pattani, Hama was now studying in a small circle of only three people. His studies, which later turned out to be based on an Indonesian insurgency manual, spanned a time of three years in total and comprised different subject areas such as geography, logistics as well as the psychology and techniques of indoctrination. With such a long period of study, Hama increasingly felt bored about the lectures and began to question the sense of his involvement: “It wasn't clear to me why I should learn all that. In the same amount of time I could have concentrated on my professional career or made some money in order to raise a family.” However, Hama decided not to quit, since that would have been a disappointment for his teacher and everybody else in the group who had put so much time and effort into him. Without them, perhaps, he would not even have had the chance to study in Malaysia. In time, however, these doubts about his involvement

disappeared as his newly acquired skills were put to the test: On his return from Malaysia Hama was made responsible for building up BRN-Coordinate in two districts:

“To ease the job at the beginning the local Ajak-committee chiefs prepared the audiences for me, while later I did it myself. And then I saw that the things that I learned in Malaysia about psychology and recruitment really worked! People indeed began to participate and I understood why I had to learn all the lessons in the first place! It’s easier than you might think. You just have to choose the right topic for the right people. When I talk to normal people in the mosque in Narathiwat, I just began talking about some general topic that might interest them – something like justice (keadilan). I start like this: ‘When someone does something to the Buddhists, then the state investigates, but when a Malay is killed nothing happens.’ Then people begin to listen. Generally, the longer the time lasted, the easier recruitment was. I became better, but that’s not all, because the more villages you recruit in one area, the easier it gets. People know others in surrounding villages. You just have to move from place to place depending on where we got members. Finally you can report that you have members in almost all Malay villages.”

When asked if it was hard to convince young recruits of the necessity to use force, Hama answered that he regarded armed attacks against the “Thai occupiers” as well as violence against civilians (both among Buddhists and Muslims) as an integral part of the current struggle: “You have to understand that we cannot defeat the Thais with tanks or rockets, therefore we must turn to other means. But once we win, everybody will see that they (i.e. the civilians, S.H) were cruel, but necessary victims. It’s something that is done in our nation’s will.” When it came to justifying the violent struggle as a whole, Hama refrained from making references to the Koran, though he saw the use of violence as legitimated by the Koran. But more important in his view was:

“[...] that if you look at the history of nations, you will see that almost all came into being through war. Look at the independence of the USA from Great Britain. This is the same with Patani independence. Why doesn’t our nation have the right to use violence? Most kids understand my argument.”

Despite this, Hama’s motivation became different from ordinary rank-and-file members as he climbed up the BRN-Coordinate’s hierarchy. Although Hama stressed that a good recruiter never takes an arrogant attitude towards the normal population, he considered himself as part of an insurgent elite within BRN-Coordinate. And indeed at least at the provincial level he was a key architect since the late 1990s. Driving through one of the districts for which Hama was responsible, he pointed to different villages and remarked to me: “See, this is all my work. I created this.” What Hama obviously saw, was the otherwise invisible network of BRN-Coordinate members and supporters which he himself had created.

To establish a cover identity for his recruitment work, Hama worked as a teacher at a

Private Religious School in each district, which allowed him to commute between the areas without arousing suspicion. He was able to recruit local pupils and, through them, build up a network to their surrounding home villages. Consequently, Hama could recruit youngsters for the military wing and Ajak-committee members at the same time. This network of supporters not only allowed Hama, so he claims, to infiltrate almost all villages in both districts. His success finally turned against him when early after the start of the insurgency in 2004, police forces arrested the different members Hama had recruited, leading police interrogators to Hama. Consequently, the police issued an arrest warrant against him. Consequently Hama had to cease his activities and flee into the jungles of the Malaysian-Thai borderland where he hid for approximately two years.

BRN-Coordinate invested a lot of time into Hama's training. This is because the group had too often experienced painful losses of qualified personnel, due to marriage and preoccupation with the responsibilities of family life. Thus BRN-Coordinate leaders even proposed Hama a woman for marriage, herself having an insurgent background, thus not undermining Hama's work. After he had to escape to the jungle his wife visited him from time to time providing him with food and other essentials for his refuge in the mountains. Less frequently, he went to see her and his two children in their home village at night. In addition, Hama's father-in-law was not mad at him for not being able to provide a living for her daughter. On the contrary, the father-in-law, a rubber peasant and stockbreeder, showed sympathy for Hama's fate and was willing to provide economically for his daughter and grandchildren in Hama's absence.

4.3. Demarcating motivations

All three cases highlight the initial openness towards involvement in the insurgency. On the one hand, we find the highly contradictory case of Ding, who was neither pious nor politically interested, but who joined initially because the organisation seemed to offer him a profane excitement in a "second life" as an underground fighter. It was only afterwards that the group offered him an ideological repertoire that justified his involvement in violent acts. Interviews with other insurgent suspects seemed to indicate that others had similar initial motives. Usually we tend to forget that young men especially are "prone to perceiving boredom almost as a physical stress" (Elwert 2003: 279; see, also, Moore 1978) and that here the "kick" offered by, for instance, an armed organisation, can constitute a rather profane motive to participate. Here, a similarity can be drawn to the way in which experimenting with drugs can ease the physical suffering caused by boredom.

Abdulloh, on the other hand, was fascinated by the idea of jihad and considered himself to be fulfilling Allah's will here on earth. Hama's decision to join was, in his own view, the fulfilment of nationalist aspirations, instilled by his father from an early age

onwards. Moreover, he was proud to be chosen by his teacher to be a member of an exclusive club. Again, the case illustrates that whereas other high-commitment armed groups that have a strong foundation in local communities can draw on the “everybody was joining”-principle, BRN-Coordinate uses the appeal of a secret community of “the chosen ones” to which only selected people have access.

This melange of motives makes it hard to reduce involvement in the insurgency to one main motive. The case of Ding shows that although recruitment agents may be instructed to select candidates who show characteristics such as “piety, impressionability and agility” (ICG 2005: 26), candidates may not necessarily fulfil these characteristics. Common to all however, is that their expectations cannot be fulfilled in the current political context. In the face of far-ranging goals, the democratisation and decentralisation of Thailand’s political system, which has been hijacked by (business) elites (Arghiros 2001), has very little integrative capacity, as both Malay Muslim politicians and even most of the Islamic clergy are considered an obstacle to a good life in the region.

All three grew up in mono-ethnic Malay villages, but, interestingly, they come from both loyalist and separatist communities among the Malay Muslims in Southern Thailand (Suhrke 1977). Whereas Abdulloh and Hama told me that they had no Buddhist friends after leaving primary school, Ding continued to have close relations with Buddhists in Hat Yai. The case of Ding proves that it was neither natural for his friends in the village, nor his family, to be “anti-Thai” or to play an active part in the insurgency. Indeed a majority of his fellow villagers considered Thai rule as legitimate and cooperated with Buddhist officials - an attitude that is also reflected in the pragmatic practices among his friends and neighbours who, unbounded by any localism, studied and took jobs outside of the three provinces. In Hama’s village, anti-Thai attitudes appeared to be more widespread and the villagers, or his family at least, were proud of his involvement in “the movement” (Hama claimed to have never told his family the name of the group). This impression was confirmed to me by two recruiters and one Ajak-committee chief who reported that there were some Malay villages in the three provinces, in which they could never really establish a full Ajak-committee, because in these villages Malays seem to be more “Thai-oriented”. Yet, even in villages infiltrated by BRN-Coordinate, there are people who oppose the insurgency (see chapter 5).

Did state suppression play a role in their decisions to join the insurgency? For the civil war in El Salvador, Dickson-Gómez (2009), for example, tried to show how the traumatic experiences of children who lost family members in assassinations by government forces led to their involvement in the anti-government guerrilla campaign. In contrast to the female BRN-Coordinate member mentioned above, notably, none of them had personal traumatic experiences either with Buddhist officials or with

Buddhists civilians, though all of them had heard stories of maltreatment and extrajudicial killing of Malays by Buddhist officials before they joined BRN-Coordinate. Hence direct state harassment cannot be regarded as a direct cause for involvement, at least in the three cases discussed here. However, images and memories of state oppression provided some of the context within which Hama's and Abdulloh's increasing involvement was actualized. Hama, Abdulloh and other insurgents, who joined BRN-Coordinate before the events in Tak Bai and Kru Se in 2004, emphasised that the killings of Malays reconfirmed their allegiance to the group.

With regard to motives the cases also indicate that these are not static systems (e.g. determined by pathology, political repression or social structure) and that they can change over time, a process that may be important in understanding why insurgents uphold the momentum of involvement beyond the initial motives to participate, enabling insurgents to overcome fear or times where they doubt their engagement, as Hama did during his studies in Malaysia. Part of the answer is the subjectivating mechanisms, which were described in the last chapter. In addition, Ding hinted at the fact that once an insurgent becomes involved in violent acts, especially as a member of the military wing, he can get involved in an ensuing logic of revenge and counter-revenge, of frenzy and escape from the police or military and attacking them, which in turn traps him within the system of violence. This is a typical example of how violent conflict creates its own motives, contributing to the reproduction of the armed group's function.

With the multiplicity of functions and positions that armed groups offer come also distinctive "psychological rewards": although the involvement in the political wing often does not comprise active participation in violence, it can generate its own motives, as illustrated by Hama who initially doubted the purpose of memorizing insurgency skills, but later gave positive feedback regarding his successful recruitment efforts, thus renewing the momentum of his involvement. Indeed, Hama showed a tendency to consider the members of the group's armed wing as "brainless henchmen", whereas he considered himself "the strategic head" behind the organisation of the widespread violent campaign. Without his recruitment efforts, as well as that of his fellow leaders in the political wing, the group could have only drawn a few members and its capabilities would have covered no more than the ability to "throw bombs here and there, from time to time like a headless chicken." Military commanders, on their part, had a tendency to view their activities as the constitutive activity of BRN-Coordinate, as one such commander once commented on the meaning of his task: the group would "mean nothing without the ability to use violence and instil fear. Everybody just sits around a table drinking tea and discussing how good merdeka would be, but none of them dares to take a gun in his hand. All they do is talk." Such contradictory perceptions and values do not necessarily undermine the spirit or coordination of the armed group. Rather, on

the contrary, it is crucial for sustaining the perceived attractiveness of functionally different positions within such a complex armed group, though such distinctive sets of values can be found even in small terrorist groups (Horgan 2008).

4.4. Charismatic mobilization

Whereas Weinstein's abovementioned distinction between activist and opportunist rebellions is a useful distinction, his rationalist approach towards armed groups fails to notice that mobilization through identity seems particularly powerful, when it is connected to a charismatic idea. The stories of Abdulloh and Hama at least illustrate the mobilizing power of ideas such as national independence or a holy war. In such charismatic situations the entire state and the social structure, which were hitherto taken for granted, are now seen as subject to (violent) change, or an apocalypse. Without such a strong belief in the possibility of change, the perpetrators of violence are rather low-commitment guerrilla armies or bands of criminals. A "charismatic situation" does not give birth to a whole new set of values, but rather a shift in their relative position as a result of a particular framework placed around events and power structures (Elwert 2003). What used to be a mere wish or hope, such as Hama's father's idea of independence, now turns into the sphere of the possible. For external observers such charismatic ideas often appear bizarre, contradictory or prone to fail. But such objection typically does nothing more than to strengthen the belief of its adherents and nourish their contempt towards outsiders (which, in Southern Thailand, includes those Malays, who are said to be on the enemy's side). One's own belief in the grand idea is stylized as the only true form of existence, the only truth.

Ideologically, examples of other social movement organisations such as GAM in Aceh have shown how charismatic beliefs can easily combine formally contradictory elements such as the mesmerising appeal of nationalist heritage with the more recent charismatic power of the jihad (Aspinall 2009). Indeed, secular political programmes, such as nationalism, can have religious dimensions. And as Koselleck et al. (2006) point out, even as ideologies switch and older layers of meaning lose their (charismatic) appeal, they are never totally destroyed and replaced by newer ones, but rather, older layers of meanings continue to exist. Over time the idea of the nation-state has shown the greatest continuity amongst the global tides of political ideas such as decolonisation, socialism, democracy or, in the case of BRN-Coordinate members, NASOSI. Even the cultural turn and neo-liberalism have not led to a replacement of ideas of national self-determination among armed groups (Schlichte 2009).

Structurally, charisma also enables new kinds of sociability such as the modus of loose coupling that was mentioned earlier. People or communities who are otherwise fragmented by personal feuds, patronage or individualism, are able to cooperate through the belief in their collective agency in what Weber calls 'charismatic communities'

(Gemeinschaft) (Weber 1978: 243). For armed groups charisma has a threefold function: First, as shown by the current use of the term jihad, it legitimises the use of violence (Schlichte 2009). Second, charisma develops an important mobilising force and, third, enables a degree of cohesion that cannot be explained by the existing social structure (Elwert 1999). Internationally, ideas like socialism or jihad are needed to attract external support.

The appeal of charisma is intrinsically based on the revelation of some higher truth, a framework that, for a moment in time, helps to interpret and make sense of all social ills and offers the promise of a better life. In other words, the legitimacy of charisma lies in its relation to transcendental forces. BRN-Coordinate, for example, claims that the establishment of an Islamic state of Patani is the fulfilment of God's will on earth. To put it in the words of one of the group's manuals: "We took God's task of freeing Patani from occupation; politically, economically and culturally [...]. We took God's given burden of laying down the religious law within national borders." The claim of contact with the divine is made to sound even more plausible among the internal audience, if it is expressed by religious experts such as ustadz, but it is also manifested in the (initiation) rituals of the group as was mentioned above.

Although there is an analytical distinction between organised bureaucratic routines and charisma, there is no empirical dichotomy between them (Eisenstadt 1995). Revolutionary armed groups are a good case in point. While they can start off with a loosely organised movement with the aim of destructing institutions and existing routines, they, facing the exigencies of organisation under violent conditions, have a predisposition towards transforming into army-like bureaucracies, to assure some continuity and military capacity. Two processes usually lead to the decline of charisma: first, following Weber, bureaucratisation or traditionalisation imply hierarchisation, formalization and hence foster a decrease of charisma, which exists only in *statu nascendi* (Weber 1978: 246). Routinized practices and material interest in the organisation come to the fore and end the transitory, fluid, and extraordinary nature of charismatic movements. Second, the charismatic appeal of armed groups is in their character of promise (Schlichte 2009). If they are not ruling, they can promise anything. If the prophecy that was proclaimed (e.g. a socialist paradise) eventually fails to emerge, charismatic ideas lose their appeal quickly (Festinger et. al 1990).

Yet this is not the end of the story. Even in routine organisations charismatic mobilization can re-emerge (Elwert 1999). The appropriation of new charismatic ideas, which are, for example, like the idea of the jihad, produced in transnational contexts, opens a new opportunity for armed groups like BRN-Coordinate to regain charismatic momentum that was lost (if it ever existed). In this sense, waves of doctrines like the Maoist conceptions mentioned earlier can foster the emergence of new cycles of armed

resistance.³⁵

4.5. Can we win? “Insurgency as a simulacrum”

One of the features of the BRN-Coordinate insurgent milieu is that all information is bent and manipulated into a form that supports the charismatic idea of an independent Islamic state of Patani. Information that is contradictory is either denied or ignored. Seemingly meaningless information is inflated, even if it is only slightly in tune with the group’s ideology. We know that in highly unequal systems of domination such as slave-owner societies or colonial systems, subordinate groups develop fantasies that turn around the terms of domination. Colonized people in Africa, for example, dreamt of a time in which they, the black subordinates, become white rulers and the white rulers become the black subordinates. In early 1930s a Papua New Guinean prophet called Marafi proclaimed a new age in which an inversed Christianity would soon arise to rule the world. In Marafi’s version of Christianity the devil would be the new God; potatoes would grow from the trees; fish would come to populate the dry land, whereas land animals would return to the sea. Anthropologists referred to this perception as the so-called upside-down world (“Verkehrte Welt”) syndrome, which is typical for radical charismatic milieus (Mühlmann 1964).

Among insurgents, all share a comparable disregard for the military preponderance of the Thai state in Southern Thailand and its chances of winning the war. For all of its weaknesses at the local level, the basic state infrastructure and numerical strength of Thailand’s security forces coupled with the weakness of BRN-Coordinate renders an insurgency a hopeless endeavour, at least if the strengths of both sides are compared on paper. But with regard to the emic views of the insurgents, what matters more is the perception of opportunity and the re-evaluation of forces on different grounds. This is nothing new in warfare: Clausewitz stressed the will to triumph as a key factor in war and Napoleon once noted that “The moral is to the physical as three to one.” (Smith 2008: 244). The German philosopher Popitz (1992) stressed that wars and collective violence are times of fantasy and fear. Ideas become detached from reality and get a life of their own. The Americans faced a comparable phenomenon in the Vietnam War: How does one defeat a people who do not acknowledge defeat (Münkler 1992)?

What is common in insurgents in Southern Thailand is the understatement of the enemy’s power. Ding, for instance, stressed that although “the Thais have more soldiers than we do, they are not a very effective force, because they lack the morale.” For him as for many others, Thai soldiers are corrupt and militarily weak, because they lack a proper commitment to defend the South, as Hama explains: “They only come to the

³⁵ This also explains why armed groups can switch their identity. However, the danger persists that they “result in sterile dogmas, largely ignored by the target population” (Schlichte 2009: 107). This is especially the case, when local elites with particular material interests or special educational skills that set them apart from the normal population, adopt such ideas. The success of charismatic ideas then depends on the elite’s ability to translate them into the vernacular language.

South, because they want the top up they receive. Look where the soldiers go on the weekend: they are drunk and visit prostitutes.” Whereas in other instances it is acknowledged that many Thais, especially officials are often nationalistic in orientation (otherwise they would not want to destroy Patani culture), the Thai armed forces are denied the capacity to act on moral grounds, if it comes to war.

Vice versa, insurgents exaggerate their own strength. Hama understands the battle in Southern Thailand, (similarly to Clausewitz), as a clash of wills. For him it is the “natural determination of any people to govern themselves freely” that underlies the militant struggle and provides for the stronger and longer lasting will of the insurgents although he admits that a military assessment of the situation might speak in favour of the “Siamese side”. Similarly, Ding concludes that it is the willingness to kill and to die for an independent Islamic nation that counts, while the enemy lacks such determination and discipline on the battlefield. Again, here we can find different nuances in the explanation of the superior will of the “Patani people”. For Abdulloh it is again the dichotomy between worldly goals and transcendental objectives that provides for the high morale of BRN-Coordinate: “Islam teaches us to fight for God, but the officials and soldiers from Bangkok and the Northeast of Thailand only come for money and positions. If an officer of the army serves here, he will rise faster in the army. In the end those who fight with Allah will win and the Godless people will loose.” Abdulloh is convinced that this determination to achieve higher goals is reflected in the wisdom of the group’s leaders and the organisational superiority of BRN-Coordinate as well.

“We have a million ways to win and we can wait a million years. No matter how long it takes in the end we will win!”, exclaimed Hama. Yet there are also concrete scenarios of victory envisioned: Ding and Abdulloh, for instance, have the idea that Thailand is comparable to a giant on feet of clay and that the mujaheddin are gradually destroying its foundation through constant and sustained attacks. A specially awaited point of time is the eventual death of Thailand’s current king, on which much of Thailand’s apparent ability to unite the country depends. Once the king passes away, Abdulloh stresses, “other parts of the country like the Northeast will demand more autonomy and the Cambodians will attack Thailand to regain territories that the Siamese have stolen from them.”

Exaggeration of one’s strength can also concern the number of fighters. On a trip through Pattani, Ding pointed at a Malay street vendor (which can be found everywhere) and remarked to me: “He looks like a simple man, but maybe he is a mujaheddin, who fought in Afghanistan. All these people will soon emerge from their hiding and rise to free us from Siamese rule.” Hama summarized this upside-down world view in the following words “As a fighter you have to know one thing: what seems to be real, is not, and what seems to be unreal, is reality. Our superiors say that what is impossible is actually possible.”

Such a messianic worldview, in its simplicity, seems raw and naïve. And to outsiders of the group such blunt eschatology seems too reductive, and too simplifying to be convincing. But for many insurgents it exerts a fascinating charismatic power over them. Indeed even local Malays that are sympathetic to the revolt feel disturbed by the bigotry of these overreaching beliefs about the final victory against the Thais. To me as well, such fantasies sometimes seemed to resemble a breakdown of the reasoning powers of otherwise more or less rational individuals, especially in the case of Hama who at other times surprised me with his strategic genius. Yet the charismatic appeal of these views and their transmitters might just lie in their denial of resistance and factual constraint (Mühlmann 1964). Ideas such as a ‘holy war’ or an independent Islamic state of Patani cannot be measured against realities. The result is not only a narrowing of insurgent and incumbent forces in the eyes of the members, but an actual turn-around of the balance of power that defies rational judgement. Such perceptions seem to become “models of the real without origin or reality: a hyper-real” (Baudrillard 1988: 166). As the reference to reality becomes obsolete, these images of strength can be reproduced without any limit. Thus, adapting Baudrillard’s terms with a degree of ferocity we can speak of “insurgency as a simulacrum”.

4.6. Violence and the authoritarian personality

When searching for the underlying background against which the use of violence can be constructed as a legitimate means, or even as an end in itself, some experts look to psychological pathologies as a factor among the producers of violence (such as trauma, paranoia or pathological hatred). Current research, however, indicates that it is highly unlikely that terrorists, for example, suffer from psychopathologies (McCauley 2001). Yet it is fruitful to have an understanding of the milieus in Southern Thailand that are receptive to BRN-Coordinate’s luring call for violence.

Elias (1997), for example, argues in his study of the “process of civilization” that the evolution of modern states is accompanied by a process of pacification, i.e. the reduction and control over internal violence through the monopolization of legitimate violence by the state, and the evolution of personality in the sense of self-control with regards to violence. This in turn allows co-existence of diversities in terms of ethnicity, religion or political opinion because controversies and conflicts can be coped with through political compromise based on peaceful bargaining. Pacification can be achieved to some degree by repressive and authoritative means of the state, which gives rise to “development authoritarianism”. If development is understood in the sense of Sen as “freedom” (in political as well as economic terms) a self-controlled personality is crucial. Thus, the formation of a “liberal” or “democratic” personality has to accompany political development processes. Such a process of personality formation is closely connected to changes of social structures namely power relations, their legitimisation, culturally framed political ideologies and how these are instrumentalized.

Lerner (1971) notes that development requires empathy in the sense that people are able to understand how persons in different positions perceive their world.³⁶ This implies that opposing positions and worldviews can be considered as legitimate and relevant and thus enter into public discourses. Such an “empathetic” personality contrasts with a personality defined within and by relations of patronage, i.e. strong and personalized power-relations, as much as an authoritarian personality is characterized by disregard of opposing views, ideas, minorities etc.

Through changes in social structures, old orders are dissolved and new ones are emerging. However, personalities are not adapting to the new circumstances. One reason is that the state itself is unable to establish a monopoly of force or to legitimate itself, and that the public sphere from where a consensus may emerge is not arising. As a result, instead of empathy, resentment rises. Power differentials are not “informalizing” and opening discourses, but rather, new ideological means are devised to maintain them. Hence development can strengthen authoritarian personalities or an orientation towards patronage. As a result, the control over violence is in itself based on violence – either on the structural violence of a repressive state or on the random violence of diverse groups. The increased level of violence makes the further development of personality even more complicated.

The situation in Southern Thailand can be cited as an example of such a discrepancy. Neither has the state monopoly of violence been well established, nor has a common public sphere emerged which could define a consensus or common good. In contrast, social and cultural differences have been enforced not the least because the elites themselves are split into different factions. Consequently, the degree of social cohesion is low, and because the administration itself is to a large degree involved in local struggles between elite factions, it could not evolve as a neutral force for integration (interview Ahmad Somboon Bualuang, Patani, September 26, 2007).

A strong authoritarian orientation is obvious among Malay Muslims in Southern Thailand, where the orientation towards a courageous leader, who dares to do the necessary things to solve problems rather than talk about them, is widely shared. These leaders or patrons should be followed, as they provide solutions. Interestingly, against popular belief with regard to the south, religion is important, but this does not mean that religious leaders are preferred. Milieus like religious schools or Islamist mosques, where authoritarian orientations prevail among members of the Malay Muslim middle class provide a partially receptive milieu for violence in which recruitment by

³⁶ Empathy in this sense has three implications (Lerner 1971): First, it enables humans to discuss and define a “common good” that makes sense for all, in contrast to abstract ideas and ideologies that have only little real concern for everyday life. Second, every person is aware of his/her own position. In other words, the decision making with regards to own interests and aspirations comes from a rational process open for discussion. It is not based on prejudices. This implies furthermore that the person takes him or herself as responsible for his or her own actions. Third, empathy reduces power differentials, and thus allows for more equality, at least in the sense that others are recognized as subjects.

insurgents is eased by bringing together Islamist teachers and young, risk-taking male youth.³⁷

4.7. Agency within a (not so?) totalizing group

In the last chapter, the totalising nature of BRN-Coordinate as an armed group was described. Examining the case study accounts closely, they reveal the continuing role of member's agency that can manifest itself simply in practices such as not only passivity or avoidance of assigned tasks, but also defection. For example: Ding, although he never intended to leave the organisation, successfully sustained a degree of autonomy against the totalizing tendency of BRN-Coordinate through the partial, though hidden, continuation of his self-indulgent lifestyle. Not as motivated as Hama or Abdulloh, he even avoided further involvement in the organisation by dismissing the offer to be promoted, though he was aware of the higher status this position entailed. In addition, at least parts of BRN-Coordinate's ulama denied that the insurgency was a jihad.

All these examples indicate that BRN-Coordinate's control over its members is never complete, and that, although opposition to the group may not always be openly expressed, subject positions can take these specific forms that avoid open confrontation within the group. To put it differently, the leaders of any organisation, even those as totalising as clandestine armed groups, do not have a monopoly over power, no matter how sophisticated their attempts are, and no matter how repressive their enemy or legitimate their cause is.

Power within organisations also comes from below (Crozier & Friedberg 1979; Scott 2009). These tactics of "dis-involvement" or passive forms of resistance like "faking engagement" as in the abovementioned case in Narathiwat lie somewhere between more salient exit and voice strategies (Hirschman 1981). As mentioned before, armed groups, in contrast to social movements in general, may draw on different mechanisms of subjectivation as well as on violence-generating motives, but as long as the armed group builds on high-commitment, voluntary support, it must just as non-violent social movements, provide at some point or another the goods it has promised (e.g. independence, communism). If these prophecies fail, movements fall apart rather quickly, sometimes leaving an even more violent core of activists behind.

4.8. Conclusion

This chapter intended to break up the sharp line between the collective organisation of violence and the individual experience of the insurgency, because this traditional dichotomy leaves out two essential points; namely the contingency of involvement as a social process and the way involvement is conceptualized by the subjects themselves. A

³⁷ For a general introduction to the concept of the authoritarian personality see Adorno (1999). For the connection between Islamic religiosity and authoritarian personality see, e.g., Chang-Ho 2007.

process-oriented view of involvement was proposed in order to prevent essentialising or mystifying Malay Muslim insurgents in Southern Thailand as a group of highly pious religious fanatics, an economically exploited people, or a bunch of criminals. Socioeconomic backgrounds vary, as do the insurgent's motivations for joining.

The three case studies represent three very different experiences and trajectories of involvement within the same organisation. Motives to be an insurgent ranged from simply the excitement of having access to a violent secret group (and the power associated with it) to religious nationalist motives and revenge, with the latter being an inexhaustible source of value and meaning that BRN-Coordinate members can draw on despite the obvious contradiction. However, what seems to be a common feature of BRN-Coordinate is that despite its relatively high degree of formalisation, the group can utilize a certain charismatic appeal to mobilise its members. In this charismatic context, insurgents set forth to achieve something that is considered a far-away hope in the group's environment.

Involvement in Southern Thailand's insurgency also encompasses continuous change, as the trajectories of members vary between an ever-increasing commitment and avoidance tactics by individuals. In other words, at least some members seem to be able to retain a degree of agency against the totalizing tendency of the group, countering the totalising tendency of BRN-Coordinate with all its concerns for secrecy and its attempt at upholding the momentum of involvement.

5. Making sense of violence: power and the communicative side of the insurgency

One of the most intriguing features of Southern Thailand's insurgency is the fact that rebels avoid taking credit for their violent deeds, leaving some observers to speak of a "conspiracy of silence" (Abuza 2009). In contrast to the practice of Basque or Northern Ireland separatism, no warnings are given before an attack, no identifiable demands are made in connection with the violence and no group takes responsibility. Analysing such claims of responsibility is important, because it grants access to what perpetrators demand and, partly, to what logic drives their violent behaviour. If armed groups refrain from taking responsibility, it is typically interpreted as a sign of pathological inversion or a fragmentation of armed actors, who apparently have no clear political agenda. Apparently, these groups are not interested in political mobilisation and commit acts of violence only as a purely self-referential act.

This chapter argues that although BRN-Coordinate and other insurgent groups avoid publicly taking credit for their actions, violence in the three provinces can be understood as a highly communicative act, if one moves beyond the victim-perpetrator interaction to the wider symbolic function that violence has for different local audiences. Violence itself becomes a symbol, which makes its integration into social structures possible. The communication of organised forms of violence such as inter-state wars, terrorism or insurgency is closely connected to different collectives (Douglas 1996, Leach 1965). Collectives serve as the organisers of violence, providing, for example, channels of communication, legitimacy, support for fighters, and also integrating violence into the collective. But violence can also demarcate the borders of collectives.

These collectives do not necessarily correspond with ethnic borders. Surely, not all Malays support the insurgency. Accounts of insurgency by non-supporters have been described by, for example, Askew (2009). If, however, the insurgency had no supporters beyond the insurgents themselves, it would be just a non-enduring, peripheral phenomenon in society. The aim of this chapter is not to evaluate the overall strength of support, but rather to identify popular accounts of Malay supporters and to explain how local acceptance of insurgent violence is connected to the stigmatisation of Malay Muslims in the Thai nation state, as well as to the specific forms of insurgent violence. It will be shown that BRN-Coordinate employs demonstrative violence as strategic tool and how the group attempts to actively manipulate the Malay population's reception of state as well as rebel violence. Finally, the chapter will throw light on the diverging interpretations of violence among state officials, taking leading officers of the 4th Army Area as an example, and how these interpretations influence counterinsurgency approaches.

5.1. Insurgencies and claim-taking

Revolutionary warfare in most parts of the 20th century was based on clear nationalist or socialist agenda. Its leaders assumed that in order to be successful they had to garner mass support – hence the expression of the “people’s war”. If terrorist acts were used, so went the assumption, it was only a secondary tactic to frighten opponents and capture mass attention. In this sense, at least until the 1980s, “conventional” guerrillas typically claimed responsibility for their actions and connected them with more or less clear political objectives. Therefore violent struggles were usually reflected in the semantic field of the national and international public, with all conflict actors making use of the confusing proximity of the terms “terrorist”, “freedom fighter” and “criminal” (Münkler 1992).

Similarly, Malay resistance groups in Southern Thailand and their aims were typically made public in order to be internationally recognized and possibly to garner local and international support. In 1948, for example, local leaders issued a letter to the United Nations, demanding independence of the area from Thailand (Surin 1982). Later in the 1970s and the early 1980s groups such as BRN or PULO framed their resistance publicly in terms of statehood. These organisations invented flags, uniforms, and assigned ministerial posts in a “to be” independent “Patani” cabinet and used them for communication with the outside world (interview with former PULO insurgents, October 11, 2008). Another separatist group, Barisan Nasional Pembebasan Patani (BNPP), openly lobbied along with Arab nations for the integration of Patani into Malaysia (Surin 1982).

During this period communication had additional uses for local armed groups. Taking responsibility was part of the “economics of resistance”, because the power and reputation of the different armed groups depended on their ability to exert violence and vice versa. Successful, publicly known military campaigns against the state attracted more members and increased fear among opponents. The former could then be transformed in political influence and (financial) resources with an increase of supporters. Only if these groups issued statements before or after attacks, could non-combatants credit specific groups with the acts of violence (Chen Wan Kadir interview, November 18, 2008). Taking responsibility for violence was also important in blackmailing Chinese company owners in Southern Thailand, which was, in the past, an important source of income for Malay insurgent organisations. If they were not paid “protection money” insurgents threatened businessmen with kidnapping family members or burning down factories.

Groups issued advanced warnings and left threatening letters or post-violence leaflets with their names at the scene of their attacks (e.g. on the corpses of killed state officials or at burned-down factories). Such practices served as a “first-move advantage” (Hoffman 2010). Since the members of the armed group themselves released the

information, they could easily control the flow of information. Even if only the state had a monopoly on information, it could always manipulate the content and timing of release of the information, possibly to the disadvantage of the militants. Besides, rivalling groups made it hardly possible for other groups to convincingly claim the same violent attacks for themselves. So competition between armed groups rendered communication of claims more probable.

The communicative dimension of Malay rebel violence has changed fundamentally since the beginning of the new century. No claims of responsibility are made - either before or after attacks. On the surface, attacks follow a confusing pattern (if any pattern at all). There seems to be neither a positive nor negative correlation between the number of attacks across different provinces (cf. Srisompob & McCargo 2010; ศรีสมภพ จิตร์ภิรมย์ศรี 2552). A significant increase in operations in one province does not lead to a proportional decrease of operations in other areas, which would normally be the case if forces were temporarily concentrated in one area. Moreover, in some localities arson attacks or bombings occur more regularly, whereas in other areas assaults are more common. Importantly, why do Muslims rank so high among victims? And why are very few high-ranking officers harmed while poor farmers and rank-and-file soldiers are killed regularly?

Judging from statistics alone, it is hard to believe that violence is planned and controlled to such a high degree as was earlier proposed. A pattern as to “who is fighting whom” seems hardly constructible from the statistics. Hence an array of conspiracy theories emerged among different local and national audiences. By 2007, for example, a prominent conspiracy theory claimed that violence was engineered not by politically driven insurgents, but by vested political interest groups (Askew 2007).

5.2. The politics of (non-) communication

On a global scale the changes in insurgent warfare, from the figure of the “revolutionary partisan” to the “partisan of tradition“ as mentioned earlier, apparently went hand in hand with changes in the communicative sides of violence, as more and more armed groups, networks and organisations started refraining from taking responsibility for violent attacks. Hamas or al Qaeda do not totally refrain from taking credit, but they do so on irregular occasions (Hoffman 2010). Coupled with new forms of diffuse forms of network-based Islamist terrorism elsewhere, this silence made it a great deal harder for observers to adequately assess armed groups. Under certain circumstances, this tactic can involve high costs for armed groups. The case of the LTTE in Sri Lanka shows that governments can successfully label their enemy as “terrorist”, when this label is not energetically countered in the international public.

Which factors can account for the avoidance of credit-taking, which is also reflected in Southern Thailand? Generally, this question has been little discussed by analysts.

According to Hoffman (2010) existing explanations focus on the following factors: first, the most common approaches of claim-taking argue that the propensity to claim responsibility depends on the ideological character of the armed group. Whereas conventional revolutionary political agendas turned to mass support for their long march to power, the rise of religiously motivated armed groups, especially terrorists, are said to have de-emphasized political agendas. In other words, reference to the masses is replaced by reference to God, and the justification of violence becomes a matter of interpreting holy scripts instead of reading popular opinions on the ground. Especially, the figure of the petty bourgeois, otherwise thwarted in self-realization, seems to be prone to embracing nihilism and symbols of necrophilia. According to Langman (2005) he dislikes the powerful, who are able to realize his hidden dreams of erotic love and power, and disdainfully looks down on the uneducated masses that do not deserve his attention. The result is a purely self-referential type of spectacular violence.

Second, taking a rational point of view, silence signifies that groups like BRN-Coordinate fear retaliatory measures by incumbent opponents and hence stress clandestinity as a working principle. Credit-taking is related to the state's ability to monitor and punish its population. A third position argues that variations in the competitive environment provide armed groups with incentives for claim-taking (Hoffman 2010). Empirical evidence from armed groups in the Middle East, for example, shows that the competitive context is a strong predictor of credit-taking. If multiple armed groups contest each other for resources in the same conflict theatre, claiming responsibilities to local, national and international audiences can ease access to them. By implication, the fact that armed groups refrain from claim-taking might be seen as evidence of the fact that there are few serious competitors. If true, this assumption would confirm the thesis that BRN-Coordinate has an outstanding position in Southern Thailand's insurgency, being more than just a *primus inter pares*.

5.3. Communicative dimensions of violence

Neither conceptualisations of violence, which restrict it to the physical relation between victim and perpetrator, nor an understanding that broadens it to a "structural" phenomenon (Galtung 1981) seem to be adequately equipped to answer the puzzling question of how violence and social structure are connected. Recent research suggests that the social dimension of violence can be captured through its communicative dimension (Richards 1986; Reemstma 2008). This communicative dimension has been typically overlooked for two reasons: first, as mentioned before, the literature on civil wars emphasised the determining factors of civil war over its forms. Second, violence is seen as a destroyer of social relationships (see, e.g. Arendt 1970), whereas the creative dimension of violence in the constitution of collectives is often overlooked. Luhmann (2003) argues that while the violent act itself destroys the relation between perpetrator and victim, it also creates a credible threat of further violence and hence a power

relation between the perpetrator and the audience(s) can emerge. A bullet or a car bomb that kills a person conveys a message. It tells the audience (e.g. a bystanding comrade) that he or she will be next if certain measures are not taken (e.g. stopping collaborating with the incumbent).

A purely instrumental view on communication has its limitations as well, because it assumes that the meaning of violence is clear and unambiguous (cf. Waldmann 1993). In phases where collective violence has become part of everyday life, the meaning of violence is not always self-explanatory as illustrated by the situation in the three provinces. In peaceful contexts, violence without a clear message or sender can be meaningfully reduced to unfussy vandalism or pathological behaviour, an accident or crime that can always happen, but that does not risk the certainty of everyday life. But what if collective violence is routinely committed by an “unnamed force” which has no defined receiver? Or to put it in the words of Appadurai, who comments on the 9/11 events:

“It was undertaken by a new type of agency, an agency neither interested in establishing a state, nor in the relations between states at all. But are we really dealing with a new kind of agency or are we to adjust our understanding of violence, without declaring a new paradigm?”

Appadurai 2006: 17

People that perceive such ambiguous violence naturally ask a different question: who is responsible? What is the motive of the perpetrator? Are we facing a credible threat? Can we defend ourselves as a collective or shall we simply leave a dangerous area? Shall we simply accept the risk of falling victim? These interpretations, in turn, influence the coping strategies and other reactions to violence.

Here, media systems and collective forms of perception come into play. Modernisation theory assumed that technical advances, rising educational standards, and social and geographical mobility were closely connected to the emergence of mass media, in which an undistinguished national mass shares the same information and reception of information, giving rise to a “national audience” (see, e.g. Lerner 1971). These mass audiences, it was assumed, would replace local, particular communities of communication, in which information is transmitted in face-to-face networks, often under the personal influence of “informed patrons”, opinion leaders or rumour factories. It was also supposed that descriptive information was disseminated according to professional principles (e.g. journalism). The meanings of war, terrorism and other forms of violence were to be constituted by rational discourses.

Notably, communication during phases of civil war is typically very different from communication during peaceful times (Zitelmann 2000). Perception of violence in civil wars is not solely a matter of objectivity, but rather a mix of objective facts, fears,

fantasies, and “dreams of grandeur”. In this respect, reception of violence is highly relevant. First, metaphors and images of violent oppression tell us a great deal about how individuals and groups understand the social and political worlds in which they live. Second, they can reveal deep fears, perceived threats, and past grievances that drive the conflict. Third, narratives are important because they sanction certain kinds of action and not others.

In this context it is especially “demonstrative violence” - i.e. a (intended) communicative dimension of violence that reaches beyond the perpetrator-victim-dyad - that becomes relevant. Demonstrative violence can range from a husband beating his wife in public to demonstrate his manhood, to public hanging as disciplinary measure by states,³⁸ to mass rape as a means of ethnic cleansing (Münkler 2004), to filmed beheadings of Western hostages in Afghanistan that are uploaded to the internet and are accessible to a worldwide audience. Combining demonstrative violence with local cosmologies, government death squads in Sri Lanka dumped the bodies of killed and mutilated Tamil insurgents at holy Hinduist sites in an attempt to destroy the social fabric of the Tamil society and establish the Sri Lankan state as the only legitimate order (Gledhill 1994).

As Deutsch (1972) pointed out, increasing education and access to means of communication can also strengthen particularistic groups that do not correspond to national boundaries. According to Apitzsch (2010) in Southern Thailand there are found at least two dissimilar interpretations of violence between Buddhist and Muslim communities. In this dual communicative structure demonstrative violence is used as a means of communication and also belongs to the centre of politically connoted violence. Indiscriminate attacks against Buddhist civilians, including decapitations and the burning of dead bodies, are committed on a regular basis. This is coupled with confusion about the perpetrators and causes of violence leading to a pervasive climate of fear among Buddhists in the region. At the organisational level, these atrocities are not the result of irrational actions. Rather they are a central component of BRN-Coordinate’s strategy of escalation. The simple logic here is to kill Buddhists on a regular basis and attack their symbolic order so as to drive them out of the region, then escalating the conflict in order to drive Buddhist civilians into acts of retaliation, which would eventually lead to a civil war.

In everyday conversations between Buddhists and Malay Muslims the topics of insurgency and its causes are typically avoided, especially among women, who are not considered to be involved in politics, because such talks are believed to lead to personal conflicts (Apitzsch 2010). These different perceptions are reinforced by different languages (Malay and Thai), school systems (Thai government and Islamic educational

³⁸ Before the age of “biopolitics”, state sovereignty was understood as the power to decide over life and death (Foucault 2007).

system), books, homepages and internet chat rooms (Phrae 2009). As a consequence of the lack of a local public sphere, contradictory explanations of violence are not put against each other, which otherwise would have provided opposing versions of violence, thus counterchecking the rumours (Simons 1995). Very few local Malay Muslims express their opinions publicly on national TV, radio broadcasts or in print media.

Another central element of Malay perceptions of violence that differs between communication in violent and peaceful times is the prevalence of rumours. In contrast to news, rumours cannot be falsified: their origins or sources are typically not traceable (Zitelmann 2000). The lack of information on the perpetrators, their motives and the background to the violence, both by the state and the rebels, leads to rumours in the form of “mass communication under condition of a limited public sphere” (Elwert 1991). Information is highly relevant for making sense of and coping with violent situations that are marked by unpredictability. The lack of reliable information is hence replaced by rumours, which are built on plausibility structures that identify responsibility and causalities of violence based on existing value systems, cognitive structures and past experiences (Zitelman 2000). Rumours typically convey a limited amount of details and, importantly, they leave out contradictory information.

5.4. Stigmatization and interpretations of violence

In the three provinces local Malays (as well as Buddhists) had to interpret the outbreak of violence in 2004. However, this demand for information has not been met with reliable information. Perpetrators remain in the dark and news coverage only reports on the consequences of violence, whilst displaying gruesome pictures of victims. Although there is only inconsistent and often contradictory information on the perpetrators and the motives of rebels, these speculations are typically put into a coherent order that corresponds to past experiences and is connected to existing value systems. In other words, to understand popular perceptions of violence among Malays we have to understand that they are related to social structures. These views are partly the result of social structures, but they can also affect structures by influencing people’s behaviour (e.g. through the use of demonstrative violence in a rebellion).

In his studies on the “established” and the “outsiders” Elias has shown how high power differentials between interdependent social groups are reflected in and reproduced by stigmatisation (Elias & Scotson 1993). While power differentials can be based on different types of power, they tend, if they are of a long-term nature, to be reflected in the morally loaded images that both groups have of themselves and the other in terms of superiority and inferiority. The more powerful group considers itself not only as powerful, but also to be “better humans” and morally superior to the weaker group (Elias & Scotson 1993). On the one hand, an established group tends to ascribe the

positive characteristics of its best members as the characteristics of the group as whole, while the bad characteristics of its worst members are ignored in the self-reflection of the group. On the other hand, it refers to the outsider group only in terms of the negative characteristics of the worst members of the outsider's group.

What is also typical for such figurations is that the outsider group embraces these stigmatisations and thus blames itself and its weaker qualities, rather than the power differentials, for its inferior position (Elias & Scotson 1993). Hereby another, more symbolic, dimension of rule is established that reproduces the original power differentials as the "internalisation" of the social structure further weakens the outsider group (e.g. colonial mind). Ideologically, stigmatisation can be legitimised by ethnic, racial or cultural differences, or simply by the time when a group dominates the power position (e.g. the old, aristocratic rich vs. the nouveau riche).

In his theory of "Anerkennung", or recognition, Honneth (1994) argues that a central aspect of stigmatisation in all systems of domination is the denial of recognition. Honneth assumes that humans are motivated by struggles for recognition. In this regard he distinguishes emotional acceptance, legal acceptance and solidarity as three types of acceptance. All three make up an individual's psychological, legal and social integrity, but, reversely, they are also related to different forms of neglect. Most basic is the neglect of physical integrity, by which a person is devoid of control over his own body. This is the case with the illegitimate use of state violence against citizens. This physical destruction hence not only victimizes the body of an individual, but also involves the complete destruction of his self-esteem. We can also speak of neglect if an individual or a group feels structurally excluded from certain rights in a society, or from the solidarity of a nation's majority. All of these kinds of neglect, which are institutionalized in stigmatization, class or ethnic structures of society, and organised repression, produce shame as the enduring quality of social relations.

The rule of Thailand's bureaucratic polity is a case in point. As mentioned above, ever since the incorporation of the region into the Thai state, the Malay-speaking people of Patani felt treated as inferior and second-class citizens (Che Man 1990). The feeling of alienation was aggravated by poverty, violations of human rights and the chauvinistic behaviour of the Thai government. Similar to the Southern Philippines chauvinistic national policies, this had the unintended effect of producing the imagination of a shared Malay culture among a heterogeneous Malay population, as Horstmann (2002) pointed out. Power relations clearly excluded the Malays. Positions in the state bureaucracy were dominated by ethnic Thais, rendering the state as an alien force in the views of many locals.

In contrast to the integration of Northern or North-eastern Thailand into the Thai nation-state, only very few local Malay elites, who dominated the power positions within the Sultanate of Patani, were integrated into the national bureaucracy. This created a

potential breeding ground for rebellions (Korff et al. 2006). The history of revolt combined with a lack of competencies required for filling positions within the administration and military, such as literacy in Thai, patronage relations to national leaders etc. made entrance into the bureaucracy difficult for people from the southern provinces. Thereby the representatives of the national administration, the local bureaucrats sent from Bangkok, could establish themselves as elites and exploit local resources for their own benefit. The power that Buddhist officials possess is legitimized by the collective merit of this group or, more specifically, of the Thai kings and the Thai bureaucracy who saved the nation from colonisation and who brought modernity and development to the country, which is expressed by the exemplary centre in Bangkok.

In this sense, the Buddhist-Malay relations have been successfully stigmatized. Officials have a tendency to consider Malays as inferior and backward, a security threat that has to be managed (Cornish 1997, Decha 2009). Malay Muslims are for many Buddhist Thais the most disturbing minority in Thailand. No other minority in the country has caused a comparable history of violent separatism. They are therefore seen as the ambivalent alien within the border and thus a threat to the Thai nation. Similar to the Chinese in Indonesia, the Malays are considered as a sort of antithesis to “national values”, although there has been a long history of local coexistence, intermarriage and cultural assimilation between Buddhists and the Malay Muslims (Horstmann 2004).

In two ways Malays in Southern Thailand seem even more dangerous than, for example, the Chinese in Indonesia or the Shan in Northern Thailand: first, they are concentrated in one area and even have their own history of statehood. Second, if Malays are not suspected to be disloyal and to want their own state, they are suspected to be oriented towards Malaysia where their “ethnic brothers and sisters” live. Particularly resented is the arbitrariness with which authority is exercised, as stated by a Malay sub-district chief:

“We have to be obedient to the orders of the great bureaucrats. When a Buddhist comes to a police checkpoint, the Buddhist policemen just let him pass, even when he has no driver’s license and no helmet. No problem. But if Malay youngsters drive motorcycles without a driving license, it’s always a big problem. They have to corrupt the police. Sometimes the police slap the face of Malay youngsters without reason. If they get arrested, I have to negotiate between the police and the parents, because the parents don’t dare to go to the police.”

Bureaucrats viewed any attempt to represent collective interest vis-à-vis the state through communal self-organisation with suspicion. Especially under Prime Minister Thaksin Shinawatra, popular Malay leaders became subject to extrajudicial killings, most prominent among them being the murder of human rights lawyer Somchai Neelaphaijit, who defended Malay victims of police harassment.

5.4.1. Popular acceptance of violence

These power differentials appear to be intrinsically linked to the meaning of violence. Looking at popular understandings of Malays, who have a supportive view of the insurgency, a major explanatory gap emerges between the perpetrators and the causes of violence. Most perpetrators of insurgent violence remain anonymous and hence there is a lack of knowledge among supporters of who is responsible for the daily non-state acts of violence. In theory, attacks could be dismissed as ordinary crime, or as the sole product of psychopaths. Violence without meaning is merely more than vandalism and would hardly be communicated at the heart of society. Interestingly, however, this lack of information does not lead to a dearth of explanations. Popular views draw on given interpretative frameworks such as communal memories of violence or particularistic (religious and ethnic) interpretative frameworks in order to make sense of what is going on.

Of course, viewpoints on the conflict in Southern Thailand are necessarily divergent, but one salient fact is that ethno-religious divisions are often clearly expressed in terms of negative stigmatization and ideas that relate to the lack of recognition by the Thai state, in particular. In other words, violence is considered an expression of popular grievances. If they refer to the region, Malay supporters often speak of a community of Malay Muslims and a community of Thai Buddhists. The root of the conflict is seen not in miserable poverty or class exploitation. Low wages, low rubber prices or an unjust distribution of land are usually not mentioned as causes. They rather tend to name the injustice that the “Malay collective” had to suffer as a consequence of the historical dominance of the Thai state. Its propagated legitimacy rests on the triad of “Nation”, “King” (who must be, as the constitution argues, a Buddhist) and the (Buddhist) “Religion”, which marginalized the Malay Muslims. Popular interpretations argue that although Thailand prides itself as a tolerant country that even deleted Buddhism as state religion from its newest constitution, Theravada Buddhism and its idea of cultural uniformity was and is still central to the idea of a stable united country. In other words, people reiterate the belief that violence arises from injustices in the political, and cultural field.

The dominance of ethnic Thais is considered to have caused a lack of recognition of Malays in various fields: first, the justice system. Officials are blamed for practices such as arrests without investigation, detention of Malays for longer than the regular law allows for, torture and, last but not least, extrajudicial killings. Most importantly, the killings of Malay demonstrators at Tak Bai and that of rebels on the holy ground of the Kru Se mosque are seen as the latest and most obvious manifestations of the long record of human rights abuses by Thai officials in the South. Coupled with disruptive processes of social change, state violence against Malays strengthened a kind of nostalgia for ethno-religious identity and recalled many existent communal memories of

former state repression of Malay individuals or collective demands (e.g. Haji Sulongs rebellion). Second, it is claimed that the region as a whole has been excluded from national development. Bangkok is said to support other regions in the country, but not the Muslim-dominated South, which is framed, for instance, in terms of per capita income or symbols of growth such as the construction of modern highways, hospitals, and shopping malls.

On the communal level, large-scale development projects caused alienation of the local population, because they were given no influence on the planning. The so-called 'participatory meetings' were held after decisions had already been taken. These projects allowed an entry of the national business conglomerates into the economy of the South, while the ecological costs were paid by the local farmers, and local business lost out. Similarly the development of the fishery industry with its large trawlers led to the decline of local fishermen, while the establishment of plantation agriculture negatively affected local small holders. The rapid development of the tourism industry drew national investors to the region, who competed with local business. Because they were more successful due to political and administrative connections, especially in larger scale projects, local business was alienated.

Third, in the area of education the state is accused of preferring Buddhist education whilst neglecting local forms of knowledge. Social change is framed in highly negative terms. It is seen as a loss of social control or state of anomy, i.e. the absence of norms, rules or laws. The spread of a corrupt Thai bureaucracy and a non-Muslim dominated capitalism are considered to have caused the destruction of local relationships (like village, neighbourhood). In many supportive accounts Malay society in the three provinces, as a consequence of uncontrolled social change, is considered to be in a state of moral decay as well as social disintegration.

The spread of drug consumption, a perceived increase in corruption and the decay of family structures are often cited as side-effects of modernisation that contradict visions of the "good life" as it is imagined by many middle-class Muslims. Ahamadabdun, a 38-year old, Iran-educated Imam from a village in Rueso district (Narathiwat), concludes his view on the conflict in Southern Thailand in the following words: "The Thai state always says that it grants us religious freedom, but the fact is that we cannot live as Muslims under this condition of moral crisis. How can you live as a Muslim if there is prostitution and alcohol all around, especially in the cities?" Such resentment is not directed at the Malay social structure itself. Importantly, unlike Bauman's picture of the liquid modernity in which there is no "control centre" of power that could be stormed by revolutionaries (Baumann 2000: 12), many Malays have someone to blame, namely the state.

Notable exceptions to the pattern mentioned above are voices from mixed ethnic villages, where both Muslims and Buddhists have been living side by side (Askew

2009b). Here Malays often seem to stress the history of multi-ethnic coexistence and the separation between both ethno-religious groups is less strongly expressed. Yet, one cannot evade the impression that for some parts of the Malay population, especially those whose contact to Buddhists is restricted to a plural society interaction on the market, the unjust rule of the state is somehow associated with civilian Buddhists in the region. Several reasons for this negative connotation can be mentioned:

1. As an ethnic group they dominate the bureaucracy in Southern Thailand, which is seen as unfair, because the majority of citizens in the three provinces are Malay Muslims;
2. Buddhists are considered to be patronized by the state. There were, for example, settled by the state in Southern Thailand in an obvious attempt to challenge the numerical preponderance of Malays in the South;
3. Similar to officials, civilian Buddhists are said to have stigmatising views on Muslims.

If the Malay supporters of the insurgency admit rebel violence, they do so in conjunction with a condemnation of violence. However, they also tend to put responsibility on the victim by questioning the actions of the victim before the assault (i.e. state officials or civilian Buddhist). In other words, they avoid blaming fellow Malays for these violent acts.

A case in point is a rumoured story of two Malay teenagers who at the age of around 16 joined the insurgent movement in Saiburi district, Pattani province. I was told that the two were indeed insurgents, but only because the state had forced them to be so. Initially, the two were just normal teenage boys who had been involved in the beating up of a local Sino-Thai pork trader (presumably for selling pork) in a local market. The police and the local subdistrict chief (kamnan) hunted them down for this rather minor offence, but while on the run, one of the teenage boys was allegedly shot by a policeman. The remaining two teenagers were understandably afraid of the police and hence decided to avoid a similar fate by joining the insurgents, simply because they had no other place to escape to. Although this story is from the mid-1970s it is still reproduced and thus its meaning has not yet been lost.

A similar story was told to me in late 2008 by an informant living in Sungai Padi district, Narathiwat province. He declared that he knew the “real reason” why some local officials in his district were recently attacked by Malays. A few months ago police and other armed forces had come to various villages in Sungai Padi to arrest around 10-15 young men that were suspected to be insurgents. My informant claimed that there were only very few insurgents among the arrested (“maybe one or two.”), but the police tortured all with electric wires - without any evidence. After they were set free, the

youngsters either built up their own insurgent groups or joined the ranks of the insurgents to take revenge on the officials and because they feared being arrested again.

Another variant of the popular acceptance of insurgent violence is the “but-response”, which refers to the mitigation of the moral responsibility of an insurgent only after people express the horror of the insurgent violence. For instance, a 47-year old Malay postman, who told me about a violent attack he witnessed, when, some time in 2006, a young Buddhist teacher was shot close to his post-station in Pattani. The postman recalled that he immediately went to the site and, together with other bystanders, stared at the woman’s dead body lying on the street. On the same day rumours stated that insurgents had shot the woman because she was a teacher at a government school. The postman stressed to me that “the sight of the shot body filled me with disgust and I didn’t like what the insurgents did that day. But remember, there are bad people on both sides.”

When I, for example, was introduced to Southern Thailand by a group of Malay students at the Prince of Songkhla University in Pattani at the very beginning of my fieldwork a group of female students active in a human rights group told me:

“Look, you want to know what is going on here? Last week a Buddhist general ordered his soldiers to kidnap a young Malay girl. So the soldiers looked for a Malay school student. They found one on her way home from, kidnapped her and brought her to the General in an Army Camp, where the General raped her. Can you understand why some people get angry and attack soldiers?”

When I asked where exactly this happened, when and why they knew about the General’s order, they could not specify any detail. Despite this, the rumour was so convincing that it spread across parts of the university within a few weeks. Similar “but-responses” are as such: “The violence committed against civilian Buddhists is horrible, but they (i.e. the Buddhists, S.H.) have committed atrocities against Malays, when they invaded the Sultanate of Patani.” or “There may be violence against Buddhist officials, but it is the result of the state suppression. Some youngsters are fed up and want to defend their village.”³⁹

³⁹ In some cases it was immediately admitted that insurgents would kill, for instance, teachers, because of either the belief that the teachers are government spies, or because the Malays simply want revenge for the killings in Tak Bai and elsewhere. In the opposite cases, people appeared to be ashamed when acknowledging the existence of insurgent violence. If one asks how the structural injustices relate to the attacks on female Buddhist teachers, direct answers are usually avoided. Instead, it is stressed that Malays who perpetrate the violence are either “hot heads”, who usually would not get involved in such ruthless acts of violence, or that they did not understand the “real Islam” (see also Askew 2009). Another “special factor” mentioned was that the perpetrators were drug addicts. How can we explain such “special-factor” references? According to Reemtsma (2008) violent acts can only have a social meaning if they are directed at an audience who share a common understanding of, or give a common meaning to it. Nevertheless, insurgent violence defies modernity’s universal norm of peacefulness which only allows for the use of “force” according to the principles of law. Insurgent violence only makes sense to particularistic epistemological communities who have specific cultural and historical frameworks that can legitimate violence. It seems as if many Malays want to avoid “misunderstandings” and the shame that comes from talking to outsiders, who are not familiar with the local Malay Muslim understanding of violence.

5.4.2. Accounting for Acceptance: violent resistance and recognition

At first sight these expressions of rumours and narratives appear to be mere anecdotes. But from an analytical viewpoint, their popular appeal is important in explaining why violence is meaningful, and explaining the popular support for the insurgency. All systems of rule are potentially subject to change. Depending on the political-cultural environment and the availability of means of articulation, the emotional responses to shame can develop motivations for engaging in a struggle to gain recognition (Honneth 1994).⁴⁰ In places like Eastern Europe, abrupt status reversals, through processes like war or the disintegration of multiethnic states, connected resentment and collective violent action. However, resentment and collective violence can also be linked through new beliefs and perceptions of violence (Wood 2003).

Typically, resistance against Thai dominance, despite occasional violent upheavals, took the form of a hidden transcript (Scott 1990). In the Thai public space there was no space for local concerns. These were considered to be illegitimate expressions of traitorous local tribalism that threatened the integrity of the Thai nation and undermined the project of modernity (as most Malays were not even able to speak enough Thai to voice themselves, so how could they determine their path of development?).⁴¹

This situation changed with the proliferation of Islamism in the region and the related rise of a Malay middle class. They allowed new standards of what were acceptable and not acceptable forms of domination and what could legitimately be demanded. Educated Malays, often fluent in Malay and Thai, could not easily be stigmatized as hindrances to modernity. They could challenge the state's monopoly of defining modernity and progress by employing modern symbols of Islamism. The adoption of Arab state concepts or the introduction of the sharia in different parts of society enabled Malays to articulate a modern alternative to Thai rule, which itself took increasingly royalist fundamentalist forms in recent years. In this sense the increase of a Malay Muslim middle class and the spread of Islamism represent an important leap in the struggle for recognition against the Buddhist majority and their claim to rule. Consider the following quote by a member of Yala's Islamic Council:

‘For a long time the Buddhists despised us as stupid and uneducated

As a result they make use of façades that make the perpetrator seem somehow different from the rest of society, i.e. references to drug use, uncontrolled feelings of revenge etc. These communicative dynamics can be illustrated by the following story: In late 2009 a German student from the University of Passau did her field research on the conflict in Pattani. In the first interviews with Malay university students, the Malay students generally, with very few exceptions, downplayed the level of sectarian violence as well as its meaning to them. This immediately changed when they learned that the father of the German student was a Palestinian. Suddenly, the interview partners were much more outspoken about the violence, assuming that she would easily understand that suppressed Muslim people often have no choice but to use violence.

⁴⁰ Honneth (1994) is hesitant to postulate a direct causal linkage between shame and revolution. For a revolution other factors such the ability to organise and articulate grievances are necessary.

⁴¹ The Southern Border Provinces Administrative Council, which was dissolved by Thaksin in mid-2002, is always mentioned as an exception in this regard, because it was assumed to be an institutionalized recognition of the specific Malay culture by the Thai state. But we still need serious research on whether it really fulfilled this function as Askew (2007) pointed out.

country people. But this changed in the last 20 years. They can no longer order us around as they did in the past, when they treated us like cattle. Now we speak their language well and are sometimes even better educated. Many of us have university education.”

When the global media identified Islamism and terrorism following September 11, and the “war on terror”, the Islamist discourse provided a degree of legitimacy for violent acts, even for those who only supported the insurgency on a very general level. When speaking of injustice, supporters of the insurgency often drew on militant Islamist imagery, drawing parallels between their suffering and that of the Muslims in Palestine or the Southern Philippines. Under the charismatic ideological influence of transnational Islamic militancy, they started to believe the separatist struggle of Patani Malays is the will of God. This allowed for a reconstruction and interpretation of local memories of violence. Rather than being an arbitrary tragedy, the hard struggle against Thai suppression could be understood as a sacrifice for the reign of God. The influence of Islamism, including the idea of the holy war, hence resulted in a renewed sense of dignity and righteousness of violence. Violence can become sacralised, if it is connected with nation, a religious community or moral order (Münkler 1992). Hence violence needs to be known and made public. Internationally, a purely “nationalist” frame or class-based frame would not provide comparable publicity and recognition.

However, the non-communication of rebel goals allows for patterns of popular acceptance of insurgent violence that are as wide-ranging as the motivations of insurgents themselves. Other supporters view the violence as a wider attempt to resist social change that is seen as destructive as one village head in Yala remarked:

“I don’t think that many people, especially in the countryside, who support the movement, actually have a clear goal. That does not mean that they are bad people. It is a way of defending themselves and proof that they cannot be pushed around by the state and by the politicians. They think that many things go wrong in society. In many villages people are divided along political and religious lines and strangers come and sell drugs to young people. Even if they can just pay money to the movement and even if nothing real is achieved, it is a sign of protest against these developments.”

Another theme that came up among the supporters of the insurgency was that the continued performance of violent acts itself, in the face of a massive Thai military presence, is understood as the most visible claim to regain recognition. The Malays as a collective had to suffer from humiliation at the hands of the authorities. However, enduring militant action expresses a claim of defiance. This defiance may not necessarily be associated with a positive goal like independence or a redistribution of wealth (Wood 2003). Whereas the killing of a Buddhist soldier, as a purely instrumental act, can be meaningful for an insurgent, namely as the destruction of state capacity, a Malay witness might consider the communicative or expressive dimension of the dead

person to be more meaningful. Although militancy has no obvious positive impact on his or her everyday life in terms of improving bureaucratic arbitrariness or bringing independence, it is the intimidating effect on the state that counts. This is illustrated by the following quote of a non-insurgent Malay Muslim female nurse, who did not expect that violence would ever free Malays from Thai rule:

“I don’t like violence and I don’t believe in an Islamic state. But the Buddhists used so much violence against us. I don’t like to see Buddhist victims of bomb attacks or officials who get shot. But sometimes I think it is a way to show them that we are still here, that we are alive as a group and that the Buddhists have to respect us.”

A founding member of Bersatu stated in an interview that: “The Thais are only nice and respectful to us, if we shoot at them.” This more existentialist dimension of violence cannot be explained by reason alone. Violence in this sense objectifies collective identity and the demand for recognition of it. According to Leach (1965), violence committed by a group against another is the highest form of social exclusion. It does not arise from cultural differences, but rather violence “is itself one of the ways in which the illusion of univocally defined and emotionally involved identities is produced” (Gomarasca 2007).

In this sense, insurgent violence represents the idea that oppression is not universal and can be overcome. Those, who deny recognition, cannot only expect compliance in everyday life, but must expect the power of violence. In this sense, insurgent violence is a social phenomenon. It embodies a minority’s resentment. Hence, it is not important if people believe that insurgents are united or disorganised, religious or driven by nationalism or that they achieve a concrete aim. The fact that the almighty Thai state can be attacked and duped for so many years is a sufficient achievement. Insurgents attack unpopular district offices and hated policemen or soldiers that are believed to be responsible for mistreating the minority.

Resistant violence is not solely destructive, but has a creative quality in recovering recognition through the exertion of the right to decide over life and death. Such an idea is far from irrational or traditional. Rather it is a typical element of modernity, although it has been criticized by an understanding of modernity (see, e.g., Elias 1997) that excludes violence from everyday life:

“The perception of the existence of the Other as an attempt on my life, as a mortal threat or absolute danger whose biophysical elimination would strengthen my potential to life and security—this, I suggest, is one of the many imaginaries of sovereignty characteristic of both early and late modernity itself. Recognition of this perception to a large extent underpins most traditional critiques of modernity, whether they are dealing with nihilism and its proclamation of the will for power as the essence of the being; with reification understood as the becoming-object of the human being; or the subordination of everything to

impersonal logic and to the reign of calculability and instrumental rationality. Indeed, from an anthropological perspective, what these critiques implicitly contest is a definition of politics as the warlike relation par excellence. They also challenge the idea that, of necessity, the calculus of life passes through the death of the Other; or that sovereignty consists of the will and the capacity to kill in order to live.”

Mbembe 2003: 18

In resistance people become meaningful subjects. Yet it is questionable whether defiance, i.e. the attempt to destroy lingering feelings of one's inferiority by violence itself, is enough to maintain collective action if the “price” is increased significantly (see below).

In addition, violence can be interpreted according to more profane interests and appeals across class divisions: For parts of the Islamic middle class insurgents embody aspirations or hopes, not necessarily for independence, but for an expansion of job opportunities in the Islamic sector (e.g. Islamic banking, halal food, Islamic education), which the state is supposed to expand. The influential group of “Private Islamic School” owners profits as well: As a result of insurgent attacks government schools in many rural areas hardly function anymore, pushing more and more Malay students into Islamic schools. At the same time, representatives of this huge state-sponsored industry argue with government representatives and international donors that in order to end the violence, Islamic education should be further expanded, so that people have jobs and a “proper understanding of Islam”. The groups outside of business and civil service depend on their own positioning in framing the violence as related to a religious conflict. In student intelligentsia circles and parts of the peasantry, rebels are even considered heroes or fighters for justice. All these actors, in addition to local Malay intellectuals, who tend to read into violence, form decentralized networks, which are important for the interpretation of events. Although they are quick to denounce government violence, there is not much public resistance to insurgent violence by Malay political and intellectual leaders.

In the accounts of Malays who oppose the insurgency these assertions of pride and achievement are notably absent. This appears to be a crucial difference. A plethora of critical voices argues against the insurgents both on moral as well as practical grounds. Most importantly, many deny that the insurgency is a jihad, because Muslims are free to follow their religion – thus these critics disallow for the connotation of legitimate violence. Besides, many Malays hold insurgents just as responsible for violence as the state: “I cannot believe that the state killed all the Buddhists. And if we kill their civilians, are we any better than the state?” Evaluations of opponents typically correspond to the assumed motives of insurgents: “If they wanted revenge for Tak Bai, they had their revenge. How many more people must die?”

Some families or individuals, who oppose the rebellion either live in multi-ethnic villages or are active in the Da'wah movement, advising their followers to refrain from politics of any kind. Other people have doubts, not so much on moral grounds, but they question the leadership qualities of the rebels:

“They sit in their comfortable houses in Malaysia and Sweden, collect the money and let lower-ranking people fight here in Thailand. This way, they will never win. We never had a daring leader like Che Guevara or Mao here. A leader, who agitates and fights in the field too.”

Others pursue careers within the state rather than against it or simply do not join due to the lack of an Ajak organisation in their particular village. Momentarily these patterns and different opinions towards the insurgents are extremely difficult to analyse and evaluate, just as the spread and support for the Ajak-committees is hard to quantify. Reliable local sources are hardly available and many opponents prefer to remain silent in the context of violence.

5.4.3. Images of insurgent restraint

Insurgents must bridge contradictory images through demonstrative violence. BRN-Coordinate strives to be loved and feared at the same time. Images of cruelty and terror are combined with images of discipline and piety. Armed groups, especially if they operate from the underground as BRN-Coordinate, are under the perennial risk of becoming self-referential entities, if they do not communicate with their environment. Consequently, violent attacks are committed only for the sake of the group itself, as was the case with the Red Army Fraction (RAF) in Germany (Münkler 1992). For Weinstein (2007) the crux for civilian support is that armed groups establish an image of restraint. Without such a credible image, general civilian support is unlikely: “Every one incident in which a combatant kills a civilian without cause damages the reputation of the rebel group” (Weinstein 2007: 206).

While BRN-Coordinate has to instill fear in their Buddhist opponents by using indiscriminate violence, if it wants to maintain the support of parts of the Malay population the group also has to correspond to certain local understandings of what violence against the enemy is justifiable. Drawing on insurgent interviews, it appears that insurgents are aware of certain counterproductive, delegitimising practices of violence. These practices include, for example, rape, looting, pillage and torture – both of Malay and Buddhist victims. Attacks against civilians - a crucial element in the group's strategy of escalation - are an especially perennial threat to legitimacy. If Malay insurgents kill and rape, crazed by barbarity, they will risk losing the support that is necessary for their survival. Insurgent leaders are well aware of this, as one BRN-Coordinate trainer pointed out:

“We instill fighters with discipline, so they don't fear attacking the

enemy. But this is also because at the time of the attack they must stick to certain rules. They must behave; they must not kill too many people at the same time or rape or steal money. People should have a good view of us. We are good Muslims.”

Understandings of legitimate violence vary according to place, time, sub-group, and objectives of violence that people have in mind. Recruiters are well aware that not all communities grant insurgents sanctity, as one insurgent of the BRN-Coordinate’s recruiter states: “There are Malay villages or people in villages, who oppose our violence anyway, but we are not interested in them. What is interesting to us, are those, who are on our side and those, who have not decided yet. We have to get them on our side.” As feelings of moral outrage change, partly in reaction to government action on the local level, and shift in time, the acceptance of violence also shifts, as another insurgent indoctrinator remarked: “After the killing in Tak Bai, we could use more force. People wanted revenge. Yet, the more time that passes, the more we had to be careful how we use force and against whom.” A practice that more and more Malays, even insurgent supporters, grew unsatisfied with over the years is the putting of spikes on the street, because it restricts mobility and fixing flattened tires is costly. According to an Ajak-committee member in Rueso district, Narathiwat province, recently more and more Malay villagers began to complain about the killing of Buddhist teachers, female civilians and other practices over the past two years:

“Our supporters become especially angry if the movement kills an Imam, even though the Imam was against the movement. We have to tell the military people to act more moderate. Even burning schools is something that is hard to do now, because people want their children to go to school. I think people become tired of these things, because sometimes they cause nothing but trouble.”

Another member of the political wing at the ligaran (subdistrict) level complained about the insurgent video clips: “I really don’t know why the fighters must film the beheadings of soldiers. Maybe they must prove how brave they are or scare the soldiers. But in my view this is counterproductive. Most of our supporters here in the villages don’t like these beheadings.”

A paradox of the popularly accepted violence is that the number of civilians killed in one incident should not exceed a certain level. If a whole busload of innocent, harmless Buddhists is killed, including children, as happened on March 14, 2007, when eight Buddhists were executed brutally in a minivan, this might be acceptable by insurgent standards. But such an incident would be seen as immoral in the view of most observers. The mixed consequences of a clear infringement of the limit of legitimate violence can be seen from IRA’s Omagh car bomb attack in 1998, which killed 29 and injured 220, including foreign tourists. This attack, which at least in the view of the British media, exceeded the popularly accepted level of violence against civilians, is said to have caused a blow to support for the IRA and a deepening of existing splits

within the group (personal conversation Dagmar Hellmann-Rajanayagam, April 27, 2011).

Another significant element in the popular acceptance of violence appears to be the belief that insurgents do not kill innocent Malays (Apitzsch 2010). Despite the lack of confirmed information, supporters hold the view that most Malays that are killed by insurgents are collaborators with the state. Consider the following quote of a Malay politician in Narathiwat, who claimed:

“As a Muslim, you can be sure that the movement won’t kill you, if you don’t talk bad about them or work with the state. If an innocent Muslim gets killed here, it is either the state or the Mafia, a matter of politics, or a personal thing. I was never afraid of going to a coffee shop or restaurant. You just have to watch your mouth.”

How can we explain this conviction? Kalyvas explains that a mix of “accurate and erroneous hit” (2006: 190) is sufficient to establish the image of a “selective killer”. Technically, local agents help to accurately identify targets to avoid attacking people in the public, who are believed to be innocent. Highly visible, indiscriminate executions communicate quickly within an audience and are hence avoided by armed groups. This is why BRN-Coordinate invests time in counter-checking information of Malay collaborators before allowing an attack on them.

However, reputation for accuracy is not only a problem of technical information. Rather than the actual “lethal performance”, it is what an audience thinks about a group’s performance that counts. Data on IRA killings in 1916-1923, for example, shows that very few victims of IRA assassinations were real informants (Kalyvas 2006). In Algeria, for example, the logic for explaining killings of the FLN went as follows: “When we heard that persons X or Y had been found murdered, we said to ourselves: ‘Who would have believed that they were traitors?’ But they must have been, since the FLN executed them.” (Hamoumou 1993 cited in Kalyvas 2006: 191). In short, killings, at least among supporters, explain themselves.

In addition, the (assumed) establishment of a network of local informants i.e. BRN-Coordinate’s village-based Ajak-committees and their informers, conveys the image of an “organisation’s willingness and potential capacity to be selective” (Kalyvas 2006: 190). Evidence from other armed conflicts shows that because an audience assumes the existence of a group’s presence, it tends to believe that victims are guilty. In Southern Thailand one can find countless accounts that resemble the following quote of a Malay Muslim teacher in a Private Islamic School: “The fighters are like ghosts, you can’t see them and can’t hear them, but they have their eyes and ears everywhere. But if you stay still, nothing will happen to you.” An RKK-fighter, being aware of the delegitimising effects of killing a fellow Muslim remarks:

“We have to successfully label Muslims, who are killed as munafiq. If

people still like that person, we have to make it look like the state did it. Sometimes I know it is necessary to get rid of these people, because they are dangerous to us, especially if they know our names and give them to the police.”

Another crucial question is how exactly the general support for the insurgency influences the perception of violence. It is probable that people who generally support the insurgents, who are subject to certain rumours and who have a certain image of them (e.g. as pious fighters for God or the Nation), tend to overestimate the lethal capabilities of the insurgents. My impression from the three provinces was that illegitimate violence was typically ascribed to the enemy, whereas insurgents were assumed to draw on legitimate attacks. Moreover, Srisompob estimates that only around a third of the region’s killings that are publicly ascribed to the insurgents are actually committed by insurgents, the rest are probably (typically) committed by Thai personal, mafia or as part of political disputes (personal conversation, August 2007). How are these general images connected to experiences of violence on the micro level and how do they influence cooperation? We know, for example, from the perception of the Mafia among Italians that as long as violent actors have no face and stay “in the dark”, their strength and capabilities are usually overestimated. Fear and admiration coupled with secrecy foster imagination. However, once a mafia member is kept on camera, arrested and handcuffed, he is quickly de-mystified and observers are usually surprised how inconspicuous and “small” they actually are (Stölting 1994).

Being aware of these delegitimising effects of violence, the group must correctly assess accepted levels and forms of violence and react to them by, for example, adjusting their attack patterns and, if possible, manipulating the perceptions of violence. There are, for example, Islamist forces within BRN-Coordinate’s leadership, who argue for an expansion of attacks outside the core area of Patani (e.g. in Bangkok or tourist areas). This could hurt the Thai economy severely. More nationalist, conservative forces are against such an escalation, and it is unlikely that it would be accepted by most Malays, as illustrated by the ostensibly negative reception of the 2006 Hat Yai bombing. Civilians have established a representation, though not detailed, of what can be expected from insurgents. Applying a model by Weinstein (2007), one could argue that for Southern Thailand, if Malay civilians were not sure of what to expect from insurgents or in cases where they expected undisciplined force and indiscriminate killings, they would flee the region, just as many Buddhists have done, or choose resistance (e.g. by collaborating with the government). In other words, a certain order of violence is established through communication. Such an approach towards the demonstrative dimension of images of restraint also helps us to understand why the nature of violence remains rather constant through time (Weinstein 2007). Yet the exact line between legitimate and illegitimate attacks is hazy and the political wing must

effectively inform and control its military counterpart, which often appears to be difficult (see below).

5.4.4. Manipulating popular receptions

Sending credible messages through demonstrative violence is not only a matter of solving information problems. As the case of BRN-Coordinate illustrates, it is only one side of the communicative effort that seemingly protects BRN-Coordinate against inversion from its environment. In order, for instance, to assess government reactions to its violent campaign, BRN-Coordinate can draw on its local intelligence apparatus and the national media. The former can show, for instance, whether there are changes in troop size, patrol patterns or counterinsurgency tactics at the local level, whereas the latter gives hints as to broader policy changes. In assessing the perception of local supporters, the group draws on its far-reaching village committees. In the days immediately after an insurgent attack Ajak-committee members assess both the perception of the recent attack among both the supporters and the general Malay population in the affected area, talking to villagers directly, or picking up rumours (Ajak-committee chief interview, November 2, 2009). This information is then processed to, for example, the *sukum* level via the *komis* level. This must be done quickly, because the earlier counterproductive rumours are identified, the easier they can be controverted by circulating “counter-rumours”.

This allows the leadership level to consider and, if necessary, influence local opinions. Rumours and leaflets are major instruments that are used to influence the perception of violence. The fact that claim-taking is not made before or after attacks leaves insurgents with some room to manoeuvre and allocate responsibility. As a general guideline, if the local population discredits an insurgent attack, the attack will be either blamed on the state or images of the victims are manipulated. This can be illustrated by the following examples: in 2009 a Phatthalung-Sungai Kolok train was ambushed with machine guns by masked BRN-Coordinate fighters in Narathiwat’s Rangae district. The BRN-Coordinate leaders soon learned that Malays in Narathiwat and widely beyond spoke out clearly against this attack, because many poorer Malays used trains regularly as a means of transportation, and therefore innocent Malays were injured in the incident. As a consequence BRN-Coordinate members in the region were told to spread the rumour that the incident was orchestrated by the Thai Army in an attempt to get additional funds for protecting trains in the South and therefore they consciously accepted the risk of killing innocent civilians for that.

In another attack in a small village in Pattani in November 2006 a Malay Muslim village head was killed by BRN-Coordinate, because he resisted cooperation with insurgents on the ground and threatened to report them to the authorities. The village head was very popular with the villagers, and therefore local opinion within the village clearly opposed this assassination. Immediately after the attack rumours spread that the

insurgents were responsible for the attack. Yet these rumours remained unconfirmed, because the police were unable to capture the perpetrator. BRN-Coordinate had just begun establishing the Ajak-committee structure in the village and hence feared that their attempt to infiltrate the village would be undermined by killing the popular village head. As a reaction, the local sukum-committee chief ordered existing members to circulate the rumour that a local policeman, who suspected the village head to be an insurgent, killed the village head. The policeman, it was said, expected to be promoted to a higher position by eliminating as many insurgents as he could. Since villages lacked any trustable relations to the police, the rumour was diffused in the village successfully. The resulting resentment against the police then eased recruitment efforts.

Although such rumours appear plausible to many Malays, the key to the success of BRN-Coordinate's use of rumours is, according to an Ajak-committee chief, that they simultaneously appear in different places, instigated by different people within a certain time period:

“You have to look at the right places. You can distribute at schools, teashops, restaurants, at the market or on the main street. A combination of them all is the best. And you have to find the right people. Find opinion makers in the school, if you want to influence what is being thought at the school. If you want to influence a village, a 17-year old is not trustworthy, so you better find older Coordinate people or you let Coordinate people talk to someone who is known to have a lot of information or get around a lot. People won't believe kids or strangers.”

The engineering of rumours takes a different territorial dimension according to the aim of the rumour and the importance of the issue. A single murder of a Malay collaborator with the government might only be communicated within a village and its neighbouring villages. So BRN-Coordinate will circulate only rumours within the corresponding area. Opinions on more spectacular attacks like the train ambush must be manipulated over a wider area. Moreover, rumours must fit to what people have seen during the insurgent attack, as a 35-year old BRN-Coordinate member, who had a B.A. degree in marketing and was responsible for BRN-Coordinate's “public relations” on the ligaran-level, stressed:

“We have different ways of blaming officials for killing a Muslim. When our fighters kill a monafiq, they either wear Ranger or Army uniforms or they kill him close to a police station or army post, so, afterwards, we can say that the state did it. But we could not claim this, when our fighters wore normal clothes and everybody saw them. It is our task to fit rumours according to what people saw. Thus the Ajak must report to us what happened.”

In other words, what appears familiar and plausible as well as what causes fear to ordinary villagers is part of the “stock of trade” of a good insurgent propagandist. Moreover, as mentioned above, insurgent rumours must be circulated through certain

“information hubs”, if they are to be effective. In the provincial capital of Narathiwat a number of restaurants and coffee shops, as well as the mosque after the Friday prayer, which are visited frequently, many by Malay men in Narathiwat, make up the centre of information exchange. According to the owner of a Malay coffee shop there were a handful of people who regularly “provided” others with new rumours about not only various issues in relation to the violence, but also about the newest political developments in the region and in Bangkok. After attacks by state and insurgent forces they were typically one of the earliest to interpret the event. They explained, for example, that one bomb attack at a market in 2007, in which both Buddhists and Malay Muslims were injured, was the product of a local military unit in Narathiwat, who wanted to get more money and guns from their superiors in order to sell them.

These “opinion makers” claimed, for example that they had special connections to villages where attacks happened, or connections with the police. These claims gave their rumours a degree of credibility, while being the earliest to spread the rumours showed that they were well connected, making the claims more trustworthy. Although they are not necessarily supporters of the insurgency, it is important for BRN-Coordinate to identify them and use them in order to influence the information flow.

Indeed one of these local “opinion makers”, a local politician and former member of Narathiwat’s provincial parliament, who opposed the insurgency, told me that one evening in mid-2007 he openly expressed his view that “the movement” (neowruam in Thai) had no chance of winning among a circle of around eight or nine people. Immediately, the day after, a friend told that politician that “the fighters for Patani” were very unhappy with his statements and that, “for the sake of his health”, he should refrain from publicly declaring his view.

BRN-Coordinate’s tactics of subversion also address and make use of Thai officials. In Narathiwat’s Bajo district, for example, BRN-Coordinate Penerangan experts had to deal with three Malay villages, in which all locals refused to join insurgent activities and had, generally, good relations to local officials. In 2006 as an attempt to raise tensions between these villagers and the state, group members left numerous threatening letters in the three villages, which said, handwritten in Thai, that “the movement” (neowruam) was strong in the area and that the Thai state had no chance of winning the war. This raised suspicions on the side of the local army unit that found the letters and immediately began to patrol the village regularly on a 24-hour-basis and interrogate locals. Although the village heads tried to explain to army officials that the letters were not distributed by local villagers, tensions persisted. On the side of the villagers, for the first time, many began to feel like victims of state harassment. This measure proved partly successful, as in at least one of the three villages, BRN-Coordinate could recruit enough members for an Ajak-committee.

Figure 5.1. Insurgent propaganda leaflets

Source: insurgents

As with other activities of BRN-Coordinate information operations follow certain rules and regulations. Whereas rumours do not need to be approved and can be released by local units independently, issuing threatening letters and propaganda leaflets, in parts of Pattani at least, apparently must be approved by the sukum level before release, in case they might contain evidence that may lead the police to identify the authors. The design of the leaflets has developed from handwritten notes to more elaborately designed flyers that are distributed to local committees via email and printed in BRN-Coordinate affiliated copy shops (see figure 5.1.). Usually leaflets are written in Thai, except for some basic Malay slogans like “Patani merdeka” (free Patani). Most local Malays can read Thai very well, and only a little of Malay or the Yawi-script.

5.5. Demonstrative violence and the virtual collectives

Another significant structuring effect of demonstrative violent acts that became apparent after September 11 is a phenomenon that can be referred to as “virtual collectives”. In the post-September 11 climate, a number of lonely wolf terrorists, independent militant cells or whole insurgent networks that feel inspired by al Qaeda Central, have committed terrorist attacks in the name of the Al Qaeda, even though they have no direct link to the group. These actors declare themselves as “new members” in acts of terrorism that serve as a kind of “initiation”, such as the Madrid bombings in

2004 (Sageman 2008). In other words, the public sphere allows individuals to understand themselves as part of a collective. This collective can remain wholly fictitious or a projection.

Demonstrative violence also appears to play a crucial role in the cohesion of more organised groups like BRN-Coordinate. To maintain the motivation of a fighter, he or she must believe that there are others fighting the same struggle. As we learned above, a typical RKK-fighter has only a limited number of fellow insurgents with whom he has contact: his recruiter, maybe another person who took the oath of allegiance, a number of trainers and 20 or 30 fellow recruits at the training camp, his own RKK-squad, a very limited number of other RKK-squads with whom he may have worked with in a larger operation, and parts of an Ajak-committee that would have assisted him in an attack. This roughly amounts in total to usually less than 50 or 60 people.

In order to transcend this limited number of face-to-face interactions and give rise to a virtual community of fighters, insurgents use various forms of media technology. Although, as mentioned earlier, communication within the group is restricted for security purposes, insurgents find ways of circulating images that shape their sense of collective action and knowledge of insurgents beyond the confines of the individual member's radius of direct interaction. Their practice includes, for example, the appropriation of media images of violence that are otherwise used by journalists in Bangkok. Although recruits are asked to avoid Thai television entertainment, insurgents watch Thai television news after spectacular insurgent attacks in order to "share" in the success of their "brothers". Whereas the journalists convey the images of blown up humvees or dead soldiers in order to show the suffering and damage done by insurgents, insurgents themselves see the same images as examples of their effectiveness.

This obsession with the visual, iconographic manifestation of violence is also illustrated by the following example. One BRN-Coordinate supporter in Narathiwat city, a Malay Muslim teacher at a government school, regularly collected Thai newspaper articles, which featured pictures of the results of insurgent attacks such as burnt out police vehicles, hospitalized government officials and blown up district offices. Every couple of weeks he gave these collected pictures to a member of the organisation, who himself lived in the province's countryside, but refrained to buy the articles in order to avoid suspicion:

"My friend in the movement doesn't like to buy newspapers from the Buddhist shops, because he fears that they report him to the police. He also likes me to cut out those articles in which journalists describe the plight of the Thai's struggle against the movement. But pictures of successful attacks are even more important. I think he shows them to the other people in the movement, as well."

In both instances, that of the television and newspaper usage, insurgents and their support networks drastically transform media texts and images according to their own

value system. To put it in the words of de Certeau, behind the official production of images by the media we find a “secondary production hidden in the process of its utilization” (de Certeau 2002: xiii).

Another practice included the distribution of small film clips of the beheading of soldiers through the mobile phone networks. The beheading was kept on camera by one of the attacking insurgents. It was not clear, however, if the filming of the beheading was ordered by superiors, or if the operatives, possibly inspired by videos on the internet, decided themselves to record it. Later the film was put on VCD and distributed widely, including to students at the Prince of Songkhla University in Pattani and the Thai soldiers themselves. Through these non-insurgent networks that circulated the region quickly within a few months or so, the film also reached other insurgent networks in other regions. After one successful attack against a high-ranking Thai police officer in 2010, at least three BRN-Coordinate members immediately informed each other before the official Thai news even reported the attack later that day. One of the sms’ sent referred to the police officer as “babi”, the Malay word for pig, stating: “Another babi was just traded in Yala!” Another special name for Buddhists, both used by civilians and officials, is ‘dog’. Referring to victims as wild animals is a common mode of “communicating about victims of violence” within armed groups because it dehumanizes enemies and excludes them from the moral community of protected fellow humans. Similarly, BRN-Coordinate’s Malay Muslim victims are usually referred to as munafiq, excluding them from the ummah. These naming mechanisms help the performers of violence to avoid the moral responsibilities attached to killing (Blok 2000).

In contrast to Sri Lanka, where the production of images of violence is more centralized by the LTTE and the Sri Lankan government, decentralized distribution plays an important part in Southern Thailand: images circulate through the internet, market mechanisms (in 2007, for example, jihad videos were sold in front of Narathiwat’s central mosques), personal networks and sometimes political networks. Before the general election in 2005, for example, VCDs on the killings in Tak Bai were widely distributed in the region by vote-brokers, and at Mosques associated with the Democrat Party, which obviously aimed to discredit the (at that time) ruling Thaksin government.

In this sense, communicated violent action is not simply the symbolic reification of insurgent’s ideology of friend and foe, of believers and unbelievers, or oppressors and oppressed. Nor is it simply a means to an end, i.e. certain fantasies of power or independence among BRN-Coordinate members. Visual attacks achieve something that rational choice cannot account for: successful violent acts are communicated in order to prove and measure one’s own will and dignity. One insurgent, who commented on the filmed decapitation, illustrates the point: “The film might look cruel. But it shows me that we are strong and that my brothers are all around and willing to make sacrifices.

We might not know each other, but we know that we are strong and powerful.” Here one is reminded of Napoleon’s military dictum, which states that in war the will to win, to triumph and carry the burden of military confrontation is three times as important as the physical strength (Smith 2008: 244).

Sociology has shown that the stronger the belief people hold about their collective abilities, the more they can accomplish (Bandura 1997). A group of self-doubters can hardly be united into a collective, efficacious force. Communication of violence reshapes the sense of the self. Violent acts across time and space are compressed through perception in order to give rise to a virtual collective of “the movement”. This collective efficacy is connected with the perceived self-efficacy of the individual holy warrior that was already instilled in the secret milieu. But now, after the outbreak of violence, the image is constantly proven by the violence performance.

BRN-Coordinate members, who have passed through the group training, know that violent attacks are the result of a highly coordinated effort by the actors both within and between the political and the armed wing. It involves the weeklong gathering of intelligence, the acquisition and transport of guns and bombs, despite tight security measures, and finally the brave act of the warrior himself. Therefore demonstrative violence instils an awareness of the spread of the group as well as its collective will to triumph. An Ajak-committee chief in Panaera district, Narathiwat province, reiterated this conviction in disturbing terms. When we saw a military convoy passing through his village, he told me: “Look at them! These soldiers are already dead, but they simply don’t know it yet.”

Violent action conveys a sense of hitherto unknown agency, an experience of power. It is the joy of impressing one’s will upon otherwise more powerful actors like officials. Albeit BRN-Coordinate’s internal structure is only known by very few people, the group’s power is not only experimental, it also affects the social structures:

“Violence shows that we can overcome differences. Although the Thai system incorporated some of our people, there are still enough to fight it. And the neutral rest has to decide on which side they stand. See, for example, we already cut out the village heads as a link between the people and the state. The government schools in the countryside, which we attacked, do not work anymore. People have to send their kids to our Malay schools. All the money the Thais have, it doesn’t count.”

Structurally, demonstrative violence also creates a sense of agency by reducing social complexities through the “immediacy”, or better, the extraordinary power of violence. As an insurgent remarked:

“It is more than revenge for our dead people, killed by the Thais. Everything the Thais did and do: their invasion, their attempt to change us into Thais through the schools and their development projects, which aim to buy our loyalty with money. None of that counts anymore. Only

what we do is important, when we use force.”

Through collective violence, it appears that historical contingencies can be revised, power differentials typical for peaceful times appear to be suspended, different interests disrupting Malay unity are flattened out, and a collective agency is created in the place of victimhood.

5.6. Breaking the logic of escalating violence? The Army’s perception(s)

How crucial the perception of violence is for the course of the conflict can be seen in the role of state reactions to insurgent violence. Luring the state into acts of indiscriminate violence against the local Malay Muslim population and thus deflecting its force to BRN-Coordinate’s own use is crucial in the group’s strategic thinking about an escalating conflict. As mentioned above, ruthless state suppression, in return, is supposed to further mobilise local and international actors, who have hitherto remained neutral.

Events in Tak Bai and Kru Se confirmed that the strategy of escalation has had a certain chance of success. Insurgents seem to be right to conclude from past experiences that the Thai state has an innate propensity to terrorize the local population. On many occasions the Thai state and state-sponsored thugs had used violence not only against Malay Muslims, but also against internal opposition like the student movement in 1976. For the same purpose, for example, BRN-Coordinate organised another wave of local demonstrations against arrests by Thai officials in 2006. Here, the group hoped that security forces would violently disrupt the demonstration, as well.

Like elsewhere, such state reprisals prove futile from the point of the incumbent, because they drive the civil population into the hands of rebels.⁴² Civilians typically consider indiscriminate state violence as highly unfair, because they are targeted regardless of whether or not they are involved in the insurgency or not. Indiscriminate violence also fails to create collaboration with the government because it is typically erratic and temporal. State forces appear and frighten the population and then disappear without establishing permanent control. Hence for civilians it is more rational to remain neutral or (secretly) cooperate with rebels (Kalyvas 2006).

The partial use of “wanton reprisals” results from the state structure. To a degree it is also rooted in perceptions. As already mentioned the “unnamed force” proved a major cognitive obstacle for Thai soldiers, who are trained in conventional warfare and hence expect a hierarchically organised, more or less visible enemy. Conventional armies

⁴² Under certain conditions indiscriminate state violence against civilian populations can indeed be of use for an incumbent government. Reprisals can deter people from cooperating with insurgents. Kalyvas (2006) seems to suggest that this is only the case, when the indiscriminate state terror eliminates organised armed opposition groups, so that the population might be angry, but, at the same time, they have no organised form to resist state reprisal. This is, however, not the case in Southern Thailand.

typically have a tendency to turn to indiscriminate violence under the condition of irregular warfare, especially if they don't know whom to look for. Security forces faced a state of confusion. Thai Military commanders, who were newly deployed in the three provinces after 2004, had very few clues as to whether they were dealing with an insurgency, international terrorism or political violence gone wild. The explanation that an uncoordinated local movement pursued a bloodstained revenge against the killings at Tak Bai and Kru Se sounded equally convincing at that time. Unfortunately, local police and intelligence were of little help as most of them had simply missed or underestimated the systematic revival of the insurgents, although there were already signs of a reviving insurgency since the turn of the century (Liow & Pathan 2010). As Thompson (1966) points out, all states have a tendency to underestimate the early warning signs of an upcoming rebellion.

Unable to draw a distinction between combatants and non-combatants, but under a lot of pressure to produce results, soldiers turned to extra-judicially killing people or tortured them into false confessions. An internal study of the Thai army showed that after a period of approximately three months many soldiers, frustrated with the inability to distinguish between insurgents and non-insurgents, began to overestimate the ties between insurgents and the local population: "Many of us still think that we have to punish everybody, so that there will be no more support for the trouble-makers...They treat everybody as sympathizers", a colonel remarked (interview, December 4, 2010).

The tendency to hold Malay civilians collectively responsible for the insurgency is aggravated, when insurgents attack Thai troops. The resulting anger coupled with weak discipline leads to revenge killings (Grossman 1996). A Thai army major commanding an area in Yala province remembered:

"Many of us were very frustrated. We got shot at and bombed, comrades got killed. Locals would not talk to us. Even those of us, who had initial sympathies with the Muslims, got frustrated. And superiors wanted to get results. So naturally some turned to blind force. Others simply wanted to take revenge for friends they had lost."

Racist attitudes towards Malays among Thai police and military forces played a crucial role here. Informal discussions by policemen and military officers about the conflict are less marked by rational argumentation or a distinguished approach than by emotional statements of hatred, love, expressions of horror in the face of violence as well as a call for national unity. Emotional pictures and nationalist slogans replace arguments and create exclusive "We-groups" such as "Buddhist" vs. "Muslims". In this context the term "Muslim" equals the term terrorist or assailant, someone who disgraces Thailand. The Buddhist "us", in contrast, is connoted with victimhood and casualties etc. Such attitudes can be found among civilians as well. It is widely believed that most of the "real victims" are "the Buddhists", although the actual casualty figures are very different (Phrae 2009).

We should add that these bigoted racial constructions of the “self” tend to relate to questions of danger and safety as they draw on the idea of the “safe home” as meaningful metaphor. The area outside of “home” is the area of the stranger, posing a potential threat (Bauman 1995: 135). The dream of the defensible terrain, which is “semantically transparent” and “semiotically legible”, becomes even more intense in times of rapid social change. Safety is associated with the own group and danger is projected on the “others”. But as Bauman stresses, this “home” rather exist in fantasies. It is through border conflicts with strangers that the ideal of the home is rendered into a practice that becomes “real”. In this sense modernity is by nature a border civilisation – it upholds its momentum through the colonisation of the bordering terrain of ambivalence. Although the Thai bureaucrats are the key safeguards of this border, the normal citizens have the same duty.

Besides, states that lack political cohesion and a strong bureaucracy feel a constant threat of disintegration. Hence politicians and bureaucrats turn to the situational power of arbitrary violence against internal opponents (Trotha 1995). The function of this violence lies not only in its physical instrumentality, but in its communicative dimension. Demonstrative violence is a sign of power that establishes a special relation between the rulers and the ruled, i.e. a relation of “unconditional” superiority and inferiority.

At the leadership level of the 4th Army Area opinions on how to understand the violence that suddenly flamed up again in 2004, after almost two decades of peace, diverged significantly as a consequence of unclear, partly contradictory intelligence (interviews Colonel and General level of the 4th Army Area, September 2009 - December 2010). At the beginning, some people at the colonel level followed Prime Minister Thaksin Shinawatra’s argument that insurgents had deteriorated into mafia-style groups. One faction of generals, socialized during the Cold War era, viewed the violence basically as a class conflict that was caused by uneven development and economic neglect of the region. This was reflected in the 1980s, when the Thai Army ended the communist insurgency by granting student rebels asylum and pouring development funds into the poor Northeast of the country. From this they assumed that the South could also be pacified by similar development efforts.

Another faction assumed that they were basically dealing with just another local hotspot of militant Islamism, which could be eliminated simply by targeting the shadowy masterminds at the top. Still, others believed that the violence was a natural, unorganized reaction to the misuse of power by the state and the massacres at the Tak Bai and Kru Se. In their view, good governance measures, and the recognition of the cultural originality of Malays, could automatically bring an end to the “eruption of popular fury”. The “good governance solution”, just like the class-based approach, had the advantage that the capture of insurgents was not of primary concern. For some time

the political leadership in Bangkok neither provided a clear policy guideline for soldiers nor personal continuity. Under Prime Minister Thaksin the commanders of the 4th Army Area were changed six times (Abuza 2009). Here it becomes clear that the façade of disorganised, reactive violence that is intrinsically connected to secrecy is more than tactical protection for BRN-Coordinate. As a consequence of the army's inability to identify the perpetrators, their degree of organisation, and the causes of unrest, forces on the ground remained unguided, with orders only to protect civilians and state personal.

A major break in the perception of violence among commanding staff of the 4th Army Area came in December 2005. Then, Amjoh Sau, a 46-year old BRN member, explained to the authorities, in detail, the structure of the Ajak-committee. He revealed the structure of the re-designed BRN-Coordinate.⁴³ From 1994 onwards Amjoh Sau had been both a member of BRN-Coordinate and a village head in Sungai Padi district, Narathiwat. Over the passing months, more and more captured insurgents confirmed the idea of a uniform organisation. Many insurgents knew about the 10-point disciplinary code and had passed the same training programme after taking the oath of allegiance; others themselves admitted being part of the Ajak-committee structure.

This proved to be a major turning point for Major General Samrej Srirai and other leading figures in the 4th Army Area. It was clear now, that the violence was not a set of unconnected, autonomous incidents, but rather characterized by a significant degree of organisation. A force (organisers behind incidents and planners) aimed to escalate the situation by manipulating the Thai state into further acts of reprisal. Though it was not clear who was responsible for the campaign of violence, it involved a significant amount of preparation including the apparent impression of suddenness. Consider the following quote by Samrej:

“Now we saw that we had to reconsider our steps. We were in need of re-designing our approach. The first thing I did was to publicly declare that there would be no second Tak Bai. We did not know who they were, but we knew that we had to think about it. This was nothing that could easily be solved with popular politics. Based on my experience with communist rebels in the South in the 1970s, I knew that this would take a lot of time. I publicly declared that there would be no second Kru Se as long as I was in the region (...). This was a first step to signal to them that we knew what was going on and that we would not be provoked into some kind of inconsiderate action again.”

For him it was obvious that, on the one hand, any aggressive actions would be highly unproductive. The dream of a quick and decisive victory against insurgents as proposed by Thaksin and other military hardliners (see, e.g., Liow & Pathan 2010) proved just as illusionary as the pouring of development programs into the region in an attempt to end the insurgency. On the other hand, investing money into development funds and

⁴³ For an early description of the re-designed organisational structure and strategy of BRN-Coordinate by a senior Thai military officer see สำเร็จ ศรีทราย (2550/2551).

governance programmes was unproductive as long as the perpetrators and their motivations were not identifiable. A central task was to look behind the façade of disorganisation and identify the main insurgent group, their organisational patterns as well as their strategic thinking on the ground. Thai counterinsurgency campaigns still faced a variety of fundamental problems. Intelligence on the insurgents was still desperately poor. It was only in the course of 2008/2009 that, for example, BRN-Coordinate's leading role and its internal structure became evident to its full extent. Even up until today there is reluctance on some parts of the Thai security agencies, especially the police, to accept the sophisticated organisational structure of BRN-Coordinate. The current government is quick to downplay the insurgency, for example, by pointing out that insurgents are not linked to international terror networks like al Qaida (Bangkok Post, 17 June 2009), while avoiding naming or identifying any specific group as responsible.

5.7. Collaboration, defection and support: local perceptions of violence and power

Civil wars are characterized by a regime of fragmented sovereignty. As long as state control at the village level in Southern Thailand is not effective, a gap between state and society exists. General support for a rebellion can be translated into concrete action, because rebels and their supporters need not fear monitoring and sanctioning. From a rational choice perspective Kalyvas (2006) argues that civilians usually shift their support to the side that exerts control and therefore seems to be the winning side. When sovereignty is disputed, civilians tend to remain neutral or secretly supportive of the insurgency. When state surveillance increases to an effective level, civilians will most likely choose to support the state. Hence, the state can enforce collaboration among the civilian population by establishing strong institutions.

According to Kalyvas (2006) the capacity to identify and apply selective violence against insurgents, or to arrest them, is basically a function of an armed actor's ability to gather territorial control. Based on this military control, the state would continue institutionalising its control by collecting local information against defectors in order to destroy clandestine networks by exerting selective violence against them. Once these networks are destroyed, increasing parts of the population switch their loyalty. He assumes that most parts of a population follow the preponderance of military power:

“Although motivations to denounce vary, the constraints faced by denouncers provide a good way to model the process. The key constraint is the likelihood of retaliation against the denouncer via the process of counter-denunciation to the rival actors by the family of the victim. Thus denunciation is a function of the control a political actor has over an area: control affects the likelihood of retaliation against the

denouncer because counter-denouncers need access to the rival political actor.”

Kalyvas 2006: 174.

In the three provinces village-based COIN units were deployed in 50 out of approximately 217 “heavily infiltrated” villages (muubaaan jadtang) from 2007. These units were ordered to reveal the structures of the insurgents and to fill the gap between state and society by being present at the village level 24 hours a day, seven days a week. By what criteria did the army choose these villages? Villages were chosen based on indicators such as the weakness or absence of village heads, the frequency of incidents within or in the perimeter around the villages, lack of cooperation or even resistance against soldiers and policemen (e.g. demonstrations, road-blocks, spikes on the street). Strong Ajak committees are recognizable by certain collective patterns of behaviour. When an army unit enters a village, the village guards immediately warn the population using walkie-talkies, mobile phones and even loudspeakers. So when soldiers arrive at a village centre, most people will have disappeared into their houses. In other places, whole groups of youngsters leave the village altogether. These reactions are not the least a result of BRN-Coordinate’s general guidelines of non-collaboration with the government. People were asked to resist the state in any possible way.

This decentralized counterinsurgency proves that territorial control - a key factor to reduce likelihood of retaliation - is not easily established. Interviews with local COIN staff and insurgents indicate that formal territorial control is not directly translated into social control. A number of factors determine whether COIN units are able to identify insurgent structures on the ground. Much depends, for example, on their policing skills. To get into regular contact with villagers, soldiers bring small development projects (e.g. fish farming schemes) to the villages in which they are deployed.

The mission of these units is not to capture RKK-fighters, because fighters work in a most concealed fashion. Their area of operation is not necessarily identical with their place of residence. Moreover, under state pressure the RKK-fighters typically escape. Ajak-committees, in contrast, are closely connected to the local community. In strongly infiltrated villages even non-insurgents are typically aware of the presence of insurgents, though they might not know the group’s name or all of the committee members. Some activities could not be concealed: members regularly meet, and they mobilise fellow villagers for the insurgency. BRN-Coordinate indoctrinators come to the village mosque to mobilise undecided villagers or keep up the morale of existing members - villagers have surely recognized these activities over the years. Even in villages with a strong degree of insurgent structure, there are people who view the infiltration with scepticism or even oppose it. As a consequence, COIN activities concentrate on the detection of the political wing by drawing on these potential informants and other forms of what military language refers to as “human intelligence”.

Figure 5.2. Soldiers facing village demonstrators

Source: 4th Army Area

In one BRN-Coordinate infiltrated village in Rueso, for example, the head of the local COIN unit, a charismatic, Buddhist sergeant who could speak Malay, successfully arrested members of the Ajak-committee. This success, however, took almost half a year to produce. At the beginning of his deployment, villagers refused to talk to the sergeant and his staff. After three or four months of silence the sergeant came into regular contact with the village head and other important people in the village. The sergeant used this opportunity by taking sick villagers to the hospital, providing free medical care and implementing various projects to improve farming methods and fight drug consumption among village youth - all issues that were of great concern to the villagers. Moreover, he tried to facilitate cooperation between the villagers (especially the Imam and the village head) and the district office, which the villagers had equally avoided. Escorted by the sergeant, villagers began to visit the district office more regularly and vice versa.

After an additional period of approximately 3-5 months during which the sergeant and the villagers built up trust, the village head and the Imam provided him with information on Ajak-committee members who were then arrested. The motivations to collaborate with the government in this case varied. The village head, for example, saw his power undermined by the shadowy structure of the Ajak-committee, whereas the Imam opposed the infiltration, because one of his relatives was killed by insurgents. In other cases, counterinsurgents offered money to local informants or amnesty to those who they expected to be insurgents (although this practice has no legal foundation yet). Although we still lack reliable comparable data, it seems certain that BRN-Coordinate does not provide any benefits - either for members or non-insurgents - except within the symbolic sphere.⁴⁴ In addition, fragmentation of villages and the prevalence of cliques

⁴⁴ Hideouts for insurgents on the run from government forces are a notable, though temporary, exception.

based on patronage proved to be an Achilles heel for the insurgents. In a village in Yala the followers of the local Imam entered BRN-Coordinate with him, whereas another group of clients - led by the village head and a local politician (a former PULO member) – refused to collaborate with the insurgents.

In the above-mentioned village and elsewhere a basic problem remained - the security of informants or insurgents who planned to defect. According to COIN officers, insurgents regularly killed a significant number of these people. Hence others were afraid of the retaliatory capacity of the insurgents and did not collaborate, unless a majority of the Ajak-committee would have been captured. Consider the following statement by a Malay Thai Army sergeant:

“Once we identify and arrest or at least closely survey five or six Ajak-committee members, so that everybody knows that we have information, the others typically freeze their activities, give in, or escape from the area, because they become afraid. Then they are willing to give names. But this point is hard to reach. For months we have to try to talk to them again and again, even though they shut the door in front of our faces and call back their children into their homes, if we pass by. At the beginning no one talks to us.”

Similarly, an army colonel and key architect of the village-based COIN argues:

“If only one or two Ajak-committee members collaborate with us, they will surely get killed. So the time between identifying and working with the first few members and getting a majority of them is usually the most dangerous time. We have to get them as a team. If the whole team defects from BRN, then the military wing won’t kill them, because that would turn the entire village against BRN. Then the rebels can’t put a foot in that place again. Villagers will remember.”

Another difficulty is that COIN soldiers are typically not well trained. They don’t know basic Malay and lack knowledge of crucial COIN skills (e.g. social network data analyses). Many lack the patience for mastering the breathtakingly laborious intelligence work of revealing underground networks. Hence, they are stationed in villages for months or even a year without being able to establish close relationships with villagers. And even if intelligence is gathered, false denunciations or inaccurate information have to be separated from what is helpful information. A COIN lieutenant estimated that

“[...] around 60 or 70 percent of the intelligence we get from villages is outright false, too old or otherwise unusable. Sometimes people want to earn money as informers and give us old information or rumours they picked up somewhere, sometimes the informer wants to hurt a person, with whom he has a personal problem, sometimes the insurgents want to play a trick on us.”

Still, the mere presence of COIN soldiers in the villages can negatively influence the performance of the military wing. While the Ajak-committee members are able to

observe the soldier's movements and provide the military wing with intelligence, they cannot directly support the military wing inside the village. This also seems to have an impact on the morale of BRN-Coordinate members. In Panarai district, Pattani province, RKK squads complained to leaders of the military wing that most Ajak-committees are not willing to support militant action as long as military units continue to place pressure on them on the ground. Consequently, military operations became more difficult.

In the same village rifts between the military and political wing became apparent. Although the political wing, i.e. the Ajak-committee chief, asked the military wing to cease its activities, so that the soldiers would soon leave the village, the local RKK squad insisted on continuing its operations:

“I told the military guys to stand still, because the soldiers would only cause trouble to the village. But they still placed burning tyres on the street. They also planned to burn down the local school, but I could avoid that. They always want to take action. That is what they are trained to do. It's only the political wing that considers the consequences of all actions. I wanted the komis or the sukum to solve this disunity, but no one made a decision.”

In sum, the cost of being involved in the insurgency increases when COIN units use these opportunities and overcome the above-mentioned obstacles. A basic problem for BRN-Coordinate remains: in contrast to armed groups who achieve clear territorial control, BRN-Coordinate can hardly protect its members against these measures.

As individuals flee, cooperate with government soldiers, get killed or simply refuse to work for the group, BRN-Coordinate can react in two ways:

1. If COIN units arrive in the villages BRN-Coordinate typically increases its propaganda activity. The rumour machinery is activated to mobilise villagers against the soldiers. In order to instil fear and resistance villagers are told, for example, that soldiers cause problems in whichever villages they appear. Soldiers are said to bring alcohol or flirt with the villagers' daughters. People are told gruesome stories about soldiers raping Malay girls and arresting villagers without evidence. As one insurgent remarked:

“Villagers are easy to scare. I tell them stories about disappearances or give them an article about a rape case from another village and claim that these things happen every time soldiers come to live in the Muslim villages. Then I ask them: ‘Do you think that this happened just by chance? Just imagine what will happen to us and our daughters and sons. I think we must do everything to make them leave as fast as possible!’ People here are so afraid and mistrust the state, that they easily believe us and spread the story themselves.”

Villagers are then told, for example, that it would be best not to talk to the soldiers or to accept any gifts at all. As a consequence, in many places people immediately enter their houses and closed doors and windows as soon as the soldiers passed by. Some villages

even block the entrance to their village or organise demonstrations against the deployment. These actions are partly organised, or at least inspired by insurgents. At other times, villagers arrange them autonomously.

2. To avoid detection Ajak-committees can take emergency measures, in which almost all members freeze their activities, except a few key functionaries such as the Ajak-committee chief and the head of the economic section, which are needed to collect membership fees. If members of the political wing are arrested or killed, their deputies can take their place or Ajak-committees search for substitutes. If, however, the army identifies the correct people, the chances of others taking their positions are rather low, as risks are credibly high. RKK squads can operate independently without the support of the political wing, though this is less frequent, less effective and less safe. This might explain the current decrease in daily attacks and the turn to less frequent, but more devastating car bombs. In this sense, state pressure can potentially lead to a fragmentation of BRN-Coordinate.

3. As mentioned above, potential collaborators, both members and non-members, are threatened, and, if necessary punished. A case in point is Aishya, the female member mentioned above. After she was filmed by a CCTV-camera transporting RKK-members and machine guns in her car, she surrendered herself voluntarily to the authorities before she was captured. During interrogation she denounced more than 17 fellow male and female BRN-Coordinate members.⁴⁵ The group took revenge by shooting her. Although the assassination failed to kill her, such retaliation attempts signal to the villagers and group members that insurgents are able to strike even under the eyes of security forces. This means that BRN-Coordinate sufficiently raises the cost of defection for Malays, who collaborate with the Thai state. In villages, where BRN-Coordinate can draw on informant networks, it constantly checks the number of villagers who are on the side of insurgents, supporting the government, and those who remain “neutral”. Malay targets are warned not to “cooperate with the enemy” at least three times before they are killed, often by threatening letters. Warnings can be communicated orally or by placing bags filled with rice and eggs in front of the target’s house (Human Rights Watch 2007: 60). Normally, these bags are used as offerings at local Malay funerals. In other cases the group draws on friends or relatives of the target in order to warn him, because warnings appear more credible, if they are delivered by people who are closely trusted by the target (Ajak-committee member interview, December 26, 2009).

In November 2010 Thai authorities found a one-page insurgent document in which insurgent leaders on the provincial level analysed the current strategy of Thai counterinsurgency and how to react to it. The paper briefly states the policies under

⁴⁵ Aishya knew them personally, because many RKK-fighters regularly found shelter in her village, which was already an insurgent stronghold in the 1970s.

which the Thai government attempted to de-escalate the situation: “kompromis” (compromise) and “otonomi” (autonomy). Although the document does not give a detailed analysis, its authors obviously consider them dangerous. Hence the paper orders three countermeasures: First, the group must under all circumstances maintain the motivation of its members through propaganda. Second, the organisation of members in the village level, i.e. the political wing, must be upheld. Third, the military wing must widen its operations against the Thai state to the “fullest extent possible”.

The strategy of escalation as proposed in the document and executed during BRN-Coordinate’s action on the ground is a risky affair. On the one hand, through the use of demonstrative violence, the group aims to be known and supported by its friends as well as feared by its enemies. On the other hand, if violence is applied rather indiscriminately against Malays Muslims, if the wrong individuals are targeted, the group’s acceptance and support are in danger. Usually information on such incidents spreads fast (cf. Kalyvas 2006) and collaboration by consent can turn into collaboration by coercion, which, at least in the mid and long term, undermines BRN-Coordinate’s status as a secret group as mentioned earlier. If an armed group has monopolised rule over a territory, collaboration is the only possible option because civilians have no enemy to turn to.

5.8. Conclusion

This chapter addressed the social dimension of insurgent violence by relating it back to social structure via the perception of violence. Popular justifications are essential to account for the insurgency, because without them, violent action can either hardly be endured, or remain a phenomenon at the fringe of society. Coupled with collective stigmatisation, lasting memories of wanton state violence render counterattacks meaningful in everyday life. Massacres and state repression against Malays imply a division of friend and foe, between active and reactive violence and thus form the foundation for the distinction between justified and unjustified violence.

Insurgents are well aware of these dynamics. BRN-Coordinate avoids becoming self-referential by adapting its violent practices to popular ideas of more or less acceptable forms of violence. If the group infringes these standards, due to strategic needs or because it intends to test the limits of publicly acceptable violence, it manipulates common perceptions through “information operations” such as circulating rumours. Maybe even more importantly, BRN-Coordinate uses these symbols of violence in order to escalate the conflict and undermine state power.

However, the support of and involvement in the insurgency not only depends on general support. The translation of popular support into collective action depends on a lack of state control at the micro level, just as BRN-Coordinate’s strategy rests on the state’s escalating reaction to rebel violence. Changing interpretations of anti-state symbolic

violence among parts of the 4th Army Area Command and successful counterinsurgency at the village level increased the cost of insurgent activities, at least in parts of the three provinces substantially.

6. Conclusion

Until recently the violent conflict in Southern Thailand had been captured in terms of historical oppression by the Thai state, economic and social exclusion of the Malays, as well as related questions of legitimacy. On the contrary, it was argued here that an analysis of the meanings of violence should not be reduced to the facades of popular narratives and declared intentions, because then “[...] one would become a participant in a process of staging where what is actually required is phenomenological distance.” (Elwert 2003: 268). In order to understand the enduring rebellion, the hidden channels of communication and organised violence behind such facades were explored. I tried to move beyond dichotomous notions such as nationalism vs. jihad, “new” network-like organised vs. “old” vertically organised armed groups, or claim-taking vs. silence.

To understand these ambivalences, we have to take into account the ability of insurgent groups to adjust to a changing social and political context. Like companies in a free market, they have to adapt and innovate constantly. To be successful, they must develop new violent and non-violent strategies that undermine state legitimacy, and mobilise the masses. They have to innovate their ideological repertoire in order to gain charismatic appeal, but in doing so they must stay within what is culturally acceptable. Yet the cost of failure can be much greater for them than for companies, as violence is a brutal mechanism of selection: in the best case, they simply fall by the wayside, and in the worst case, their members get killed in significant numbers without achieving the political objective.

As a reaction to the defeat of earlier Malay rebellions in Southern Thailand, BRN-Coordinate underwent a major organisational adjustment. Whereas other separatist groups gave up their old-style guerrilla fights in the 1980s and 1990s, BRN-Coordinate proved to be astonishingly capable of re-designing itself and therefore laid the foundation for the latest round of insurgency. This transformation had a twofold dimension: Firstly, instead of a full-time guerrilla hiding in the jungle, the present insurgency is based on a part-time guerrilla-cum-terrorist force in the villages, making use of a lack of state control at the local level in Southern Thailand. Secondly, the group introduced village-based mass indoctrination using a mixture of nationalism and jihadist thought that became globally prominent at the time. Under the new circumstances there was a greater need for BRN-Coordinate to protect itself against state infiltration by acting hyper-secretly, which, until today, obstructs our understanding of the conflict.

As a reaction to the demand for secrecy a social figuration emerged that combines elements of both vertical organisation with clear command and control channels, as well as network elements, which are, however, integrated into the organisation. The former allows the group to build on the professionalism and effectiveness of a division of “violent labour”, whereas the latter allows for a reduction of communication and hence protects the group against infiltration. Here recruitment and training play a crucial role,

where recruits are socialized into the use of violence, learn how to brave fear, and are familiarised with the group's roles, channels of orders, collective aims and standardized insurgent practices.

The symbolic consensus between group members coupled with disciplinary mechanisms is the basis for channels of communication as well as the acceptance of the dominance of BRN-Coordinate leaders. They also allow for a smooth transmission of general goals, strategies and tactical practices that enable a hardly visible mode of latent coordination, in which superiors do not need to give permanent orders. In other words, the coordination of this "loosely coupled" insurgent action on the ground is not motivated by material benefits or systematic coercion, but rather by a strong, emotionally loaded ideological consensus.

This combination of strong identification, vertical organisation, and network elements distinguishes BRN-Coordinate from a social movement. And although the group makes use of terrorist violence, it is distinguished from a cellular terrorist organisation by its territorial structure, i.e. the infiltration of villages.

Another key ambivalence of Southern Thailand's insurgency concerns the relation between silence and communication. BRN-Coordinate refrains from public claim-taking for its attacks, the group has no visible shadow state or visible leader. Hence communication through violence itself becomes a crucial process. Violence is linked to society through the perception of the symbolic dimension of violence, allowing for a more processual view of violence that takes into account networks of interpretation. One communicative dimension of violence concerns its tactical use. As has been shown, indiscriminate insurgent violence against Buddhist civilians and state personal aims to lure the state into ruthless repression against the Malay civilian population, which is supposed to lead into escalation, possibly internationalisation, of the conflict. More selective violence aims to demonstratively punish Malays who collaborate with the Thai government.

Beyond the instrumental dimension the communicative side of violence is connected to collectives. Insurgents aim to construct a divide between, on the one hand, the Thais, as a community of oppressive infidel colonisers and, on the other hand, the Patani Malays as a discriminated minority who legitimately claim the land of their Muslim forefathers. The border between these communities is marked with real and ascribed violence. Memories of a "Golden Age" of independence as opposed to the collective memory of the humiliating Siamese annexation are constantly recalled through the BRN-Coordinate propaganda apparatus. On the micro level the group systematically fosters fear and suspicion between villagers and government officials by manipulating rumours through local information networks and staging insurgent assaults against Malays so as to appear to be the result of government suppression. All this aims to reproduce the image of a suppressed minority, mobilise support and legitimise the use of violence. At

the same time the opposing group is dehumanised and deprived of all individuality.

The core of this process is not the fallback into a state of barbaric irrationality or the emergence of another hotspot of international terrorism. Rather, it should be understood as a reduction of social complexity through violence on the one hand and, the constitution of conscious agency by a minority that had been stigmatised successfully, on the other. The resulting meanings of violence inform and motivate different kinds of action. They attempt to drive the Malay population into making a choice as to which side of the conflict they stand, which, in turn, will influence the course of the insurgency. For the rebels themselves as well as their supporters, the images of successful attacks against the Thai state personal are the symbols motivating the virtual collective; the “warriors of God”, who stand at the core of the nation to be.

A crucial aspect of this connection between social structure and meanings of violence is the destruction and establishing of institutions. BRN-Coordinate aims at the obliteration of local institutions that form the power base of the state and inhibit the use of violence. These range from the educational system, to village heads and personal channels that solve conflicts between the Malay population and government officials. Malays and discourses that inhibit the use of violence are silenced. The virtual or imagined collective of insurgents is realised in training camps, schools, in armed squads and, especially, in insurgent village committees that reach into everyday life. At the interface between civilians and insurgents, the Ajak-committees facilitate new social bonds with separate flows of information.

BRN-Coordinate’s knowledge and manipulation of local communication is as important for its political campaign as is the superior knowledge of terrain for its military campaign. The legitimacy of violence is always contested. If violence appears to lack a common meaning, if it is perceived as righteous revenge or a restoration of collective dignity, and if it infringes certain norms of what is acceptable, violence transforms into depoliticised vandalism or pathological chaos. Not every single act, but violence in general must be plausibly ascribed to certain actors. Here BRN-Coordinate’s organisational structure, especially its political wing, is crucial for creating meaning in the midst of violence in a twofold way: First, as networks of information they enable BRN-Coordinate to identify collaborators with the government and thus send a message through selective killings that collaborators, at least if they are dangerous to the group, will be killed. Second, through the manipulation of local perceptions and the political wing’s control over the military wing, the group attempts to uphold its image of engaging in restrained use of insurgent violence. In other words, violence and discourse have a complimentary relationship in creating power as long as the group finds a balance between a mixture of brutality and restraint, conviction and coercion.

At the level of individual insurgents, the motives for joining the insurgency vary. For some members the experience of state suppression, direct or indirect, may have played a

role. Whereas some members fight a holy war in order to establish an Islamic state, others are driven by more secular ideas of Patani nationalism. The case studies also show that involvement in the insurgency entails a more profane experience of power. With regard to structural explanations, variations in the socio-economic as well as educational backgrounds do not speak for class explanations. In sum, these (preliminary) data seem to defy the idea of a single “insurgent profile”.

Different motives and long-term goals within one organisation can potentially lead to conflict. However, as long as there is no need to operationalise them and the promise of redemption for all social ills remains, BRN-Coordinate, as the carrier of these ideas, can continue to claim a special relation to the transcendental sphere. Because BRN-Coordinate is not in power and thus in a position to deliver the goods, the group can uphold their appeal in the form of promises. However, charismatic mobilisation typically has only a limited half-time. Charismatic appeal of BRN-Coordinate only lasts as long as its followers believe in it. At some point in time BRN-Coordinate must deliver the goods it promised and it must show its success in one way or another.

However, one should not overestimate the strength of BRN-Coordinate. A major weakness appears to be the fact that although BRN-Coordinate makes strategic use of communication, organisation and violence, it offers few or only very vague answers to fundamental questions that matter in the everyday life of the local population, such as drug addiction, economics or social change.

Future developments depend on the Thai state. There is more knowledge on the insurgent organisation and logic behind their practices than commonly assumed. Parts of the Thai security apparatus recognise BRN-Coordinate’s leading role and hence follow a strategy of de-escalation to counter the group’s own strategy. Much depends on how far this knowledge will be distributed in different state agencies and in how far it will be used to formulate policies accordingly. Apparently, arbitrary state violence has already subsided to some extent and hence an internationalisation of the conflict currently appears improbable. However, if major human rights violations should reoccur, any attempts to economically or culturally recognise the Malay minority would be in vain. Whether these changes will successfully undermine the image of an oppressed minority and thus render violent resistance less meaningful remains to be seen. Currently an important factor in this regard is the lack of a local public sphere that could help to counter rumours and lead to an inter-communal understanding of violence between Buddhists and Muslims.

At the same time the Thai military aims to increase state control by bridging the gap between state and society at the village level that enabled BRN-Coordinate to infiltrate the region. This would reduce possible opportunities to organise and significantly increase the cost of the insurgency. It has been argued that contrary to the static assumptions of Kalyvas, the presence of government troops at the village level in

Southern Thailand does not automatically lead to state control. Under the conditions of an insurgency, the transformation of military power into institutionalised domination and control is an open-ended, dynamic process. If neither BRN-Coordinate nor the state can ensure absolute control, the population remains caught in a zone of violence and mistrust.

Preliminary data suggest that if the counterinsurgency effectively undermines the workings of BRN-Coordinate's political wing, the group could shift towards a more military campaign that would be no longer influenced by the social context. In other words, although arbitrary state violence and a lack of state control fuelled involvement in the insurgency, especially since 2004, this does not mean that a reduction of indiscriminate state oppression, ascribed or real, would lead to a reduction in insurgent activities. For example, armed groups like the IRA or ETA reacted to soft approaches by the state with escalated violence (Mayntz 2004). Such a reaction, however, bears the risk that the group would simply maintain their influence through terror and fear, even among members and supporters. In a context where conviction shifts into coercion, the instrumental and symbolic dimensions move further apart.

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(Sascha Helbardt)